

Multi-Object Spectroscopy: 4MOST Instrumentation & Observational Analysis using CIII]

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*For my family, for your unconditional love
and for showing me the value in hard work*

I, Mark H. Cunningham, confirm that the work presented in this thesis is my own and was carried out at the Department of Physics and Astronomy at University College London between September 2020 and April 2024 under the supervision of Prof. Peter Doel and Prof. Richard Ellis. This research was also funded by UKRI STFC. Where information has been derived from other sources, I confirm that this has been indicated in the thesis.

In particular, I note these contributions:

- The work presented in Chapter 3 (and Appendix A) has been published in Cunningham et al., 2023 and was a collaborative effort conducted primarily between myself, Prof Peter Doel and Prof David Brooks in the Optical Science Laboratory (OSL) at UCL, whom without, this work would not be possible.
- The work presented in Chapter 5 (and Appendix B) has been published in Cunningham et al., 2024. The data reduction of the VANDELS data was conducted by the VANDELS team. The modelling, visualisation and identification was carried out by myself using the MPDAF3 code and PANDORA software.
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Abstract

This thesis is an interdisciplinary endeavor spanning the realms of both astronomy instrumentation and scientific inquiry. Embodying a unique fusion of spectroscopic instrument development and the analysis of spectroscopic data. This thesis details the assembly, alignment and integration of the 4MOST Wide Field Corrector (WFC). 4MOST is a new Multi-Object Spectroscopic (MOS) instrument with a hexagonal 4.2 square degree field of view, a high-multiplex fibre-fed spectrograph and a capability to simultaneously obtain spectra of ~ 2400 objects, that will be mounted at the focus of the 4m-VISTA telescope, Chile. To achieve its science goals, aligning each lens of the WFC within $\sim 100\mu m$ of the optical axis posed a significant challenge. This was addressed through contact metrology methods, supplemented by pencil beam laser probes. The thesis outlines the opto-mechanical instrumentation at UCL for aligning the lenses within their cells, detailing the assembly process and presenting comprehensive results on lens positioning and the anticipated WFC performance. Using a MOS instrument, the second half of this thesis investigates the utility of C III] $\lambda\lambda 1907, 1909$ emission, usually the brightest UV line after Ly α , as a proxy for Ly α velocity offset in analogues of reionisation era galaxies. The velocity offset of Ly α emission from its systemic redshift is an excellent tracer of conditions that may enable the escape of hydrogen ionising Lyman continuum (LyC) photons. However at $z \geq 6$, Ly α is often heavily attenuated by the neutral intergalactic medium. By utilising a sample of 52 star-forming galaxies selected from the VANDELS survey spanning a redshift of $z \sim 3 - 4$ with robust detections of the C III] emission line as well as Ly α we constrain a new correlation between C III] and Ly α velocity.

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Free Palestine, Erin Go Bragh

Sláinte

"We are all in the gutter, but some of us are looking at the stars."
- Oscar Wilde

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Impact Statement

This thesis is a unique hybrid between spectroscopic instrument development and the analysis of spectroscopic data for exploring the early universe. The core of this thesis details the assembly, alignment and integration of the 4MOST Wide Field Corrector (WFC) from September 2020 to June 2023, which is to be commissioned on the Visible and Infrared Survey Telescope for Astronomy (VISTA) telescope in Chile. The second half of the thesis outlines the use of a multi-object spectrograph in order to investigate the Epoch of Reionisation through emission line spectroscopy.

Chapter 1 describes the evolution of astronomical multi-object spectroscopy and introduces the scientific motivations behind the need for 4MOST. Chapters 2 and 3 introduce the 4MOST instrument and outlines the design specifications, instrument subsystems and science goals. These chapters focus on the metrology, assembly and alignment of the 4MOST WFC. For the instrument to meet its science goals, each lens of the WFC was aligned to be within $\sim 100\mu m$ of the optical axis. This thesis then presents the achieved lens positioning results, outlines the projected WFC performance, and details the upcoming telescope installation process for commissioning. Chapter 4 goes on to detail the subsequent testing after shipment of the WFC to AIP and the projected testing that will occur at the telescope upon delivery. Linking the instrument to science, chapter 5 discusses the use of a multi-object spectroscopic instrument survey VANDELs. This chapter contains the investigation of the semi-forbidden $C\text{III}] \lambda \lambda 1907, 1909$ doublet emission line as a valuable tool

for exploring early star-forming galaxies as a proxy for Ly α emission during epoch of reionisation. In this study, we investigate the utility of the CIII] line by comparing the equivalent widths (EW) and velocity offsets of both emission lines. Finally, chapter 6 provides an overview of the work completed in this thesis and looks to the future of multi-object spectroscopy.

The research conducted for this thesis has been showcased at both national and international conferences, including EAS, NAM and SPIE. Additionally, this work has been presented at various institutes in the UK, USA and Asia, through invited talks, as well as public engagement events such as 'Pint of Science'. Moreover, it has been utilised as teaching material for students at Banbridge Academy in Northern Ireland through the Orbyts Program, which partners scientists with schools to empower school students to undertake world-leading research.

Acronyms

4MOST	4-metre Multi-Object Spectroscopic Telescope
AAT	Anglo-Australian Telescope
ACW	Anti-Clockwise
ADC	Atmospheric Dispersion Corrector
AGN	Active Galactic Nuclei
AIP	Leibniz Institute for Astrophysics Potsdam
AIT	Assembly, Integration and Testing
CaCw	Cassegrain Cable Wrap
CDFS	Chandra Deep Field South
CGM	Circum-Galactic Medium
CIII]	Carbon III
CL	Confidence Level
CTE	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion
CTS	Cassegrain Test Stand
CW	Clockwise
DECam	Dark Energy Camera
DESI	Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument
EAS	European Astronomical Society
ELT	Extremely Large Telescope
EoR	Epoch of Reionisation
ESO	European Southern Observatory
EW	Equivalent Width
FoV	Field of View
FSTT	Focal Surface Test Tool
FWHM	Full Width Half Maximum
GMT	Giant Magellan Telescope

IBP	Inner Bearing Plate
IFU	Integral Field Unit
IGM	Inter-Galactic Medium
IR	Infrared
ISM	Inter-Stellar Medium
IWST	Image Wavefront Sensing Tool
JWST	James Webb Space Telescope
LAE	Lyman-alpha Emitters
LAMOST	Large Sky Area Multi-Object Fibre Spectroscopic Telescope
LAS	Laser Alignment System
LDS	Laser Displacement Sensor
LPBT	Laser Pencil Beam Tool
LSF	Line Spread Function
LVB	Left V-Block
Lyα	Lyman-alpha
Ly-C	Lyman-Continuum
MIRI	Mid-Infrared Instrument
MOS	Multi-Object Spectroscopy
MOONS	Multi-Object Optical and Near-infrared Spectrograph
MPDAF	MUSE Python Data Analysis Framework
MSE	Mauna Kea Spectroscopic Explorer
MSP	Main Structural Plate
MUST	Multiplexed Survey Telescope
NAM	National Astronomical Society
NIRCam	Near-Infrared Camera
NIRISS	Near-Infrared Imager and Slitless Spectrograph
NIRSpec	Near-Infrared Spectrograph
OBP	Outer Bearing Plate
PAC	Positive Away from Centre
PAS	Positive Away from Surface

PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
PTC	Positive Towards Centre
PTS	Positive Towards Surface
RTV	Room Temperature vulcanized rubber
RVB	Right V-Block
SDSS	Sloan Digital Sky Survey
SED	Spectral Energy Distribution
SFG	Star Forming Galaxies
SMR	Spherically Mounted Retroreflector
SNR	Signal to Noise Ratio
SOSS	Single-Object Slitless Spectroscopy
SPIE	Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers
STFC	Science and Technology Facilities Council
TMT	Thirty Meter Telescope
UCL	University College London
UDS	Ultra Deep Survey
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation
UV	Ultra-violet
VIMOS	Visible Multi-Object Spectrograph
VISTA	Visible and Infrared Survey Telescope for Astronomy
VLT	Very Large Telescope
WEAVE	WHT Enhanced Area Velocity Explorer
WFC	Wide Field Corrector
WFSS	Wide-Field Slitless Spectroscop
WHT	William Herschel Telescope
WST	Wide-field Spectroscopic Telescope
ZD	Zenith Distance

The obstacle is the way

Chapter 1

Introduction: A brief history of Astronomical Spectroscopy

The development of modern astronomical instrumentation stands as a pivotal factor in unraveling the cosmic puzzle, enabling astronomers to peer deeper into the universe and unlock measurements and observations of distant stars, galaxies, and black holes. Spectroscopic instruments broaden our view beyond what we can see with our eyes, granting us access to study the light emitted by these luminous celestial objects. This wealth of data obtained from such sources greatly enhances our understanding of their origins, evolutionary paths, and cosmic environments.

This chapter will outline the fundamental principals of spectroscopy, with a particular focus on Multi-Object spectroscopy and its significance in astronomical research. It will cover essential design considerations along with an overview of past and current facilities.

1.1 The basic principles of spectroscopy

In astrophysics, spectroscopy is the study of physical processes by measuring the wavelength dependence of the intensity of light emitted by astronomical objects. Light from a source is passed through a prism or grating which splits the light into its components before being focused on a detector to produce a spectrum as shown in Figure 1.1. Practically all information about astronomical objects outside the solar system originates from the analysis of electromagnetic radiation received by

telescopes. This light encapsulates intricate details regarding the composition, temperature, abundance, and motion of these astronomical objects. This astrophysical information is encoded within the spectroscopic absorption and emission features within a spectrum. An example spectra is shown in Figure 1.2, showing characteristic emission lines shown in its spectrum.

Figure 1.1: Illustration showing the fundamental principles and components of spectroscopy from a light source and a slit, which is then focused onto a detector to produce a spectrum. (Illustration created by author)

Figure 1.2: Example spectra showing 2D (top) and 1D (bottom) spectra of GN-z11 captured using the NIRSpec instrument on JWST. Notable emission lines in the spectra are highlighted as peaks. Both the 1D and 2D spectra exhibit clear visibility of emission lines. (Credit: Bunker et al., 2023)

Consequently, by examining spectral line features, we can determine the physical conditions of distant stars and galaxies, enabling us to unravel the processes by

which galaxies synthesise their chemical elements, thereby deepening our understanding of the Universe's evolution. In addition to this, there is significant physical information contained within the continuum. The continuum provides insights into the underlying stellar populations and dust content, which can be analysed to extract critical physical parameters.

Extracting Galaxy Properties from Spectral Data

Extracting information from both the continuum and spectral lines is fundamental to understanding galaxy evolution. One approach is Spectral Energy Distribution (SED) modelling, where multi-wavelength photometry is used to fit theoretical templates and infer properties such as stellar mass, dust attenuation, and star formation history. By analysing the shape of the continuum, astronomers can determine the relative contributions of young and old stars, as well as the impact of dust on observed fluxes. The ability to reconstruct past star formation activity relies on the accuracy of these models, which in turn depends on the quality and coverage of the observed data. In addition to continuum analysis, emission line diagnostics provide direct insights into star formation rates (SFRs) and metallicities. Lines such as $H\alpha$ and [OII] serve as tracers of ionising radiation from young massive stars, allowing for SFR estimates under certain assumptions about dust attenuation and initial mass function. Metallicity, an important parameter for understanding galaxy evolution, is commonly derived using ratios of strong lines such as [OIII]/[OII] (R23) or [NII]/ $H\alpha$ (N2), which depend on the ionisation state and chemical composition of the gas. The reliability of these indicators depends on the spectral resolution and sensitivity of the observations, as line blending and noise can introduce significant uncertainties.

Spectrograph Design Considerations

These scientific goals impose specific technical requirements on the design of the spectrograph. High spectral resolution is necessary to separate emission lines and measure their widths, which can provide insights into kinematics and physical

conditions. At the same time, a broad wavelength coverage is equally important to capture multiple diagnostic lines simultaneously, enabling robust estimates of star formation rates and metallicities. Achieving a balance between resolution and coverage is a major challenge in instrument design—higher resolution improves line separation but reduces the wavelength range that can be observed in a single exposure. Additionally, sensitivity considerations also dictate the need for efficient optics and detectors to maximise signal-to-noise ratios, particularly for faint high-redshift sources. These competing demands shape the architecture of modern spectrographs, determining their ability to extract meaningful astrophysical information (see Section 1.4 for a detailed discussion of key design considerations for multi-object spectrographs).

Beyond characterising physical properties, spectroscopy plays an essential role in measuring the motion of astronomical objects. By analysing shifts in spectral lines, astronomers can determine whether an object is moving towards or away from us, providing insights into galaxy dynamics, stellar kinematics, and the expansion of the universe.

Doppler Shift

The motion of objects can also be detected through spectroscopy, resulting from a phenomenon known as the *Doppler shift*. This effect describes the shift in the frequency (or wavelength) of a spectral line from that measured in a laboratory, it is given by the equation,

$$f = \left(1 + \frac{\Delta v}{c}\right) f_0, \quad (1.1)$$

where f is the observed frequency, f_0 is the rest-frame or emitted frequency, Δv is the relative velocity of the receiver with respect to the source, and c is the speed of light. This can be related to the wavelength by,

$$\frac{\Delta v}{c} = \frac{\Delta \lambda}{\lambda_0} \quad (1.2)$$

where λ_0 is the rest-frame wavelength of the transition and $\Delta \lambda$ is the change in

wavelength from the emitted wavelength to the observed wavelength.

When an object moves towards us, the wavelengths shift towards the blue end of the spectrum. Conversely, when an object moves away from us, the wavelengths shift towards the red end of the spectrum, giving rise to the term "red-shift". Red-shift, z , can be defined as:

$$z = \frac{\Delta\lambda}{\lambda_0} \quad (1.3)$$

It was through this observation that Edwin Hubble initially deduced the expansion of the Universe (Hubble, 1929). It should be noted that the formula outlined in equation 1.1 is for non-relativistic motions for which $v \ll c$.

To further understand the basics of spectroscopy, let's consider the interaction between matter and electromagnetic radiation. When atoms or molecules absorb or emit photons, they undergo transitions between energy levels. The energy difference given as ΔE , between the energy levels is related to the frequency (f) or wavelength (λ) of the absorbed or emitted radiation:

$$\Delta E = h \cdot f = \frac{hc}{\lambda}, \quad (1.4)$$

here, h is the Planck's constant, and c is the speed of light. As all atoms have discrete, quantised energy levels, when a transition occurs between two different energy levels, light for a specific wavelength is released which corresponds to the exact energy difference. Similarly, each atom exhibits a characteristic set of absorption wavelengths and indeed ionisation stages, these allow for astronomers to identify these unique fingerprints and distinguishes them from other atoms (Tennyson, 2011).

Line features

In spectroscopy, absorption lines and emission lines are two key types of spectral features that provide valuable information about the physical conditions and composition of astronomical objects. Absorption lines occur when light from a hot, continuous source passes through a cooler intervening medium, such as a gas cloud.

The atoms or molecules in the cloud absorb photons at specific wavelengths corresponding to transitions between energy levels, creating dark lines in the spectrum at those wavelengths.

In contrast, emission lines arise when atoms or molecules in a gas cloud are excited to higher energy states—often due to heating or external radiation—and subsequently emit photons as they return to lower energy states. These photons are emitted at specific wavelengths, producing bright lines in the spectrum (Figure 1.3). The pattern and intensity of these lines allow astronomers to determine the chemical composition, physical conditions, and kinematics of the emitting or absorbing medium. A common analogy for grasping these spectral features is likening them to a supermarket barcode, which uniquely identifies products in stores. Similarly, the spectrum of an astronomical object serves as a barcode, providing detailed information about the object and the atoms or molecules it contains.

Figure 1.3: Infographic illustrating the relationship between the continuous spectrum of a light source whose light is shining on gas cloud, and how absorption and emission features are produced from that gas. (*Illustration created by author*)

1.1.1 Fundamentals of ISM Physics

Ionisation and Gas Phases

To understand how atoms interact in astronomical environments, it is crucial to study the interstellar medium (ISM), as it governs the physical and chemical conditions that shape star formation and galaxy evolution. The ISM consists of gas

in three primary phases—ionised, atomic, and molecular—each with distinct temperature, density, and ionisation properties. These phases regulate the cooling and heating processes of galaxies, drive the formation of new stars, and influence the observed emission line spectra. Understanding the ISM is therefore key to addressing fundamental questions in galaxy evolution, such as how star formation is regulated, how feedback from stars and active galactic nuclei (AGN) impact gas dynamics, and how the chemical enrichment of galaxies progresses over cosmic time. Ionised gas (primarily HII regions) forms around young, massive stars, where ultraviolet (UV) radiation ionises surrounding hydrogen atoms. These regions, which typically have temperatures of 8,000–10,000K, are dense in emission lines like hydrogen recombination lines (e.g., $H\alpha$) due to high rates of electron recombination (Osterbrock et al., 2006). Atomic gas (HI regions), with temperatures around 100–10,000K, primarily comprises of neutral hydrogen, emitting a characteristic 21cm line from hyperfine transitions (this line is commonly used in cosmology to map the distribution of hydrogen) (Draine, 2011). This emission is essential for tracing cold, diffuse hydrogen clouds in galactic disks (Kulkarni et al., 1988). Lastly, molecular gas, (mostly H_2), exists in the densest and coldest regions (~ 10 –100K) and serves as the principal site for star formation (Glover et al., 2012). These varying ISM phases shape the ionisation structure of galaxies, with ionised regions producing critical emission lines that trace stellar feedback and star formation activity. Understanding these emission lines requires an in-depth examination of radiative processes, which determine how photons are generated and how they propagate in different astrophysical conditions. By exploring these processes, we can better interpret spectral observations and gain insights into the physical conditions within different ISM regions.

Radiative Processes

The production of emission lines in astrophysical spectra is governed by a variety of radiative processes. Among these, electronic transitions play a significant role in shaping the strong emission lines observed in the optical and near-infrared

(NIR) spectrum—wavelength ranges particularly relevant for modern spectroscopic instruments. However, radiative processes extend beyond electronic transitions, including molecular transitions and free-free emission, which contribute significantly at longer wavelengths. A clear understanding of these mechanisms is essential for interpreting the physical conditions of galaxies and the ISM.

In the ISM, three primary electronic radiative processes contribute to emission line formation:

Recombination: When free electrons recombine with ions (typically hydrogen or helium), the excess energy is released as photons. This process produces emission lines such as the Balmer and Lyman series in hydrogen. The recombination rate is given by:

$$R = n_e n_p \alpha_B(T), \quad (1.5)$$

(with n_e and n_p as the electron and proton densities, and $\alpha_B(T)$ as the recombination coefficient) is influenced by the medium's temperature (Osterbrock et al., 2006).

Collisional Excitation: Free electrons can also excite atoms or ions through inelastic collisions. These excited states eventually relax, emitting photons with energies characteristic of the species involved. The probability of collisional excitation is given by:

$$q_{ij} = \Omega_{ij} \frac{e^{-\Delta E/kT}}{\sqrt{T}}, \quad (1.6)$$

where Ω_{ij} is the collision strength, ΔE is the energy difference between states, and T is temperature (Draine, 2011).

Radiative De-excitation: Atoms in excited states can spontaneously emit photons as they transition to lower energy levels. This mechanism is responsible for “forbidden” lines commonly observed in low-density nebulae, where collisional de-excitation is rare. The emission coefficient is given by:

$$I_{ji} = n_j A_{ji} h\nu_{ji}, \quad (1.7)$$

where n_j is the density of ions in the excited state j , A_{ji} is the spontaneous emission coefficient, h is Planck's constant, and ν_{ji} is the transition frequency (Spitzer, 1978). Together, these processes provide diagnostics of temperature, density, and ionisation conditions within galaxies, making them central to spectroscopic analysis.

Beyond Electronic Transitions

While electronic transitions dominate in optical and NIR, other radiative mechanisms contribute to emission at different wavelengths:

Molecular Line Emission: Molecular transitions, such as those in CO and H_2 , result from vibrational and rotational energy level changes and are particularly important in infrared and millimetre wavelengths.

Free-Free Emission (Bremsstrahlung): Arising from electron-ion interactions in ionised gas, free-free emission produces a continuum spectrum that dominates in hot plasma environments, such as HII regions and AGN.

The focus of this discussion is on electronic transitions because they produce the strongest emission lines in the optical and NIR, the primary wavelength regimes targeted by instruments discussed in this thesis. However, a complete picture of ISM emission requires consideration of these additional processes.

Selection Rules and Line Diagnostics

Although the primary radiative processes—recombination, collisional excitation, and radiative de-excitation—define how atoms and ions emit photons, the likelihood of these emissions depends on the specific atomic transitions involved. Here, the distinction between 'allowed,' semi-forbidden, and forbidden transitions becomes essential, as these categories shape the types of emission lines observed under various conditions in the ISM. Understanding these transitions further illuminates how specific lines, such as Lyman alpha ($Ly\alpha$) and Carbon III (C III), can serve as diagnostics for physical properties within galaxies. *Normal 'Allowed' Transitions* refer to transitions between quantum states that exhibit relatively high

transition probabilities and short lifetimes, resulting in strong resonance lines such as $\text{Ly}\alpha$. In contrast, *Forbidden Lines* arise from transitions between states with low transition probabilities due to specific selection rules, which make these transitions less likely to occur. These lines, such as those for [OIII] and [SII], are typically observed in low-density environments such as nebulae, where the long lifetimes of the excited states allow for their detection. Another category, *Semi-Forbidden Lines*, such as C III] (C III] $\lambda\lambda$ 1907,1909), possess moderate transition probabilities. These lines are particularly useful in low-density, ionised regions where collisional de-excitation is infrequent, allowing for their observation in environments like high-redshift galaxies. The diagnostic utility of the semi-forbidden C III] line in reionisation studies makes it an important indicator of ionisation conditions and the physical properties of the ISM in these early cosmic epochs. The relative intensities of different emission lines provide crucial insights into the physical conditions of the interstellar medium (ISM) and their host galaxies. For instance, they reveal information about ionisation states, electron densities, and gas temperatures, while line widths can probe the kinematics of the emitting gas. Strong recombination lines like $\text{H}\alpha$ trace recent star formation, while forbidden lines such as [OIII] and [SII] highlight ionised gas in HII regions and supernova remnants. Additionally, semi-forbidden lines like C III] $\lambda\lambda$ 1907,1909 offer a window into the ionisation conditions of high-redshift galaxies, providing critical clues about the reionisation epoch (further discussed in Chapter 5).

However, interpreting these lines is complex because multiple physical parameters can affect their properties. Spectroscopic observations therefore rely on diagnostic tools such as the BPT diagram (Baldwin et al., 1981) to distinguish between star-forming regions and AGN. Measuring equivalent widths is another key approach for quantifying line strengths independently of flux calibration uncertainties. For example, Figure 1.2 shows a representative spectrum where prominent emission lines such as $\text{Ly}\alpha$, C III], and [OIII] can be identified, illustrating how these features appear in practice.

1.1.2 Equivalent Width

As discussed in Section 1.1, identifying spectral lines—both emission and absorption—allows us to determine the composition of astrophysical objects. Beyond identification, measuring the relative strengths of different absorption and emission features provides further insight into the physical properties of these systems, such as temperature, density, and chemical abundances. One way to achieve this is by quantifying the *equivalent width* of the absorption or emission features. Equivalent width (EW) is the measure of the area between the spectral feature and the continuum in a normalised spectrum of the object (Figure 1.4) and can be thought of as the strength of the feature relative to the continuum, given by:

$$EW = \int \frac{F_c - F_\lambda}{F_c} d\lambda, \quad (1.8)$$

where F_c represents the underlying continuum intensity, and F_λ represents the intensity of the actual spectrum (the line and continuum). This equation can be applied to either emission or absorption, but when applied to emission, typically the value of EW is negative, and so the absolute value is used. Equivalent width is particularly useful for comparing the strengths of spectral features across different objects or time periods, for identifying the presence of specific elements or molecules, and for studying the dynamics of interstellar and intergalactic gas along the line of sight. Equivalent width serves as a practical measure due to the variability in the shapes of spectral features.

Instruments and telescopes can influence the accuracy of EW measurements due to spectral resolution and the line spread function (LSF). While EW is theoretically invariant under changes in spectral resolution, blending of nearby lines and low signal-to-noise (S/N) can lead to practical difficulties in measuring it. At lower spectral resolutions, the broader LSF may cause line blending, making it harder to distinguish individual features, particularly in crowded spectral regions. Additionally, reduced S/N can obscure the wings of broader lines, complicating accurate EW measurements. High-resolution spectra help mitigate these issues by preserving well-defined line profiles and reducing the chance of blending, whereas

low-resolution data is more prone to confusion and measurement uncertainties.

To combat this, the LSF is typically determined by observing calibration sources such as arc lamps or stars with well-known, narrow absorption or emission lines. Theoretical spectra are then convolved with the LSF to model the instrument's broadening effect. **Corrections are applied to the measured EW to account for instrumental broadening effects, including the spectrograph's LSF and wavelength-dependent response. These corrections are typically derived by observing standard stars with well-characterised EWs, allowing for an empirical calibration that compensates for resolution-induced biases and throughput variations.**

For the work carried out in this thesis and the use of VANDELS data (Chapter 5), see Garilli et al. (2021).

Figure 1.4: The area of a spectral line, measured above or below the continuum level, corresponds to a rectangular line profile with the same area and equivalent width, shown as the shaded region. (*Illustration created by author*)

1.2 Types of Spectroscopy

There are multiple types of ways to measure emission lines through spectroscopic instruments as outlined in Figure 1.5. The James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) for example makes use of multiple of these techniques throughout its instruments onboard, each with their own advantages and disadvantages.

- **Wide-Field Slitless Spectroscopy:** In this method, no slit is used, allowing

spectra to be collected over a large field of view. This makes it highly efficient for surveys of wide regions of the sky, especially for studying populations of galaxies or stars. However, the lack of a slit can lead to overlapping spectra from adjacent objects, complicating data reduction. This technique is particularly useful for photometric redshift surveys or identifying spectral lines over large areas. JWST's NIRISS (Near-Infrared Imager and Slitless Spectrograph) uses this technique in its SOSS (Single Object Slitless Spectroscopy) and WFSS (Wide-Field Slitless Spectroscopy) modes, particularly for exoplanet transit studies and galaxy surveys.

Pros: Efficient for large area surveys, can observe multiple sources simultaneously.

Cons: Spectral overlap from neighboring objects, lower resolution.

- **Single-Object Slitless Spectroscopy:** This method focuses on a single target, capturing its spectrum without the need for a slit. It is effective for cases where the target is isolated or bright enough to dominate the field, reducing the risk of contamination from nearby sources. It simplifies the setup since no precise slit positioning is required, but the absence of background rejection means that stray light or objects in the same line of sight can affect the data quality. This method is ideal for exoplanet atmospheres and distant galaxy studies, where the target is sufficiently isolated. JWST's NIRCам (Near-Infrared Camera) employs this technique for exoplanet observations.

Pros: No need for precise alignment, useful for isolated objects.

Cons: Cannot block out background light, leading to contamination.

- **Slit Spectroscopy:** In slit spectroscopy, light from the target passes through a narrow slit before being dispersed into a spectrum. The slit helps isolate the target, reducing contamination from nearby objects and background light. This leads to higher spectral resolution, making it suitable for detailed studies of individual objects, such as stars, nebulae, or distant galaxies. However, it has a limited field of view, and precise slit alignment is required. JWST's NIRSpec (Near-Infrared Spectrograph) employs slit spectroscopy for high-

resolution studies of galaxies, star formation regions, and stellar populations.

Pros: High spectral resolution, reduces contamination from nearby sources.

Cons: Limited field of view, requires precise alignment.

- **Multi-Object Spectroscopy:** MOS allows simultaneous observation of multiple objects by using multiple slits, fibres or microshutters. This technique is highly efficient for observing galaxy clusters, star-forming regions, or other fields containing many targets. Each slit, fibre or microshutter can be positioned on a different object, allowing simultaneous acquisition of multiple spectra. The main challenge lies in the complexity of the instrument design and setup. JWST's NIRSpec can observe up to hundreds of objects simultaneously with its microshutter array, making it ideal for galaxy evolution and dark matter studies in large fields. *This thesis will focus on a MOS instrument, see next section.*

Pros: Increases observational efficiency by targeting multiple objects at once.

Cons: Complex instrument design and setup, limitations in field density.

- **Integral Field Unit Spectroscopy:** IFU spectroscopy provides a 3D data cube by capturing a spectrum at each pixel of a 2D field. This is particularly useful for studying extended objects like galaxies, nebulae, or complex regions with spatial and spectral variation. IFUs allow astronomers to analyse the spatial structure of an object alongside its spectral information, providing detailed insights into velocity fields, chemical composition, and temperature distributions. The drawback is the large data volume generated and the complexity of data reduction. JWST's NIRSpec and MIRI (Mid-Infrared Instrument) use IFUs for spatially resolved spectroscopy of galaxies and star-forming regions.

Pros: Provides spatial and spectral information simultaneously, ideal for extended objects.

Cons: Generates large data volumes, complex data reduction.

- **Time-Series Spectroscopy** This technique involves taking spectra over time

to observe changes in the spectral features of a target, allowing the study of dynamic processes such as variable stars, stellar pulsations, and exoplanet transits. It is particularly useful for characterising time-dependent phenomena like changes in an exoplanet's atmosphere during transit or the variability in a star's emission. While it provides crucial temporal information, it is limited by the requirement of continuous observation and the transient nature of the events being studied. JWST's NIRISS and NIRCams employ time-series spectroscopy for monitoring exoplanet atmospheres and stellar variability.

Pros: Ideal for studying dynamic or time-variable phenomena.

Cons: Requires continuous, often long-duration observations.

In this thesis, we will focus on the use of Multi-Object Spectroscopy.

Figure 1.5: Different techniques of spectroscopy utilised throughout astronomy to generate a spectrum. *Credit: NASA/ESA/STScI.*

1.3 Multi-Object Spectroscopy

As astronomers' ambitions expand and technology progresses, there's a growing demand to observe more of the night sky. As previously discussed, various forms of spectroscopy have enabled astronomers to gather detailed information from celestial objects. Building on that, since the late 1970s, the development of MOS has revolutionised the field by allowing astronomers to efficiently observe multiple objects simultaneously, using either multiple slits or optical fibres. The advantages of MOS are twofold; Efficiency and Survey Capability. As mentioned in the previous

section, MOS enables the simultaneous observation and measurement of multiple astrophysical objects within a single field of view, significantly increasing observational efficiency. This allows astronomers to collect spectral data for a larger number of targets in less time, facilitating large-scale surveys. The capability to efficiently gather data across the sky is invaluable for mapping the distribution of galaxies, studying large-scale structures in the universe, and identifying rare and transient phenomena.

A disadvantage of MOS is its potentially lower instrument throughput compared to other spectroscopic techniques, particularly when observing many faint objects. This can result in longer exposure times and reduced signal-to-noise ratios for individual targets. Additionally, MOS requires precise alignment for each target, the complexity of positioning multiple slits or optical fibres can limit field coverage, especially in densely populated regions where objects are closely spaced. The challenges associated with fibre placement, such as alignment accuracy and potential crosstalk between fibres, also contribute to the limitations of this method.

The first MOS instrument of its kind was developed in 1979 at Steward Observatory. Named MEDUSA (due its array of optical fibres that resembled the hair of the figure from Greek mythology), it pioneered the use of optical fibres to direct light towards a spectrograph (Hill et al., 1980). By deploying optical fibres across the field of view in the same exposure, multiple targets could be observed at once. MEDUSA used an aperture plate that was pre-drilled with holes corresponding to the positions of the target objects on the sky with the fibres 'plugged' into the plate (example of a plug-in-plate used at the Anglo-Australian Telescope (AAT) shown in Figure 1.6). The plates required replacement after each target set due to being uniquely drilled for specific observations, thus posing drawbacks. Nevertheless, this technology began to establish itself as the standard for new ground-based spectroscopic instruments and is still currently in use on the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) at the Apache Point Observatory in New Mexico. Further developments saw improvements to the fibre optic design and are described in the next section.

An alternative type of MOS instrumentation uses slit spectroscopy. Tradition-

Figure 1.6: (a) Fibres plugged into a plate at the AAT during the 1980's. (b) Demonstrating how astronomers would individually position each fibre into the corresponding pre-drilled hole for observation. (*Images courtesy of Richard Ellis and Ellis (2022)*)

ally a spectrograph uses a rectangle single slit entrance, however for multi-slit, a metal plate with many individual 'slit-lets' allows light to travel through and each produce a spectrum. The advantage of this type of MOS instrumentation over fibres is that it can provide measurements for the adjacent sky signal that is useful for sky subtraction (Allington-Smith et al., 1990). The challenge with using slits is to 'pack-in' the best arrangement of slit in one mask, which is a unique set of constraints compared to the fibre optimisation. Highlighted in Figure 1.7 is an example of a multi-slit data acquired using the VIMOS survey providing over 200 individual spectra (Le Fèvre et al., 2003). With multi-slit spectroscopy the quantity of detectable objects is restricted by both the dimensions of the image detector and spectral overlap.

Figure 1.7: Multi-slit data captured with VIMOS during its inaugural observation in February 2002. Across these two masks, over 220 objects were simultaneously observed, achieving a spectral resolution of approximately $R \sim 250$ (Le Fèvre et al., 2003).

1.4 Design Consideration of Fibre-fed MOS Systems

When designing your MOS instrument, there are several key considerations to keep in mind. First, it is important to determine whether a fibre-based system is the most suitable option for your scientific objectives. Second, selecting the appropriate fibre system is crucial to ensure optimal performance. Third, optimising the number of positioners and the size of the field of view is essential for maximising observational efficiency. Finally, considerations regarding image size—such as the design of the WFC, the integration of an ADC, and the maximum zenith angle—are critical for achieving high-quality spectral data. These factors collectively shape the functionality and effectiveness of the MOS instrument. Naturally, your scientific requirements play a significant role in shaping these decisions and largely dictate the design of the instrument. It's a balancing act between costs, manufacturability, and meeting the minimum science requirements.

1.4.1 Fibre optic positioners

Developments to the type of fibre system used in MOS instruments saw an improvement in how the fibres were placed and moved. The objective of a fibre optic positioner is to place the fibre end to efficiently transmit maximal light into each

fibre, ensuring that all pertinent information reaches the spectrograph without loss. The next iteration of MEDUSA, the MX spectrograph (Hill et al., 1986), saw a replacement of the pre-drilled aperture plates with a computer-controlled system of actuators. These actuators enabled the fibre ends to be directed to any position in the focal plane. The actuators resembled 'fishing-rods' projecting radially into the telescope's field of view. Each actuator has the ability to move in both radial (r) and angular (θ) directions about its pivot at the edge of the field, with a fibre attached to its free end (Watson, 1983).

The evolution continued with the rapid adoption of automated fibre positioners (Parry et al., 1988), leading to exploration of various iterations of automated positioning systems. With each type of positioning system, there is a set of factors that are taken into account to determine which is best, these include positioning accuracy, positioning speed, closest approach, target density and clustering ability to name a few. Below, is a concise overview of the diverse automated fibre positioning techniques currently employed in astronomy and MOS instruments.

- **Tilting Spine positioner** - Each fibre is encased within a sturdy carbon fibre tube, capable of tilting freely around a ball joint located at one end. This tube is balanced around the ball joint to create a passive spine assembly. Subsequently, the spine is inserted through the centre of a cylindrical piezoelectric actuator assembly and secured in place magnetically. Each spine's actuator assembly adjusts the ball's surface, tilting the spine and moving its tip in small steps. The step size depends on the drive waveform's amplitude, the stepping frequency, and direction on electrode activation. These spines typically have a large patrol radius. One notable characteristic of spine positioners is their high target allocation yield. This is made possible by each fibre's extensive and overlapping patrol area, coupled with a minimal exclusion radius surrounding the fibre tip. Due to the nature of the tilting spines an unavoidable weakness is the optical loss suffered due to non-telecentricity and defocus offsets when the spines are tilted. See section 2.4.1.2 for more details on AESOP. (e.g. FMOS-Echidna, 4MOST AESOP) (Brzeski et al.,

2018; Gillingham et al., 2000; Smedley et al., 2018)

- **Pick and Place** - Pick-and-place positioners typically consist of mechanical fingers mounted on a robotic gantry above a magnetic field plate. The robot sequentially lifts fibres and deposits them at the desired locations, particularly suitable for observing highly-clustered fields. One drawback of pick-and-place positioners is the relatively slow pace of field placement of the fibres due to the sequential nature of the positioning process. To alleviate this problem some systems use several robots and implement a "tumbler" system where there are two focal planes that can be switched so the fibres can be positioned while the other is on-sky. (e.g. WEAVE, AUTOFIB) (Dalton et al., 2012; Parry et al., 1986)
- **Theta-Phi positioners** - Theta-phi positioners were first developed for LAMOST and have since been utilised on DESI (Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument) and PFS (Prime Focus Spectrograph). The positioning of the fibre ends can be adjusted to various positions through the manipulation of rotation angles governed by two motors, which is where the 'theta-phi' name comes from. This mechanism is also known as the double-revolving fibre positioning unit. Every positioner is limited to placing the fibre end within its designated patrol area. The maximum radius of this patrol area is determined by summing the lengths of the alpha and beta arms. The alpha and beta arms refer to the links connecting the first rotation axis to the second rotation axis and from the second rotation axis to the fibre end, respectively. (e.g LAMOST, DESI, PFS, MOONS) (Schubnell et al., 2018; Xing et al., 1998; Zhang et al., 2024)
- **Roaming positioners (Starbugs)** - Starbugs are miniature piezoelectric 'walking' robot devices capable of parallel operation to position optical fibres, across a telescope's focal plane. These robots are comprised of two concentric piezo-ceramic tubes that move in micron-sized steps. When a voltage is applied, the tubes bend and flex, making the robots move. These have

been specifically designed for the Giant Magellan Telescope (GMT) but have not yet been implemented. (e.g TAIPIN, MANIFEST) (Gilbert et al., 2012; Goodwin et al., 2010; Kuehn et al., 2014)

1.4.2 Optical Correction Systems

MOS instruments are designed to simultaneously observe celestial objects across a wide field of view (FoV). However due to the complex nature of optical systems, distortion and image aberrations can occur particularly towards the edges of the field of view. In the design of optics, a spot diagram serves as a visual tool used to assess how well a lens or optical system focuses light onto a target area. It helps evaluate the quality of lenses by showing any imperfections in the focal point, like spherical, astigmatic, or coma aberrations, which affect image clarity (Figure 1.8 and 1.9). These aberrations are outlined below:

- **Coma** - Coma's occur when light rays passing through different parts of the lens or optical system do not converge to a single point, resulting in blurring and asymmetrical distortion in the image.
- **Astigmatism** - Astigmatism occurs when light rays traveling in two perpendicular planes converge at different focal points.
- **Spherical** - Spherical aberrations arise when light rays from the edge of an optic focuses to different points than rays close to centre. This causes multiple focal points to form along the optical axis.
- **Chromatic** - Chromatic aberration occurs because different colors of light refract by different amounts when they pass through an optical system, resulting in color fringing or blurring in the image.

However, a common mistake is simplifying spot diagrams to just spot size, ignoring other issues like asymmetries. Since optical systems are complex, spots represent many light rays converging onto the image plane. So, it's important to consider the overall shape and distribution of spots to fully understand how the optical system behaves.

Figure 1.8: Zemax test spot diagram for the 4MOST WFC over the range 390-950 nm for field angles over the range 0° to 1.25° at Zenith angles 55° , 45° , 30° , 15° , 0° , respectively configurations 1 to 5. The circle diameters correspond to $85 \mu\text{m}$ which is the fibre core diameter. (Figure taken from Azais et al., 2016)

MOS instruments are specifically designed to incorporate optical elements and correction systems that can mitigate these effects to ensure that objects across the field of view are sharp and accurate. Wide Field Correctors (WFC) and Atmospheric Dispersion Correctors (ADC) are optical systems designed to enable astronomers to gather spectroscopic data from multiple objects in a single observation, without distortion, across a wide field of view. They help facilitate large-scale surveys, from mapping the distribution of galaxies in the universe to studying transient events.

Figure 1.9: Optical aberrations (a) Coma, (b) Astigmatic, (c) Spherical, and (d) Chromatic. *Figure adapted from MeetOptics* ¹

1.4.2.1 WFC

The concept of corrector elements in optical telescopes dates back to 1913 when Sampson (1913) introduced the first corrector for Newtonian Telescopes. Significant advancements came later in 1968 when Charles Wynne (Wynne, 1968) developed a refined triple-element lens corrector, departing from the standard four-lens systems of the time. Since then, the integration of correctors has become integral to survey instruments, particularly in wide-field telescopes.

The correctors placement varies depending on the telescope type. For instance, in the case of 4MOST, which this thesis outlines, the WFC is positioned at the Cassegrain focus (more details in chapter 2 and 3), other positions include Prime focus, positioned at the focal point in front of the primary mirror, and Nasmyth focus, positioned off the side of the telescope, typically after a tertiary mirror. A comprehensive overview of different corrector systems for wide-field telescopes can also be found in Terebizh (2011).

It is essential to note that wide-field optical telescopes inherently require the inclusion of refractive corrector elements to optimise their performance.

Reflective Wide Field Correctors are generally not employed in astronomical

instruments due to several key limitations that arise when attempting to achieve large fields of view with minimal optical aberrations. Reflective systems, while effective for narrow fields, tend to introduce significant distortions such as astigmatism and field curvature across wide fields. These aberrations are more pronounced compared to those encountered in refractive WFCs. Furthermore, reflective WFCs typically require more complex and bulky designs, making them challenging to align and manufacture for wide-field applications. As a result, refractive WFCs are often preferred in modern telescope systems, offering a more practical solution for achieving high image quality over large fields of view.

1.4.2.2 ADC

The atmosphere acts as a prism, refracting incoming light, a phenomenon known as atmospheric dispersion (Filippenko, 1982). This effect becomes more pronounced as the source's zenith distance increases. Zenith distance is not a physical distance, but rather an angular measurement representing the angle between a celestial object and the point directly overhead (the zenith) as observed from a specific location on Earth's surface. As light travels through the atmosphere, dispersion increases, especially when observing objects low in the sky at high zenith angles. An ADC is essential in fibre spectroscopy, where observing a broad range of wavelengths simultaneously is required, as it compensates for this atmospheric dispersion.

The primary objective of any corrector is to maximize the capture of light, ensuring optimal transmission through optical fibres or slits, therefore the corrector must fulfill its image quality criteria even in the presence of this atmospheric dispersion. Without proper correction, this dispersion could result in throughput loss at the fibre. For multi-object observations across a wide field, it's crucial to account for the diverse effects of differential refraction. Differential refraction occurs when light from an astronomical object is refracted by the Earth's atmosphere by different amounts depending on its wavelength, causing a slight separation of colours (blue light is refracted more than red light). In multi-slit systems without an ADC, careful consideration of slit angles is essential to ensure that all wavelengths are properly admitted. Parallactic angle refers to the angle between the object being

observed and the horizon, measured along the vertical circle passing through the object. Aligning observations with the parallactic angle can minimise the impact of atmospheric dispersion, ensuring optimal performance. This is especially important in systems like the VIMOS instrument, as recommended by Cuby et al. (1998).

An atmospheric dispersion corrector can be constructed in multiple ways, most commonly done with a pair of wedged prisms. The setup involves two wedge prisms rotated in opposing directions, as depicted in Figure 1.10. In this setup, the rotation of one prism refracts the light. Conversely, the diagram illustrates the prism orientation for achieving maximum ray angle deviation. To ensure angular displacements remain within the vertical plane, both prisms must rotate in opposing directions.

Figure 1.10: Schematic showing how an ADC works with two wedged lenses, in their maximum and minimum beam deflection positions. (*Illustration created by author*)

ADCs are usually composed of lens doublets, which is a type of lens assembly made up of two simple lenses which can be either air-spaced (like that in WEAVE (Dalton et al., 2016)) or cemented (like that of 4MOST, *see section 3.2.2*). When a positive focal length of one type of glass is combined with a weaker negative lens, it results in the correction of certain aberrations, leading to improved optical performance.

Other types of ADC have also been proposed such as a 'Compensating Lateral' ADC (Saunders et al., 2014). The concept describes shifting a weakly powered spherical lens laterally that mimics the effect of inserting a thin prism into

the beam, with the prism angle proportional to the displacement. By adjusting another lens similarly, it can counteract the tilt and astigmatism caused by the initial displacement. Together, these adjustments provide variable strength atmospheric dispersion correction. A version of a laterally shifting ADC is found on the PFS on the Subaru telescope, a Japanese 8.2m telescope based in Hawaii.

As with the design of any instrument, cost is a significant consideration. Additionally, the availability and manufacture of large glass blanks must be carefully factored in (Glass blanks are large, unshaped pieces of high-quality optical glass that serve as the raw material for crafting precision lenses, mirrors, or other optical components). This can often limit the types of optical systems and fields of view that can be feasibly considered. Currently the maximum size of glass blank available are in the range of 1-1.5m in diameter ².

1.5 Current Facilities

Wide-field MOS has been highlighted as a high priority of European astronomy (Astronet Strategic Plan for European Astronomy Roadmap 2022 – 2035) ³. An ESO 'Future of Multi-Object Spectroscopy Working Group Report' by Ellis et al. (2017) also provides a detailed summary exploring the future of multiplexed and wide-field surveys. An overview of current facilities can be seen in Table 1.1 where we compare their main properties. However, many current 8-10 metre class telescopes typically offer a limited field of view, which renders 4-metre class telescopes notably appealing for wide-field instruments (Balcells et al., 2010; Ellis et al., 2017). The conversion of 4-metre telescopes into wide-field systems primarily stems from the availability of these telescopes, which have been surpassed with the emergence of 8-10-metre class telescopes. Additionally, the sturdy construction of older 4-metre telescopes enables them to support the substantial additional WFC optics to some extent. With current and upcoming 4-metre class instruments such as DESI, WEAVE, and 4MOST there is a new era for wide-field instruments with lots of exciting opportunities on the horizon for follow-up spectroscopy given the explo-

²<https://www.schott.com/shop/medias/schott-tie-41-large-optical-glass-blanks-eng.pdf>

³<https://www.astronet-eu.org>

sion of data from the many ambitious surveys including Gaia, eROSITA LSST and Euclid..

Table 1.1: An updated summary of telescopes and MOS instruments of that in McConnachie et al., 2016. The table shows the main properties of current and upcoming instruments and is sorted by Class type.

Facility / Instrument	First light	Aperture (MI in m)	Field of View (sq. deg)	Etendue	Multiplexing	Wavelength coverage (μm)	Spectral resolution (approx)	IFU	Dedicated facility
4 metre									
Guo Shoujing / LAMOST	2008	4	19.6	246	4000	0.37-0.90	1000-10000	No	Yes
AAT / HERMES	2015	3.9	3.14	37.5	392	windows	28000, 50000	No	No
Mayall / DESI	2018	4	7.1	89.2	5000	0.36-0.98	4000	No	Yes
WHT / WEAVE	2024	4	3.14	39.5	1000	0.37-1.00	5000	Yes	Yes
VISTA / 4MOST	2024	4	4.2	52.8	1600	3 windows	20000	No	Yes
					800	0.37-0.95	4000-8000	No	Yes
						3 windows	18000-20000		
8 metre									
Subaru / PFS	2024	8.2	1.25	65.9	2400	0.38-1.26	2000-5000	No	No

Etendue is defined as the product of the area of the telescope's entrance pupil and the solid angle over which it collects light.

1.6 4MOST vs VIMOS

In this thesis, I explore a unique combination of astronomical instrumentation and observational analysis. Focussing on two main instruments; 4MOST and the VIMOS instrument. Each plays a pivotal role: the WFC, which was built for the 4MOST project and will be discussed in detail in Chapter 2 & 3, is optimised for wide-field surveys and designed to capture expansive spatial data for large-scale spectroscopic studies. In contrast, VIMOS, which is covered more deeply in Chapter 5, was integral to earlier studies of galaxy evolution and targeted spectroscopy, allowing for high-resolution observations critical for emission line analysis.

While 4MOST facilitates high-throughput, multi-object spectroscopy on a wide field, VIMOS provides targeted, high-resolution analysis of compact fields, making each instrument uniquely suited to different scales of observational inquiry. By evaluating both in this thesis, a dual perspective is established that takes advantage of the strengths of each instrument, advancing both instrumental and observational astrophysics through a complementary lens.

1.7 Thesis Aims and Future Outlook

This introductory chapter lays the foundation by emphasising the pivotal role of spectroscopy in astronomy and highlighting how MOS capabilities have transformed our understanding of the Universe. Through spectroscopic techniques, we extract crucial information from light, revealing the properties, compositions, and dynamics of distant astronomical objects. Multi-object spectrometers have been essential in contemporary optical research, enabling efficient observation of large samples simultaneously and thus advancing the fields of observational astronomy.

The chapter includes a brief historical overview, tracing the development of MOS instruments since the 1970s, and exploring how different fibre optic systems have been tailored to address specific scientific needs. As MOS instruments evolve, advances in fibre positioning, WFCs, and ADCs have become crucial for optimal data quality and functionality, shaping the design of instruments at leading facilities today.

The development of wide-field correctors and MOS instruments addresses some of the most profound challenges in modern astronomy. WFCs enable large telescopes to observe wide fields of view with minimal optical distortion, significantly enhancing survey efficiency and depth. By enabling simultaneous observations of numerous objects across wide fields, MOS instruments maximise data collection efficiency. This capability allows astronomers to study large-scale cosmic structures, galaxy evolution, the intergalactic medium (IGM), and more.

One of the primary scientific challenges these tools aim to address is understanding how the Universe evolved to its current state. A key question is identifying the sources of cosmic reionisation—the process that ionised the hydrogen in the early Universe (discussed in Chapter 5). Although star-forming galaxies and quasars are known to contribute, it remains unclear which was the dominant source. MOS surveys, like those conducted with 4MOST, will provide an unprecedented ability to assemble statistical samples of galaxies and AGN across a broad range of redshifts ($z < 6$). While not directly probing the epoch of reionisation, these 4MOST surveys will be essential for tracing the evolution of AGN and their role in shaping the ionisation state of the intergalactic medium (IGM) over cosmic time. By capturing spectra of numerous objects simultaneously, MOS instruments enable the detection of emission lines linked to ionising photons, offering insights into AGN feedback, IGM ionisation history, and the transition from the reionisation era to later cosmic epochs.

The lessons learned from the setup of 4MOST will lay the foundation for even larger projects on next-generation telescopes like the Extremely Large Telescope (ELT) and the Wide-Field Spectroscopic Telescope (WST). The experience gained in optimising wide-field surveys, managing complex fibre positioning systems, and developing data reduction techniques with 4MOST will inform best practices for these future observatories, enabling them to handle larger fields of view and even higher spectral resolution. This evolution from current MOS surveys to larger, more powerful telescopes will be crucial for investigating fundamental questions about the early universe.

By integrating technological advancements and scientific inquiry, this thesis addresses these challenges head-on. The first part of the thesis is dedicated to the engineering of the 4MOST WFC, detailing the alignment, integration, assembly, and testing processes. The second part focuses on observational analysis, using the VIMOS instrument to examine emission lines from star-forming galaxies at $3 < z < 4$. Specifically, this work investigates whether the equivalent width of C III] can serve as a proxy for Ly α emission, providing insights into probing the reionisation era where direct Ly α measurements are limited. By combining instrumentation development with observational study, this thesis aims to advance our understanding of reionisation and galaxy evolution in the early Universe. By establishing the connection between technological advancements of instrumentation and scientific outcomes, it becomes evident that the trajectory of astronomical research will be heavily influenced by our capacity to develop state-of-the-art instrumentation. This thesis aims to bridge both aspects of astrophysics research.

Chapter 2

4MOST

Desert Vista

The rugged terrain of the Chilean Atacama Desert with the VISTA Telescope depicted in the middle ground, where the 4MOST instrument is destined.

(Image Credit: ESO/A. Tudorică)

2.1 The 4MOST Instrument

As technology and engineering continue to make great leaps, it is of no surprise that in the last decade there have been incredible strides in optical and infra-red imaging, with follow-up spectroscopy, and telescope updates becoming the status quo. This has led to large investment into Multi-Object Spectroscopic facilities.

4MOST is a new spectroscopic survey facility that will provide the highest target multiplex on the largest field of view in the Southern Hemisphere (de Jong et al., 2012). The instrument is to be installed on the 4.1m Visible and Infrared Survey Telescope for Astronomy (VISTA) (Sutherland et al., 2015) of the European Southern Observatory (ESO), located at the Paranal Observatory in Chile.

2.2 Science Goals

This unique survey facility will enable many exceptional science cases which can be broken into galactic and extragalactic science surveys. The primary goal of 4MOST is to have a facility that caters to a multitude of science cases and under the philosophy that it is not just an instrument but a survey facility, with the core values being that, (a) 4MOST runs all the time, (b) 4MOST provides an integrated system (target selection, operations and survey strategy, instrument capabilities, and high level data product delivery) and (c) one design fits many science cases. This survey will run for a period of at least 5 years, with the VISTA telescope being dedicated exclusively to observations with 4MOST. During its 5-year survey, the 4MOST project is expected to record >20 million resolution spectra.

The science plan has been structured into ten Surveys (see Table 2.1):

i) five dedicated to Galactic Archaeology obtaining spectra of stars in our Milky Way and its nearest neighbours

ii) five dedicated to Extragalactic objects

The science programme of 4MOST is driven by its individual Surveys outlined above, each pursuing different science cases. 4MOST will complement and enhance many large area sky surveys, such as four space-based observatories of prime European interest: Gaia, eROSITA, Euclid, and PLATO, and many ground-based facili-

Table 2.1: 4MOST Science Surveys

4MOST Science Surveys			
Galactic Archaeology		Extragalactic	
S1	Milky Way Halo LR Survey	S5	Galaxy Clusters Survey
S2	Milky Way Halo HR Survey	S6	AGN Survey
S3	Milky Way Disk and Bulge LR Survey	S7	Galaxy Evolution Survey (WAVES)
S4	Milky Way Disk and Bulge HR Survey	S8	Cosmology Redshift Survey
S9	One Thousand and One Magellanic Cloud Fields Survey (1001MC)	S10	Time Domain (TiDES)

ties like VST, DES, LSST, and SKA. Such a facility has been identified as of critical importance in a number of recent European strategic documents (Bode et al., 2008; Drew et al., 2010; Ellis et al., 2017; Turon, 2008; Zeeuw et al., 2007) and forms the perfect complement to the many all-sky survey projects around the world. During the upcoming 5-year period, the 4MOST consortium will receive 70% of the observation time to conduct 10 distinct Consortium Surveys, focusing on both Galactic and Extragalactic domains. The remaining 30% of observing time is designated for the broader ESO community to explore additional scientific opportunities through 15 selected Community Surveys, collectively forming the comprehensive 4MOST Survey Programme. The following outlines the main science cases of 4MOST:

- **S1 Milky Way Halo Low Resolution Survey**

This survey aims to unravel the Milky Way halo’s formation and evolution, deciphering its assembly history and mass distribution. Utilising multi-band photometry, Gaia data, radial velocities, and 4MOST spectra, this survey will provide an unprecedented characterisation of the halo and its interaction with the thick disk. Covering 10,000 sq. deg. of high-latitude sky, the survey will produce a comprehensive sample of giant stars, measuring their velocities with 1-2 km s⁻¹ precision and metallicities with 0.2 dex accuracy (Helmi et al., 2019).

- **S2 Milky Way Halo High Resolution Survey**

This survey will explore the Milky Way's formation and early chemical enrichment using a sample of 1.5 million high-latitude stars. Precise elemental abundances (up to 20 elements with <0.2 dex precision) will be derived. Identifying kinematically coherent substructures, science teams will associate them with birthplaces, testing galaxy formation models. The catalog will also include 30,000 stars with metallicity less than 1/100th of the Sun's, enabling an unprecedented, detailed study of the early chemical evolution of the Milky Way, nearly 100 times larger than existing samples (Christlieb et al., 2019).

- **S3 Milky Way Bulge and Disk Low Resolution Survey**

The Milky Way's formation and evolution details lie in its stars' orbits, chemistry, and ages. The 4MIDABLE-LR Survey seeks to explore kinematic and chemical substructures in the Milky Way disk and bulge, offering unprecedented sample sizes and precision compared to Gaia or other ongoing/planned surveys. Leveraging Gaia's unique parallax and magnitude-based target selection enhances efficiency in sampling extensive Milky Way volumes with well-defined selection functions (Chiappini et al., 2019).

- **S4 Milky Way Bulge and Disk High Resolution Survey**

Galaxies reveal their history through the characteristics of their stars—velocities, ages, and chemical compositions, offering crucial insights into galaxy formation models and various processes like gas flows, accretion, migration, and star formation variability. The 4MIDABLE-HR Survey aims to advance our understanding of Milky Way evolution by obtaining high-resolution spectra ($R \approx 20,000$) and detailed elemental abundances for large stellar samples in the Galactic disk and bulge. High-quality data will provide accurate diagnostics for millions of stellar spectra, including precise velocities, rotation, and abundances of elements like Li, s-process and r-process. Synergies with programs like Gaia and TESS will enrich the dataset, allowing exploration and constraints on the Milky Way's origin and structure (Bensby et al., 2019).

- **S5 Galaxy Clusters Survey**

The 4MOST Galaxy Clusters Survey aims to obtain spectroscopic redshifts for optical counterparts of 40,000 groups and clusters of galaxies detected by the eROSITA X-ray telescope. This will facilitate dynamical mass estimates and exploration of member galaxy properties. For clusters at $z > 0.7$, precise redshifts of the brightest cluster galaxies are the primary focus, while at lower redshifts ($z < 0.7$), the program targets over 15 member galaxies per cluster for dynamical mass measurements, aiding in cosmological experiments. The survey also addresses optical identification of galaxy groups and filaments at $z < 0.2$, enabling spectroscopic confirmation down to eROSITA's detection limits (Finoguenov et al., 2019).

- **S6 AGN Survey**

Using 4MOST, this survey aims to conduct an extensive survey of Active Galactic Nuclei (AGN) across a significant portion of the eROSITA extragalactic sky. This includes systematic follow-ups on eROSITA X-ray sources (mainly AGN) and employing a WISE mid-IR approach for obscured AGN selection. The well-matched X-ray and mid-IR flux limits of eROSITA and WISE to the spectroscopic capabilities of a 4-metre class telescope will enable this survey to achieve completeness levels of $\sim 80\text{-}90\%$ for X-ray selected AGN with fluxes $f_{0.5-2\text{keV}} > 10^{-14}$ erg/s/cm², reaching depths about 30 times deeper than the ROSAT all-sky survey. This comprehensive dataset will provide physical properties for up to one million supermassive black holes, allowing the exploration of their cosmic evolution, clustering properties, and the connection between AGN and large-scale structure from $z \sim 0$ to $z \sim 6$ (Merloni et al., 2019).

- **S7 Galaxy Evolution Survey (WAVES)**

The Wide Area Vista Extragalactic survey (WAVES) aims to study structure growth, mass, and energy from ~ 1 kpc to ~ 10 Mpc over 7 Gyr. On large scales (1–10 Mpc), it will explore group, filament, and void structures, comparing findings with simulations to assess the Cold Dark Matter paradigm. At intermediate scales (10 kpc – 1 Mpc), WAVES will investigate galaxy group properties, merger rates, and dark matter halo assembly. On small scales (1–10 kpc), it'll provide distance and environmental data to complement space-based imaging, focusing on galaxy bulge, disc, and bar evolution. Overall, WAVES will create a legacy dataset of ~ 1.6 million galaxies, bridging the low ($z < 0.1$) and intermediate ($z \sim 0.8$) redshift Universe (Merloni et al., [2019](#)).

- **S8 Cosmology Redshift Survey**

This survey will conduct rigorous cosmological tests using spectroscopic clustering measurements, enhancing existing lensing, cosmic microwave background (CMB), and other southern hemisphere surveys. With carefully chosen samples, including bright galaxies, luminous red galaxies, emission line galaxies, and quasars, totaling ~ 8 million objects from redshift 0.15 to 3.5, the Cosmology Redshift survey will enable decisive tests of gravitational physics. Combining spectra from this survey with data from facilities like LSST, Euclid, and SKA will address key science questions (Richard et al., [2019](#)).

- **S9 One Thousand and One Magellanic Fields (1001MC)**

The goal of this survey is to assess the kinematics and elemental abundances of diverse stellar populations, offering insights into the formation and interaction history of the Magellanic Clouds. It will obtain spectra for approximately 500,000 stars with $G < 19.5$ mag (Vega) across an area of approximately 1000 deg^2 , creating a valuable dataset applicable to various scientific inquiries (Cioni et al., [2019](#)).

- **S10 Time Domain Extragalactic Survey (TiDES)**

TiDES focuses on spectroscopic follow-up of optical transients and variable sources from large surveys like LSST. It includes three sub-surveys: (i) spectroscopic observations of supernova-like transients, (ii) comprehensive follow-up of transient host galaxies for redshift measurements, and (iii) repeat spectroscopic observations for Active Galactic Nuclei (AGN) and supermassive black hole binary candidates. Simulations suggest classifying transients down to $r = 22.5$ mag (AB) and obtaining spectra for up to 30,000 transients ($z \sim 0.5$), redshifts for 50,000 transient host galaxies ($z \sim 1$), and monitoring 1,000 AGN, including binary candidates, to redshift $z \sim 2.5$ over five years of 4MOST operations (Swann et al., [2019](#)).

2.3 VISTA Telescope

4MOST is set to be mounted on the VISTA telescope, located in the southern hemisphere at ESO's Cerro Paranal Observatory in northern Chile, at latitude $24^{\circ} 36' 57''$ south, longitude $70^{\circ} 23' 51''$ west, at a height of around 2518m (Sutherland et al., 2015) (Figure 2.1) and will replace the telescope's current instrument, *VIRCAM*, which made its last observation on the night of 5/6th March 2023 after more than a decade of infrared surveys (Emerson et al., 2023). The VISTA telescope itself consists of a $f/1.024$ concave primary mirror (M1) and an $f/1.62$ convex secondary mirror (M2) in a Ritchey-Chretien configuration (see Figure 2.2). The instrument will be positioned at the Cassegrain focus and will be reached via the two mirrors that will reflect the light through the WFC and Atmospheric Dispersion Corrector (ADC) as can be seen in Figure 2.2 and will deliver a focal ratio of $f/3.28$. (Winkler et al., 2020). Due to 4MOST being a visible instrument, compensations need to be carried out due to VISTA being built to also function in the infrared regime. Notably, VISTA employs an undersized secondary mirror relative to the primary mirror, preventing the projection of warm telescope structure light onto the focal surface through the mirrors. The telescope's configuration incorporates factors such as vignetting resulting from the central obstruction, spider vanes of the M2 holding cell, the under-filled M2 mirror relative to M1, the WFC optics, and the ADC.

Figure 2.1: VISTA telescope in Chile with the Paranal summit in the background. *(Photo credit: G.Hudepohl/ESO)*

Figure 2.2: Optical layout of the VISTA telescope including the 4MOST WFC sitting at Cassegrain focus with the components labelled. (Winkler et al., 2020)

2.4 Instrument overview

4MOST will provide a multiplex and spectral resolution, high enough to detect chemical and kinematic substructure in the stellar halo, bulge, and disks of the Milky Way, and enough wavelength coverage to secure receding velocities of extragalactic objects over a large range in red-shift (de Jong et al., 2012). A WFC creates a 4.2 square degree FoV on the focal surface, where 2436 optical fibres positioned by the Australian–European Southern Observatory Positioner (AESOP) (WavesSurvey, 2016) feed the light to two resolution $R\sim 5000$ spectrographs and one $R\sim 20,000$ spectrograph. This will yield more than 20 million spectra at resolution $R\sim 5000$ ($\lambda=370\text{--}950$ nm) and more than 2 million spectra at $R\sim 20,000$ ($\lambda=392.6\text{--}435.5, 516\text{--}573, 610\text{--}679$ nm) over the duration of the surveys conducted by 4MOST (de Jong et al., 2016).

A metrology system supports the accurate positioning of the fibres in the focal surface, while a calibration system provides the illumination from the M2 support spiders for wavelength and flat-field calibration. Figure 2.1 and 2.3 show in detail the VISTA telescope and the 4MOST instrument along with its subsystems.

In order for the project to carry out its ambitious science goals the optical performance of the instrument is critical. This places tight tolerances on the manufacture and alignment of the WFC optics (Table 3.3). In particular precise micrometre scale alignment is required, a major challenge in any astronomical instrument assembly. In this chapter, we outline the metrology methods used to precisely measure the elements of the WFC and present the results of the alignment and assembly of the WFC lenses along with the processes used.

Figure 2.3: Physical layout of the 4MOST elements on the VISTA telescope with the main components labelled. (de Jong et al., 2012)

2.4.1 4MOST Subsystems

The 4MOST instrument is comprised of numerous subsystems, each with distinct roles, that collectively contribute to its overall functionality. Those subsystems are:

- **Wide Field and Atmospheric Dispersion Correcter (WFC/ADC)**
- **AESOP - Fibre positioner**
- **Acquisition & Guiding and Wavefront Sensor System (A&G/WFS)**
- **Metrology Cameras**
- **Spectrographs**
- **Cassegrain Cable Wrap (CaCW)**

2.4.1.1 WFC/ADC

To enable such a wide field survey, a WFC and ADC are needed (see section 1.4.2.1). The 4MOST WFC and ADC corrects for image aberrations and atmospheric dispersion up to 55° zenith angle, beyond which the performance drops.

The WFC produces an almost unvignetted image with a diameter of 2.5° on the focal surface of the telescope and is the most expensive subsystem of 4MOST, costing approximately \sim £3million. The WFC is a key optical component for the 4MOST facility in that it performs the critical image correction to the VISTA telescope optics in order to deliver the requisite field of view, image quality and plate scale; all of which are crucial for the science cases Azais et al. (2016). The WFC consists of 6 lenses grouped in 4 parts, two of which act as doublets, forming a counter-rotating prisms, that make up the ADC unit. The layout and breakdown of the WFC components can be seen in Figure 2.4 and Figure 2.5. The lenses underwent manufacturing at KiwiStar Optics, New Zealand, and received anti-reflection coating by Coherent in the USA. Following these processes, they were transported to UCL for integration and assembly. Further discussion and details of the optical specifications can be found in Azais et al. (2016).

Each lens was mounted in a lens cell which acts as an interface to the main barrel assembly. The ADC lens cells are mounted on interfaces (bearing plates) that can rotate as part of the ADC action. The Main Structural Plate (MSP) serves as a foundational component designed to provide structural integrity, support, and stability to the overall instrument. Its primary goal is to ensure that the various components and instruments mounted on it are securely and precisely positioned and connects via a spacer to the telescope Cassegrain rotator.

The WFC and ADC will be explored in depth in Chapter 3.

2.4.1.2 AESOP Fibre Positioner

The 4MOST Fibre positioning system is based on a tilting spine principle, with 2436 science fibres and 12 guide fibres (see Figures 2.6 and 2.7). The design for AESOP is an evolution of a design that was first implemented in the FMOS-Echidna instrument for the Subaru telescope (Akiyama et al., 2008; Kimura et al., 2010; Moore et al., 2003). The field of view for the 4MOST instrument is designed as a hexagon to optimise the tessellation of the sky. This allows for more efficient coverage with minimal overlap and gaps between adjacent pointings. Hexagonal fields of view can be arranged in a close-packed grid, which makes them ideal for surveys that aim to

Figure 2.4: Labelled drawing of WFC (including ADC) with the main components.

maximise sky coverage without unnecessary repetition, like 4MOST. This geometric arrangement ensures that the fibre positioners can access targets more efficiently over a wide area. The goal of the optical fibre positioners is to simultaneously deploy and position all 2436 science fibres (812 fibres connected to each spectrograph) to their required position on the spherically curved focal surface within a time of ~ 2 minutes. The fibre positioning system allows each spine tip to be deployed within a circular patrol area, ensuring flexibility in target coverage. Overlapping patrol areas enable subsets of fibres to collectively cover the entire observation area and enhance fibre allocation completeness for clustered targets. The system aims for precise fibre positioning with a $10 \mu\text{m}$ RMS radial error, maintaining the relative positions of science spines and guide spines throughout each observation. (Brzeski et al., 2018)

Figure 2.5: Labelled zoomed in version of Figure 2.4 showing the ADC unit.

Field reconfiguration is achieved in an iterative closed-loop process with positional feedback from a metrology system. Thanks to the 4-camera metrology system, the accuracy of fibre positioning is expected to surpass 0.2 arcsec (Brzeski et al., 2022). The tilting spine positioner provides the advantage of granting each fibre a large patrol area, with a pitch between spine tips of 9.542 mm (~ 161 arcsec) and a patrol radius of at least 11.8 mm (~ 200 arcsec). The system achieves a closest separation of about 15 arcsec on any side between fibres. This design ensures that each target in the science field of view can be reached by at least three fibres leading to the Low and High Resolution Spectrographs. Consequently, the system guarantees high allocation efficiency, especially in scenarios where targets are clustered. This 4MOST configuration is quite competitive compared to similar instruments. For instance, the DESI instrument has a fibre pitch of approximately 7 mm, allowing for a tighter packing of fibres, which translates to a density of around 6 arcseconds separation between individual fibres. This enables DESI to target closely spaced objects more efficiently but limit its patrol area compared to 4MOST. In contrast, the MOONS instrument features a fibre configuration that typically results in wider separations, meaning that while it can cover larger areas, it might not target as dense a region as effectively as 4MOST or DESI. Overall, 4MOST's ability to achieve a closest fibre separation of 15 arcseconds provides a balanced approach, enabling efficient observation of densely packed targets while still allowing for a relatively

Figure 2.6: *Left* Illustration showing the arrangement of the 2436 science fibres, mapped to three spectrographs (LRS-A, LRS-B, and HRS) with alternating feeding in each column. *Right* the 4MOST AESOP fibre positioner is displayed, with fibres back-illuminated in red light for precise metrology system identification of their positions.

large patrol area.

The AESOP unit itself will attach to the back of the WFC MSP. Before deciding on AESOP, an alternative fibre positioner design was explored for 4MOST, named 'PotsPos' and developed specifically for the needs of the 4MOST. Its primary advantages over the tilting spine design include immunity to focal ratio degradation and defocus issues caused by the fibre tilt, which significantly reduces light losses. Additionally, the PotsPos actuator boasts a shorter length, making it better suited for the confined spatial requirements of the 4MOST positioner. Ultimately this design was not chosen due to AESOP's maturity and rigorous testing with other instruments. While PotsPos served as an initial design prototype, its intricate design posed numerous challenges that made it unsuitable for immediate adoption in instrument construction. More information on PotsPos can be found in Saviuk et al. (2014).

Figure 2.7: AESOP fibres showing the spines placed in the shape of a number '4'. (Credit: F. Watson)

2.4.1.3 A&G/WFS

The 4MOST Guiding and Wavefront Sensing cameras are composed of 6 cameras in total, mounted at the edge of the science field. A schematic drawing of the system can be found in Figure 2.8. The A&G and WFS cameras have three primary functions:

1. Two cameras serve as acquisition and guide cameras (A&G) positioned at the Cassegrain focus on the edge of the science field of view. Only one camera is active at a time, with the second camera acting as a backup, providing additional coverage for regions with scarce bright stars. Placed on opposite sides of the field, the acquisition camera facilitates precise telescope pointing adjustments, ensuring alignment with the 4MOST instrument's target field.
2. Four cameras function as curvature wavefront sensors (WFS), also mounted

at the edge of the science field. Two cameras are positioned inside of focus, and two are outside of focus, capturing images of intra- and extra-focus pupils of bright stars. These images assist in computing the telescope's wavefront performance, correcting misalignment's caused by temperature and a changing gravity vector as the telescope is moved to different positions. The wavefront measurements contribute to adjusting the primary and secondary mirrors through the active mirror support system. (Bellido-Tirado et al., 2022)

3. One camera is situated in an electronics rack and receives fibre arrays for the secondary guiding (SG) (Barden et al., 2020; Bellido-Tirado et al., 2022). Each fibre array ensures the spatial centration of target stars within the science field of view. This spatial information provides telescope tracking data, including field rotation. Working alongside the A&G cameras, the SG camera ensures that the field remains locked onto scientific targets, operating in a nearly continuous readout mode.

The A&G and WFS system will sit at the Cassegrain focus and will be attached to the Main Structural Plate of the WFC as shown in Figure 2.9.

Figure 2.8: A&G and WFS labelled schematic drawing showing the two A&G cameras, along with the four WFS cameras, the coolant lines to remove the heat generated by the cameras, and the lifting hook that is used to place the system on the MSP. (Bellido-Tirado et al., 2022)

2.4.1.4 Metrology Cameras

The metrology system precisely gauges the spatial coordinates of each fibre within the focal plane and seamlessly aligns them with on-sky targets. This advanced system is comprised of four identical cameras, which comprehensively capture the entire field of view, complemented by a sophisticated back-illumination unit that lights up both the scientific and reference fibres as can be seen in Figure 2.10.

2.4.1.5 Spectrographs

4MOST consists of three spectrographs, two Low-Resolution (LRS) (Caillier et al., 2018; Disseau et al., 2022) and one High-Resolution (HRS) (Seifert et al., 2016), each feed by 812 fibres. Details of the spectrograph specifications can be found in Table 2.2. Figure 2.11 shows the optical layout of both the LRS and HRS. Each spectrograph comprises of fixed blue, green, and red arms, each with a $6k \times 6k$ CCD detector. The LRS delivers uninterrupted wavelength coverage spanning from 390 to 950 nm with a resolution exceeding 4000 ($R > 4000$). On the other hand,

Figure 2.9: Photo of A&G and WFS.

the HRS spans the ranges 392.6 – 435.5 nm, 516 – 573 nm, and 610 – 679 nm, providing a high resolution of over 18,000 ($R > 18,000$) (Figure 2.12). The Fibre-Feed System, which is situated between the Cassegrain focus of the telescope and the spectrographs, facilitates the transmission of the light from the science targets imaged at the focal surface to the slits of the spectrographs.

2.4.1.6 Cassegrain Cable Wrap

The Cassegrain Cable Wrap (CaCW) prevents twisting of cables and optical fibres during rotation of telescope cassegrain axis.

To safeguard the delicate fibres, a comprehensive support and guide system is employed, comprising multiple layers of conduits and cable carriers. Notably, a substantial Cassegrain cable wrap positioned at the rear of the telescope facilitates

Figure 2.10: (a) AESOP fibres backlit before positioning. (b) AESOP fibres after positioning has been complete using the metrology system.

Figure 2.11: Schematic showing the LRS (*left*) and HRS (*right*) optical layout, with the red, green and blue arms (Caillier et al., 2018; Disseau et al., 2022).

the rotation of the focal surface area while the Alt-Az telescope tracks a field in the sky. An image of the CaCW can be seen in Figure 2.13.

Figure 2.12: Covered wavelength range and resolution of the (*top*) HRS and (*bottom*) LRS for the Blue, Green and Red channels. (Credit: de Jong et al., 2016

)

Figure 2.13: The Cable Wrap prevents twisting of cables and optical fibres during rotation of the telescope cassegrain axis.

Table 2.2: 4MOST Instrument Design Specifications (de Jong et al., 2016)

Parameter	Design Value
Telescope	VISTA, 4.1m ϕ
Field of View	Shape: hexagonal Size: 4.2 deg ² Diameter: 2.5°
Accessible sky (zenith angle < 55°)	30,000 deg ²
Multiplex fibre poisoner	2436
On-sky fibre aperture	Shape: circular Size: 1.64 arcsec ² Diameter: 1.45 arcsec
Minimum distance between fibres	15 arcsec (on any side)
Low-resolution Spectrograph	
Multiplex	812 ($\times 2$)
Wavelength range	370 – 950 nm
Spectral resolving power	4000 – 7700
Spectral sampling	≥ 2.5 pixel/FWHM
Radial velocity accuracy	< 1 km/s
Sensitivity	Limiting AB magnitudes for S/N = 10 \AA^{-1} 6 \times 20 min exposures mean seeing, new moon
High-resolution spectrograph	
Multiplex	812
Wavelength range	392.6–435.5 nm 516–573 nm 610–679 nm
Spectral resolving power	18,000 – 21,000
Spectral sampling	≥ 2.5 pixel/FWHM
Radial velocity accuracy	< 1 km s ⁻¹

Chapter 3

4MOST WFC: Optics, Metrology, Alignment, Integration and Testing

An Eye to the Sky

A view of the complete WFC system, peering directly through the L1 lens. The inner baffles can be seen along with the dispersion of the laboratory lights.

(Photo taken by author)

The work described in this chapter was published in Cunningham et al., 2023 "Assembly and alignment of the 4-metre Multi-Object Spectroscopic Telescope Wide Field Corrector"

Building on the introduction of 4MOST's capabilities and structure in the previous chapter, this chapter explores the instrument's intricate optical components in greater depth. The 4-metre Multi-Object Spectroscopic Telescope (4MOST) is a fibre-fed multi-object spectrograph for the VISTA telescope at the ESO Paranal Observatory in Chile. The goal of the 4MOST project is to create a general-purpose and highly efficient spectroscopic survey facility for astronomers in the 4MOST consortium and the ESO community. The instrument itself will record 2436 simultaneous spectra over a ~ 4.2 square degree field of view and consists of an optical Wide-Field Corrector (WFC), a fibre positioner system based on a tilting spine design, and three spectrographs giving both high and low spectral dispersion. The WFC comprises of 6 lenses grouped into 4 elements, 2 of which are cemented doublets that act as an atmospheric dispersion corrector (ADC). The first lens element is 0.9m in diameter whilst the diameter of the other elements is 0.65m. For the instrument to meet its science goals, each lens was aligned to its optical axis to be well within $\sim 100\mu\text{m}$ — a major challenge. This was achieved using contact metrology methods supplemented by pencil beam laser probes. In particular, a novel off-axis laser beam system has been implemented to test the optics' alignment before and after shipment. This chapter details the alignment and assembly methods and presents the latest results on the achieved lens positioning and projected performance of the WFC.

3.1 Introduction

This chapter summarises and presents the WFC subsystem and the work carried out at UCL. All the work presented in manufacturing, procuring, cementing and coating of the lenses was either completed before the author joined the collaboration or was done by groups the author was not involved with. The design of the optics and the WFC was spearheaded by Damien Jones (Prime Optics), Sam Barden and Greg Smith (Leibniz Institute for Astrophysics Potsdam (AIP)). Glass blanks for L2, L3 and L4 were made by Schott, while the L1 blank was made by Corning Speciality Glass in the USA. Testing, characterisation and polishing of all the lenses (except L1), including the cementing and potting of the L2 and L3 lenses were carried out by KiwiStar Optics (a business unit of Callaghan Innovation, New Zealand). The aspheric surface of L1 was produced by Precision Asphere in the USA while all the lenses were coated with an anti-reflective coating by Coherent Coatings in the USA and inspected by KiwiStar Optics before arriving at UCL.

UCL was responsible for inserting the L1 and L4 lenses into their respective lens cells and meticulously measuring each element, including height, surface variation, run-out and thickness of lenses, lens cells, barrel components, and the MSP. Additionally, UCL was tasked with determining the necessary shim thickness to ensure that the WFC met the correct lens to focal surface distances. Following the completion of measurements, the alignment, integration, and assembly of the WFC and ADC commenced.

3.2 Optical Design

Like all instrumental endeavors, the development of the 4MOST WFC underwent several iterative design phases before arriving at its current configuration. Alternative concepts for 4MOST were proposed by Gillingham et al. (2014), suggesting that one or more lenses could be translated laterally to introduce prismatic dispersion, which would compensate for atmospheric dispersion. This idea offered a potential simplification by reducing the number of optical elements from 6 to 4, however an internal study by Prime Optics was carried out comparing the rotating

Figure 3.1: Optical layout of the WFC lenses, showing different focus positions for different field angles. This shows that all the lenses contribute in correcting the incoming light to produce high quality images across the focal plane.

and translating concepts and the rotating ADC option was ultimately selected. Although there were additional optical fabrication costs associated with the two extra lenses required for the rotating ADC, the technical approach was well understood and the performance criteria were better met. Bernard Delabre from ESO proposed an alternative design that simplified the optical prescription again by reducing the number of aspheric surfaces and shrinking the lens diameters. An improved version of this design was chosen for presentation at the April 2016 4MOST Preliminary Design Review (PDR) stage and this became the final design (Azais et al., 2016; Bellido et al., 2017).

The final optical design for 4MOST consists of 4 elements with 6 lenses in total. Two singlets; L1 and L4, and two cemented wedged doublets; L2A/B and L3A/B, which act as counter-rotating prisms and form the ADC unit. The lenses are labelled L1 to L4 in order of position from the secondary mirror down to the focal plane. The layout of the optics can be seen in Figure 3.1 and the main specification details for each lens are presented in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Lens Specifications for the optical elements of the WFC. S1 and S2 refer to the surfaces of each lens. Data acquired from 4MOST internal documentation. For lens tolerances see Table 3.3. Final Lens positions are discussed in section 3.18.1.

Element	Material	Diameter (mm)	Shape of Lens	Centre Thickness (mm)	Radius of Curvature (mm)
L1	Fused Silica	900.0	S1 Convex S2 Aspheric Concave	85.0 (± 0.2)	S1 947.4 S2 929.4
L2A	LLF1	649.49	S1 Concave Sphere	45.26	S1 9353.5 S2 > 1km
L2B	N-BK7	650.04	*S2 Plano (wedge angle 90.57) (tilted tilted -0.568° about x-axis wrt S1) *S1 Plano (wedge angle 90.57) (tilted -0.566° about x-axis wrt S2) S2 Convex	45.112	S1 > 1km S2 5114.8
L3A	N-BK7	649.58	S1 Concave *S2 Plano (wedge angle 90.84°)	45.15 (± 0.2)	S1 741.06 S2 > 1km
L3B	LLF1	650.0	S1 Plano (wedge angle 90.84°) *†S2 Plano	44.81 (± 0.1)	S1 > 1km S2 > 1km
L4	N-BK7	650.14	S1 Convex S2 Convex	83.46 (± 0.2)	S1 2155.4 S2 1330.1

Note: '*' denotes cemented layer with material Sylgard - 184 silicone elastomer.

† - Lens L3B was flipped: inner doublet surface S1 has become outer due to its better surface irregularity, therefore L3B S2 was the cemented layer.

3.2.1 L1

L1 is a HPFS 7980 lens, which is a standard grade of fused silica made by Corning, and the largest of the optics at 0.9m. It is the only lens with an aspheric surface (Figure 3.2). Aspheric surfaces can help correct optical aberrations such as spherical aberration, coma, astigmatism, and distortion, while also using fewer elements than conventional spherical optics. In a wide field corrector, aberrations tend to amplify towards the periphery of the lens due to the expansive field of view. To counteract this, an aspheric surface is introduced to minimise aberrations, ensuring sharper and more precise images throughout the entire field.

Figure 3.2: Side view drawing of the L1 lens. (Credit: Internal 4MOST Documentation)

3.2.2 ADC

3.2.2.1 L2

L2 consists of two lenses, L2A and L2B, which together form a cemented wedged doublet (wedge angle $90.57^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$). L2A is made from LLF1, while L2B is made from N-BK7 glass. With a diameter of 0.65m, L2 serves as the first component

of the ADC. The correct clocking of L2 within the lens cells was achieved using a reference marker applied by Kwistar. This marker indicated the direction of the wedge, allowing precise alignment of L2 in the required orientation within the cell.

Figure 3.3: L2 side view. (Credit: 4MOST WFC Mounted Doublet Dimensions by Kwistar Optics)

3.2.2.2 L3

L3 is also composed of 2 lenses L3A and L3B, which form the second component of the ADC (wedge angle $90.84^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$). L3A is concave lens and has a much smaller radius of curvature as can be seen in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4: L3 side view. (Credit: 4MOST WFC Mounted Doublet Dimensions by Kwistar Optics)

3.2.2.3 Cementing the ADC

The wedged doublets are cemented together using Sylgard-184 silicone elastomer (Jonas et al., 2020). The process of cementing these two wedged lenses together posed a significant challenge, attributable to the distinct coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) associated with each glass type (N-BK7 – $7.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ C}^{-1}$ and LLF1

$- 8.1 \times 10^{-6} C^{-1}$), which can cause stress within the cemented assembly. This had to be carefully managed while also ensuring there were no air bubbles trapped in the cement layer. Careful attention was warranted due to their diameter and the large survival temperature range.

The following steps were carried out by Kiwistar to ensure a successful cementing:

- Small Plate trials: to validate elastomer thickness, cementing techniques, and address issues like hazing and transmission performance.
- Finite Element Analysis (FEA): Assess stress on the elastomer and confirm optimal handling support techniques to prevent distortion during the curing process.
- Large Plate Glass Trial: Utilise larger diameter plate glass to validate developed procedures and tools.
- Optical Testing: Conduct established procedures for transmission and surface reflection tests on the bonded ADC prisms.
- Full-Size Cementing Trial: Utilise the flat polished surfaces of L2A and L3B to evaluate deformation and optical performance.

3.2.3 L4

L4 is a 650mm convex lens that sits at the back of the WFC (below the MSP) and is the last optical lens before the light reaches the focal plane. This lens is made of N-BK7 and is the only lens with both surfaces convex.

Figure 3.5: Side view drawing of the L4 lens. (Credit: Internal 4MOST Documentation)

3.3 Mechanical Design

The WFC follows a cylindrical shape and with the exception of the two tilted surfaces (small tilts of the doublet interface surfaces of L2 and L3 to produce the ADC action), all optical interfaces, the rotational axes of the ADC lenses, the Cassegrain instrument rotator axis of the telescope, and the optical axis of the VISTA telescope are aligned along a common axis (Azais et al., 2016). When carrying out the alignment and measurements at UCL, we came up with our own coordinate system based on the MSP and used this as a reference throughout. This will be discussed later in section 3.6.

In the design of wide field correctors, it's crucial to account for temperature variations experienced by telescopes, which can range from 30 degrees during the day to -10 at night. Thermal expansion plays a significant role here. The objective is to ensure that the system remains undistorted despite these temperature changes. To achieve this, engineers aim to create an athermal system, meaning it maintains alignment regardless of expansion. One way to achieve this is by using materials with controlled thermal expansion, such as an iron-nickel alloy. For the cells holding the lenses, typically made of metal (nickel-iron alloy for L1 cell and steel for

the L4 cell), a rubber interface is utilised between the glass and the metal (see Section 3.14.1). This interface is carefully designed to minimise stress on the lenses during temperature fluctuations by considering the thermal expansion properties of the glass/rubber/cell system. Where the cell and barrel thermal properties differ, flexures are included between cell and barrel (see section 3.3.2).

3.3.1 The Barrel

The Barrel that houses the optics and provides a mount for the lens cells comprises four tubes all made from steel: A, B, C, and D (Figure 3.6). Tube A connects to the top end of the L1 lens cell and Tube B at the bottom end. Tube B is further connected to the base of the MSP. Both Tube A and Tube B are equipped with internal baffles. Tube C accommodates the ADC unit, while Tube D is affixed to the L4 lens cell. Access ports were added to tube A to allow lens access while in full assembly and to allow for cleaning.

The WFC is provided with external baffles, known as the 'permanent' and 'removable baffle', and with internal baffles. Internal baffles are installed to Tube A (Figure 3.6) to attenuate stray light reflected within the WFC. The design of apertures and axial locations has been optimised to ensure at least three reflections of errant rays before they enter the second lens L2. The external permanently mounted baffle provides protection for the L1 lens. These baffles are used to prevent excess scattering of light within the system that may adversely effect the incoming light.

3.3.2 Cell Design

When it comes to lens cell designs, ideally the lens cell would be produced from the same material as the barrel to ensure consistent expansion and contraction with temperature changes. However, the choice of barrel material is influenced by factors like cost, ease of production, and weight considerations. In the case of 4MOST, steel is the preferred option for the barrel material.

Steel, however has a notably high coefficient of temperature expansion (CTE) (~ 12 ppm), which differs greatly from the CTEs of the lens materials. Fused silica, for instance, has a CTE of 0.5 ppm, while N-BK7 registers a CTE of 7 ppm. As

Figure 3.6: Half-section of WFC showing the lenses and baffles within the barrel.

Figure 3.7: (a) Drawing of the cell design for the L1 Lens.(b) Schematic demonstrating the positioning of the L1 lens within its cell.

an alternative solution, a nickel-iron (Ni/Fe) alloy can be considered for the fused silica lens cell and was ultimately used in the 4MOST design. This material offers a lower CTE, allowing for a closer match to the CTE of fused silica. Consequently, it requires a thinner layer of Room Temperature Vulcanised (RTV) for achieving an athermal design. If an iron cell was used with a fused silica lens then a greater thickness of RTV would be required to be athermal. This increased thickness would then not adequately meet the flexure and gravity requirements.

The L1 and L4 cell designs feature tubular structures, each with a flange at one end serving as the axial reference for the lens, and another flange at the opposite end where the lens retainer is bolted. The L1 cell is made from a Ni/Fe alloy, while the L4 cell is made from a low-carbon steel. Given the material discrepancy between the L1 Ni/Fe cell and the steel barrel, flexures have been integrated into the L1 cell design (Figure 3.7). These flexures adeptly compensate for the differing thermal expansion rates, allowing for seamless adaptation. They are securely attached to a steel ring possessing the same coefficient of thermal expansion as the barrel, ensuring harmonious performance.

In contrast, as the L4 cell (Figure 3.8) is constructed of steel, there is no such material or CTE mismatch between the lens cell and the barrel. Consequently, the design does not necessitate the incorporation of flexures.

Figure 3.8: Schematic demonstrating the positioning of the L4 lens within its cell.

3.4 ADC Verification

The ADC, comprising L2 and L3 lenses already potted in their cells, required the installation of ADC motors to facilitate rotation. Consequently, to evaluate the alignment of L2 and L3 in the ADC configuration, it was essential to install and verify the functionality of the ADC motors. Designated as ADC 1 and ADC 2, these motors played a critical role in rotating both set of doublets respectively, allowing precise

correction of light dispersion in the atmosphere up to a zenith angle of 55 degrees (see Figure 3.9).

Figure 3.9: ADC relative position in degrees for both L2 and L3 for based on zenith distance.

At UCL, rigorous testing was conducted on the ADC motors, to ensure seamless integration with the programmable logic controller (PLC) and web visualization software. This functionality was tested within the UCL laboratory, with comprehensive tests conducted to enable remote control of the ADC from the control centre in Germany. This ensured that the ADC could be remotely operated while at the telescope. Figure 3.10 outlines the basic layout depicting the connection of the ADC motors to both the PLC and the web visualisation software. The ADC1 and ADC2 motors control the rotation of the L2 and L3 doublets respectively (see Figure 3.11). Both motors demonstrated smooth operation when tested separately, however during testing in full assembly we identified an undesirable design feature in the ADC mechanism. When bolted, in full ADC configuration with ADC covers on, the power cables/sensor cables to the motor were easily caught by the ADC2 limit switch bar as it passed the motor. Consequently, it became necessary to loop the cables around the motor area to mitigate this issue however space and access was very limited. After the rewiring, no further issues were encountered.

The ADC motors are tracking devices which update the position of the axis as a function of the telescope coordinates and the UTC time. The general equations for the ADC prism position calculation (in radians) are:

$$\alpha_{ADC1} = \left(\cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\tan(ZD)}{\tan(ZD_{max})} \right) - \frac{\pi}{2} \right) - \text{cass} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\alpha_{ADC2} = - \left(\cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\tan(ZD)}{\tan(ZD_{max})} \right) - \frac{\pi}{2} \right) - \text{cass} \quad (3.2)$$

Where:

- α_{ADC1} : rotation angle of lens L2
- α_{ADC2} : rotation angle of lens L3
- ZD: telescope zenith distance
- ZD_{max} : maximum design angle for the ADC (0.96rad (= 55 deg))
- cass: Cassegrain rotation angle in radians

For α_{ADC1} : α_{ADC1} is calculated as the difference between two terms. The first term involves the inverse cosine (arc cosine) of the ratio of $\tan(ZD)$ to $\tan(ZD_{max})$. This ratio effectively represents the correction needed based on the zenith distance of the telescope (ZD) and the maximum designed zenith distance for the ADC (ZD_{max}). Subtracting $\frac{\pi}{2}$ ensures that the correction is referenced to a position where the zenith distance is at its maximum ($\frac{\pi}{2}$ radians or 90 degrees). Finally, cass (the Cassegrain rotation angle) is subtracted. For α_{ADC2} : Similar to α_{ADC1} , but the entire expression is negative. This ensures that the rotation angle for α_{ADC2} is in the opposite direction compared to α_{ADC1} . In summary, these equations are used to compute the rotation angles for lenses L2 and L3. These angles are crucial for correcting atmospheric dispersion effects in astronomical observations.

This section provides a detailed account of the setup and testing procedures for the ADC motors, along with measurements conducted on L2 and L3. Given that both lenses in the final configuration would be rotated using the ADC motors, it was crucial to evaluate how the surfaces and centers of the lenses varied during rotation.

3.4.1 ADC Motor set-up

When a positive input value is entered into the PLC web-visualizer to control the motors for ADC1 and ADC2, the bearings move in a clockwise direction when

Figure 3.10: Schematic drawing showing the basic cable layout system for the ADC motors, and the PLC.

viewed from above through the WFC (looking down through L2 towards the L3).

Prior to the installation of the L2 and L3 lenses, the motors underwent initial testing in the UCL lab to ensure proper functionality (Figure 3.11 a) displaying on of the motors that was tested). Additionally, the inner bearing plates of L2 and L3 were rechecked, as detailed in section 3.9.1. Once their operation was confirmed and rotation of ADC1 and ADC2 proceeded smoothly, the L2 and L3 lenses were then installed for further testing.

Figure 3.11: a) Photograph displaying one of the exposed ADC motors. b) PLC system utilised to control the ADC motors. c) Depiction of the wire cabling for the motor within Tube D, secured with blue cable ties. d) Photograph of the motor cables passing through dedicated holes in Tube D.

3.5 General Assembly

The comprehensive assembly process for the WFC is described in the flow diagram presented in Figure 3.12. This process is divided into three primary stages. Firstly, the pre-assembly phase entails initial preparatory tasks necessary to facilitate both the 'dry' assembly and the final assembly. The 'dry' assembly stage involves alignment procedures conducted without the inclusion of lenses. This phase serves to

provide insight into the cohesive integration of the WFC components during the final assembly, as well as to assess the compatibility of various surfaces. The 'dry' assembly phase also provided an opportunity to derive the positions of the different mating surfaces, which are subsequently utilised in determining the thickness of spacers (metal shims) required for installation at specified locations on the WFC. These spacers are essential for maintaining the precise relative axial positioning of the optics. During this measurement phase, all lens cells were aligned to a chosen axis and locked in location using retractable pins. The final assembly describes the last stage of assembling the WFC, after all individual measurements have been taken and lenses were potted in their cells (potting refers to the method of securely mounting the lens within the cell using a potting compound). During this stage, all elements were integrated and aligned together as described in Figure 3.12.

Figure 3.12: Flow diagram showing the general process of alignment and assembly for the WFC at UCL. The key at the top shows the different stages of assembly. This process chart shows the general procedure that was followed during the building and assembly of the WFC.

3.6 Alignment strategy

The alignment technique adopted was to use precision metrology of the components to position them to the required accuracy. The main metrology methods used were

a Faro gage arm, and digital dial gauges coupled with a precision rotary table (see Figure 3.13 for image of dial gauges and Table 3.2 for instrument accuracies).

Table 3.2: Table showing the accuracy of the metrology instruments used throughout the assembly and integration of the WFC.

Metrology tool	Accuracy of instrument (μm)
Rotary Table	± 1
Dial gauge	± 2
Faro Gage Arm	± 10
Micrometre & Vernier Calipers	± 5
Laser Displacement Sensor	± 1
Laser Alignment System	± 5

3.6.1 Performance and Precision of Alignment Equipment

Each piece of equipment was chosen for its accuracy and specific application in the alignment process. Below is an overview of the primary instruments used and their operational precision:

The precision rotary table ran true, maintaining complete flatness with an accuracy of approximately $\sim 1\mu m$, ensuring that the axis of rotation remained highly vertical. This setup allowed the rotation to define the exact centre; any deviation from this centre introduced a measurable run-out. By maintaining such stringent flatness and accuracy, the rotary table played a crucial role in achieving the alignment tolerances required for optimal lens positioning. Dial gauges were critical for measuring surface flatness and centre run-out. These gauges operate by translating mechanical movement into a digital readout, allowing high precision in positional measurements. During measurement, the dial gauges were carefully positioned to prevent damage to the lens surface. Notably, the dial gauges only touched the outside edge of the lens, never the clear aperture. The Faro gage arm provided flexibility in measuring heights and mapping out surface profiles. By moving the arm along surfaces, height data was accurately captured, facilitating a thorough analysis of lens positioning. The Faro gage arm's measurements were cross-referenced with dial gauge data to ensure consistency. A micrometer and vernier calipers were also used for a section of the assembly. Used primarily for height measurements of the Tube A

barrel, these instruments provided additional dimensional verification. With precision down to the micron level, they were essential in maintaining consistency across the assembly's vertical alignment. The laser displacement sensor (LDS) was employed to measure the height of the Room Temperature Vulcanised (RTV) rubber axial pads that supported the lenses. This sensor operates by emitting a laser beam and measuring the reflected light to calculate precise height variations. The non-contact nature of the LDS prevented any potential displacement or damage to the soft rubber material. To optically test the alignment of specific lenses (L1 and L4), a laser alignment system (LAS) was used. This setup, employing a pencil beam laser, allowed for the verification of lens positions post-alignment. The laser and camera system's precision ensured that final adjustments met the tight tolerances needed for optimal the WFC performance and gave us confidence when comparing to the Zemax as built model, more on this procedure is discussed in section 3.15. Individual lens position tolerances for the WFC are detailed in Table 3.3.

Table 3.3: Lens element position tolerances. Axial tolerance is $\pm 200\mu m$ for each element. *Note: L2 has a larger tolerance due to its flat shape and low refractive power, making it less sensitive to misalignments. L3's curved surface and higher refractive power require a tighter tolerances.*

Element	Decentre ($\pm\mu m$)	Tilt ($\pm\mu rad$)	Tilt run-out across diameter ($\pm\mu m$)
L1	200	873	785
L2	1000	1454	945
L3	100	145	95
L4	200	218	142

Generally throughout the measurements, a 1-24 numbering system was used to mark angular position on each component, with each position corresponding to the evenly spaced bolt holes on the ADC bearing plates. The first position No.1 started at +X and the rotary table was turned anticlockwise until No.24. These positions were marked on the other elements so that the same numbering system re-

Figure 3.13: Image showing dial gauge measurements being taken of the both the L1 Lens and L1 cell.

mained consistent. In positions where the ADC coordinate/numbering system was not used, (mainly MSP) a 1-36 numbering system was used that again corresponded to evenly spaced holes on the MSP with No.1 stating at +X and the rotary table turning clockwise until No.36 (No.1 is defined as being along the +X axis throughout).

3.6.2 Static and dynamic contributions to the lens alignment offsets

The tolerances outlined in Table 3.3 establish the acceptable range for lens offsets, which can be broken into static and dynamic budgetary contributions. The static aspect encompasses manufacturing tolerances of mechanical components such as barrel, cells, and ADC mechanism, along with assembly tolerances during component integration taking into account equipment contributions. Notably, tight tolerances apply to static tilt manufacturing for barrel and cell components as there is a limited means to adjust this axis. Conversely, static decentre mechanical component tolerances, primarily bolt circle centring, are less critical due to adjustable centring accuracy within specified tolerances. Dynamic contributions consider gravitational-induced flexure and ADC centre offsets from the optical axis, affecting element po-

Table 3.4: Estimates of the various contributions to decentre of the individual lens.

Element	Static Lens/cell/barrel ($\pm\mu m$)	Dynamic Lens/cell/barrel (gravitational) ($\pm\mu rad$)	Total ($\pm\mu m$)	Allowance ($\pm\mu m$)
L1	50	9	59	200
L2	300	7	307	1000
L3	50	4	54	100
L4	50	17	67	200

Table 3.5: Estimates of the various contributions to tilt of the individual lens

Element	Static Lens/cell/barrel Max ($\pm\mu m$)	Static Lens/cell/barrel RMS ($\pm\mu rad$)	Dynamic Lens/cell/barrel (gravitational) ($\pm\mu m$)	Total (Using RMS value) ($\pm\mu m$)	Target ($\pm\mu m$)
L1	290	121.1	9.0	130.1	785
L2	135	51.7	9.5	61.2	945
L3	120	42.7	9.0	51.7	95
L4	150	66.7	8.0	74.7	142

sitions. Estimates provided in Tables 3.4 and 3.5 detail both static and dynamic contributions to lens decentre and tilt, derived from previous experience, FEA analyses, and manufacturing tolerances. Additionally, static values include contributions from common components such as the main plate and tube C.

3.6.2.1 Estimates of lens alignment contribution

Static lens/cell values are derived from previous experimental work carried out by Prof. Peter Doel on DESI and DECam, and extensive experience and expertise in the field, using dial gauge run-out measurements on a precision rotary table and are shown in Table 3.4. Dynamic values for L1 stem from FEA analysis of tube A and L1 cell movement at a 60-degree zenith angle, while those for L2 and L3 originate from AIP FEA analysis at a 45-degree zenith angle ¹. Table 3.5 provides the estimations of the diverse factors impacting the tilt of each individual lens. The static component pertaining to the lens/cell/barrel is determined from manufacturing tolerances specified in the technical drawings of each contributing component, referenced from the main plate. These values are presented both as a straightforward sum of tolerances, likely overestimating the tilt, and as a more realistic and accurate RMS sum.

¹This FEA analysis was carried out before the author joined this project

3.7 Establishing a reference for measurements

3.7.1 The L3 outer bearing plate

In order to ensure proper alignment of the system, a reference point was essential. The L3 outer bearing plate (L3OBP) was selected for its accessibility and its circular shape, which made it suitable for alignment during the measurement of all lens and barrel components. Consequently, the centre of the L3 outer bearing plate serves as a crucial reference point, to which various surfaces within the system are aligned. To establish a consistent reference surface position relative to the outer bearing plate, measurements of the L3 outer bearing plate diameter were taken using dial gauges each time a new construction or alignment was conducted. During each re-measurement of the L3 outer bearing plate centre the plate was aligned such that its centre was within $10\mu\text{m}$ of the rotary table axis. Figure 3.14 illustrates how well centred the L3OBP is between measurements taken on different dates.

Considering the tolerances outlined above, particular attention was given to aligning all lenses to this central point, with a special focus on the L3 lens due to its tighter tolerances. Given that the L3 lens is positioned along the bearing axis, it was also imperative to ensure that the bearing axis was properly aligned with the L3 system.

To facilitate data visualisation, arbitrary radius was employed throughout as a reference point for plotting positional data, chosen based on the measurements we collected. This approach allowed us to interpret alignment deviations more clearly, even though a standardised radius value was not always feasible due to varying measurement conditions. Of greater significance are the variations observed and the central positions derived from these measurements. This applies for all diameter run-out measurements throughout this chapter.

Figure 3.14: Comparing the centre of the L3 outer bearing plate diameter to previous measurements indicating a high level of stability. The graph demonstrates minimal variation, with the centre of the L3 outer bearing plate moving by less than approximately 10 micrometers between measurements. *Arbitrary radius of 200 μm chosen.*

3.8 Main Structural Plate

The Main Structural Plate (MSP) is an integral part of the WFC system and acts as the support foundation to which all components of the WFC (including AESOP and the WFS) are attached to (see Figure A.1(a)). During the testing phase, UCL received two plates: one designated for alignment, integration and testing (AIT), which was intended to be returned to AIP in Potsdam for further testing with other subsystems, and another designated as the final MSP for the WFC (Figure 3.15).

The back of the MSP features two mounting blocks: Block 1 and Block 2 (Figure 3.16). These blocks are what the testing systems and AESOP will sit on in the final configuration. The angle formed by the inner flat surfaces of these two blocks is represented by the symbol α . Additionally, the angle formed by the outer diameter bevel surfaces, often referred to as 'flat faces', is denoted as angle β . The terms 'Right' and 'Left' Blocks correspond to Block 1 and Block 2, respectively, as observed on the back of the MSP. The XY coordinates depicted in Figure 3.16

Figure 3.15: Main Structural Plate on the rotary table while being measured supported by jacks.

serve as the coordinate system for the rotary table utilised at UCL for measurement purposes.

3.8.1 Spherically Mounted Retroreflector

The AIT plate featured holes labelled A1-A12 while the MSP had holes from A1-A6 (Figures 3.16 and 3.17). These were specifically designated for the installation of spherically mounted retroreflector nests intended to accommodate the spherically mounted retroreflectors (SMRs) (Figure 3.18). These nests were incorporated to enable the use of a point cloud with SpatialAnalyzer software² at AIP. The precise positioning of these SMRs was of paramount importance, as they would play a crucial role in the final assembly process during integration testing at AIP and also during the final commissioning at the telescope. These SMRs will be affixed to other subsystems connected to the WFC, enabling the integration and recommissioning team to precisely locate these points and compare them to the WFC position. The positions of the SMR's for the AIT MSP were measured at UCL using the Faro

²<https://www.kinematics.com/spatialanalyzer/index.php>

Figure 3.16: Schematic of the MSP showing the XY coordinate system used along with the position of the 6 SMR positions, and the angles that the blocks and flat faces make with each other. The arrow illustrates the direction in which the rotary table moved during measurements.

Arm and will serve as reference points for the team in AIP and Chile and facilitate alignment verification.

3.8.2 MSP Measurements

The back surface of the plate underwent measurement at three distinct positions to assess its flatness, conducted while the plate remained in its natural formation on the rotary table (i.e. not bolted down, which would cause distortion). These positions were situated at distances of 0.3cm, 8.5cm, and 34cm from the outer edge, respectively (refer to Figure 3.19 for the depiction of two of these positions). Adhering to standard procedure, measurements commenced at the coordinate labelled as +X and at hole number 1, proceeding in an anticlockwise direction. The measurements illustrated in Figure 3.19 indicate a variation in flatness ranging from ± 40 microns at the edge to ± 15 microns closer to the inner diameter. Notably, as proximity to the

Figure 3.17: Drawing of the AIT MSP showing the same XY coordinate system as before, along with the position of the 1-36 numbering system used. The angles α and β represent the angles that the blocks and flat faces make with each other. The number system A1-A12 represent the AIT plate SMR positions that were used in the testing at AIP along with a spatial analyser.

Figure 3.18: Photo showing a pair of Spherically Mounted Retroreflectors.

inner diameter increases, the MSP exhibits a progressively flatter profile. In Figure 3.20 we compare the front and back surfaces of the MSP and find that they both exhibit consistent trends.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.19: (a) Image of the dial gauges taking measurements of the various positions across the AIT plate. (b) Plot of the AIT MSP back surface variations taken from 3 different positions, 0.3cm, 8.5cm and 34cm from the outer edge respectively. All 3 positions follow the same trend, peaking and troughing in the same positions, especially for the inner two measurements.

3.8.2.1 MSP Inner/Outer Diameter

The inner and outer diameters of the MSP were assessed using dial gauges. Due to limitations posed by the reach of the Faro Arm, all measurements were referenced

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.20: (a) Image of dial gauges on the top/front and bottom/back surface of the MSP while taking measurements as the table was rotated. (b) Graph showing the variation in both the top and bottom surface. Both of these surfaces follow the same trends. The orange line shows the front/top of the plate while the blue line shows the back/bottom of the plate. The blue line has been offset by 30 μm .

to the centre of the MSP's inner diameter. Given that the Faro Arm was employed to determine the positioning of the SMRs, understanding the relationship between the inner and outer diameters of the MSP was essential. This knowledge was particularly crucial for determining the relative placement of the mounting blocks in relation to the MSP's outer diameter. The relationship between the inner and outer

Figure 3.21: Inner and Outer MSP run-outs and centre comparison.

diameter is shown in Figure 3.21.

3.9 Lens-Cell and Barrel Alignment

Each lens of the WFC had a requisite tolerance to which they were to be mounted into their respective lens cells. A full description of the optical prescription data can be found in Azais et al. (2016) and Table 3.1. The lenses as shown in Figure 3.1, describe the optical lens layout with L1 being the largest lens at 0.9m in diameter and with the only aspheric surface, while the rest of the lenses (L2, L3 and L4) being 0.65m in diameter. UCL was responsible for the alignment and mounting of the L1 and L4 lenses into their respective cells, while Kiwistar Optics were responsible for the mounting of the L2 and L3 lenses into their cells. UCL was then tasked with reviewing the manufacturing tolerances of L2 and L3 as well as integrating all of these lenses with the ADC unit, and full assembly.

Accurate measurements of the elements interfaces and mating surfaces such as the cell flange surfaces were first produced. These measurements pertain to the heights of the components along the z-axis. These included the L1 cell flange which connected to Tube A, the L3 OBP plate surface which mated with the bottom of Tube A and finally the MSP. The measurement of the flange positions when combined with the lens crown to cell base measurements after mounting allowed a spacer thickness to be determined that would put the lens in the correct position relative to the focal plane. All measurements were within $100\mu m$ of the nominal positions except for the L3 inner bearing plate flange to base of tube C which had a deviation of $\sim 300\mu m$ from the nominal position (this was a manufacturing issue and had already been given a nominal spacer thickness). These differences were adjusted using machinable spacers and were added to the final assembly to ensure the distance from each lens to the MSP/Focal Surface Plane (FSP) was consistent with the optical design. The results of the shims are described in section 3.17.

3.9.1 Alignment of L2 and L3

L2 and L3 form the ADC unit and sit very close together. As L2 and L3 had to be integrated into the ADC unit, the centre of the L2 and L3 inner bearings had to be established as this would become the rotary axis of the lenses. To do this, the L3 inner bearing plate inner diameter was measured in four positions each rotated by

90 degrees to understand how the centre changed as the bearing is rotated. From this, the centre was calculated by finding an average of the 4 positions. The same process was carried out for L2. Both the L2 and L3 inner bearing plates centre were aligned to each other to be within $\sim 20\mu m$ and aligned to the L3 outer bearing plate to within $\sim 40\mu m$ (Figures [3.22](#) & [3.23](#)).

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.22: (a) Plot showing the L2 inner bearing plate inner diameter run-out when rotated through 4 positions 90 degrees apart. (b) Plot showing the corrected L2 Inner bearing plate inner diameter centres with the L3 outer bearing plate centre.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.23: (a) Plot showing the L3 bearing inner diameter run-out in 4 different positions as it was rotated through 90 degrees. The plot shows that it is rather distorted from a circle and displays the 4 centres of each of the 4 positions. (b) Plot showing the L3 bearing inner diameter 4 centres (of the 4 different positions as it was rotated through 90 degrees as shown in Figure 3.22) corrected using the L3 outer bearing centre to find how the centres compare

Once the inner bearing centres were confirmed, the L2 and L3 lens surface and centres were measured (Figures 3.24 and 3.25), before measurements of lenses relative to the mating surfaces on the cell were taken. We conducted measurements on the cell flange to ensure that its bottom surface was flat and true. This was done to ensure that any further run-out would be attributed to the lens rather than the cell flange when the lens was inserted. The L2 lens top surface was measured using the dial gauges and gave a run-out of $\sim 500\mu m$ (discussed in more detail in section 3.16.2 and Figure 3.73). A wedge was put into both L2 and L3 by Kiwistar Optics which was part of the manufacturing specification and was within the manufacturing tolerances. The initial measurements of L2 showed that it had $\sim 450\mu m$ of run-out due to the wedge on the surface of L2, along with an additional $50\mu m$ of tilt relative to the cell flange. The L2 cell flange run-out was then minimised. Following this, we remeasured both the top and bottom surfaces of the lens. The bottom surface was found to be tilted, giving a run-out of $\sim 50\mu m$ (which happened to be in the same direction as the wedge). In the final set up, there was an additional $\sim 40\mu m$ of run-out which is likely caused by the roughness of the mating surface. The L3 Lens top surface was measured in the same way using the dial gauges and gave a total run-out of $48\mu m$. The centres of the L2 and L3 lenses in the ADC unit were found in the same way as the inner bearing centres, by rotating the bearing axis by 90° (this time using the ADC motors that were tested at UCL) in 4 positions and finding an average.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.24: (a) Image showing the L2 lens flat surface being measured by a dial gauge while in the ADC unit. (b) Showing L2 lens and cell being lowered into the ADC unit. In this image, the L3 lens is also visible.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.25: (a) Image showing the L3 outer bearing plate and L3 lens being measured with dial gauges while supported on the rotary table using jacks. (b) Image showing a closeup of the L2 lens top surface in the ADC unit after measurements have been taken.

3.10 L1 and L4 Cell alignment

UCL oversaw the alignment and assembly of lenses L1 and L4, this included the in-house production of RTV pads which facilitated precise procurement and manufacturing (see more in section 3.14.1). These RTV pads were used for affixing the lenses to the cells and comprised of both axial pads which the lens sat on, and radial pads which held the lens in position to the cell. These precise measurements were crucial for installing the lenses as centrally as possible. Measurements were taken using the dial gauges and the Laser Displacement Sensor (LDS) to work out the centre of the pads.

Figure 3.26 illustrates several measurements conducted utilising both dial gauges and the LDS for the L1 and L4 cells described.

Figure 3.26: (a) Labelled photo of the L1 cell top surface being measured with a dial gauge and simultaneously measuring the L1 pad heights with the LDS. (b) Image showing the L4 cell housed within Tube D, while the L4 cell angled surface is being measured. In both images we can see the red RTV square axial pads that both the L1 and L4 lens will be placed.

3.10.1 L1 Cell

The centres of the L1 cell are plotted against the centre of the L3 outer bearing plate at the time of measurement. These plotted L1 centres include the centre of L1 radial pads surface (measured using LDS), the centre of the L1 inner bore, and the run-out of the L1 outer diameter. These measurements indicate that all centres are well

aligned, with a discrepancy of approximately $10\mu\text{m}$ between them (refer to Figure 3.27).

Figure 3.27: The plot illustrates the L1 cell centres for the inner bore, radial pads, and outer diameter run-out in comparison to the diameter of the L3 outer bearing plate. All L1 cell centres are found to be within approximately $10\mu\text{m}$ of the centre of the L3 outer bearing plate. The centre of the L3 outer bearing plate diameter was recorded as $(-0.82, -0.75)$ during these measurements.

3.10.2 L4 Cell

3.10.2.1 L4 cell angled surface run-out to L3 OBP diameter centre

Since the L4 lens cell featured convex surfaces on both sides, the surface on which the lens would rest was angled. This angled surface was measured with reference to the surface of the L3 outer bearing plate. Figure 3.28 and 3.29 illustrate plots of the L4 cell's angled surface centre compared to the surface of the L3 outer bearing at the time of measurement along with the L4 cell radial pads. It is evident from the plot in Figure 3.29 that the L4 cell's angled surface is offset from the L3 outer bearing plate to approximately $20\mu\text{m}$ of each other (+X by $\sim 17\mu\text{m}$ and in +Y by $\sim 14\mu\text{m}$).

Figure 3.28: Plot showing the L4 cell angled surface run-out to L3 outer bearing plate diameter.

3.10.2.2 L4 cell radial pads surface (pre-RTV added) offset to angled surface and L3 OBP diameter centre

Continuing the L4 cell measurements, the LDS was employed to measure the L4 radial insert surfaces (prior to RTV application), along with the L4 angled surface and the L3 outer bearing plate. These measurements were essential before applying the RTV pads, allowing for any necessary adjustments to the pad heights. A discrepancy of approximately $\sim 10\mu\text{m}$ was observed in the L4 radial insert surfaces; however, this offset was accounted for with the RTV pads, as their thickness could be adjusted and is discussed later in section 3.14.2.2. It's worth noting that this offset falls well within the tolerance of the RTV pads.

Figure 3.30 illustrates the comparison of the centre of the L4 outer cell wall, L4 angled surface, and the diameter of the L3 outer bearing plate. Due to space constraints during assembly and the necessity for an accessible reference surface reachable with the probe, the L4 outer cell wall serves as the reference surface for L4. This reference will be utilised to verify the centre after inserting the L4 lens.

Figure 3.29: The plot illustrates the relationship between the L4 cell radial pads surface, L4 cell angled surface, and the diameter of the L3 outer bearing plate. It's apparent that there is a shift of approximately $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ in the L4 cell pads, indicating a very centered position. The use of RTV pads allows for adjustment to accommodate this slight offset, which falls within the tolerance of the RTV pads. Given that this is an N-BK7 system, the RTV pads are relatively thick, resulting in a negligible percentage difference in thickness.

Figure 3.30: Plot showing the L4 outer cell wall centre, L4 cell angled surface and L4 radial pads surface compared to the L3 outer bearing plate diameter. The outer diameter of L4 lens was used as the reference surface due to the limited space in assembly. This reference will be used to check the centre after we put the lens in, as we will not be able to access any other surface to check for centring. The plot shows that the L4 outer cell wall centre is well centred compared to the L4 Angled surface and L3 centre however they are all within $\sim 25 \mu\text{m}$. These measurements were taken after L4 has been pinned.

3.10.3 WFC All centres measured after pre-assembly

Figure 3.31 displays all previously measured centres, adjusted relative to the L3 OBP at the time of measurement. Two circles are depicted to indicate that the majority of centres fall within $20\mu\text{m}$ (as shown by the inner circle) of the L3 OBP centre. With this understanding of centre positioning concerning the L3 bearing plate, adjustments to the lenses can be made accordingly during alignment with their respective cells. Given the close proximity of the L3 OBP to the L3 bearing axis (within $20\mu\text{m}$) and the difficulty in accessing the L3 bearing axis during full assembly, aligning to the L3 OBP guaranteed an alignment offset of approximately $20\mu\text{m}$ to its centre. Additionally, it is noteworthy that L2 has a significantly larger tolerance compared to the other lenses.

Figure 3.31: The plot displays all the measured centres, centred around the L3 outer bearing plate. Two circles, one with a radius of $30\mu\text{m}$ (inner circle) and the other with a radius of $50\mu\text{m}$ (outer circle), are included to visually represent the proximity to the L3 outer bearing plate.

3.11 Lens Cells to L3 OBP

3.11.0.1 Tube A

To determine the distance between the L1 cell mating surface and the L3 OBP, measurements of the two sections of Tube A, on which the L1 cell is positioned, were necessary. Tube A underwent measurement using three distinct methods: the Faro arm, vernier calipers, and a micrometer, ensuring precision and consistency. Measurements were taken from the cell flange of Tube A. Figure 3.32 depicts an image of Tube A pinned to the MSP, during the dry assembly with the L1 cell attached at the top end and resting on the rotary table.

Figure 3.32: Image depicting the unpainted section of Tube A (part i and part ii together) prior to measurement, mounted on the rotary table with the L1 cell attached.

Figure 3.33 illustrates strong agreement between Vernier and micrometer measurements, with both falling within $\pm 10\mu\text{m}$ of each other. Although Faro arm measurements in Figure 3.33 slightly exceed these values, the average remains within $30\mu\text{m}$ of Vernier and micrometer measurements. In the bottom plot, Faro arm, Vernier, and micrometer measurements exhibit a variation of approximately $40\mu\text{m}$.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.33: Plot showing the height measurements using 3 different measuring techniques of (a) Tube A front section (part i) and (b) Tube A back section (part ii). *N.B – the tail in the micrometer measurement in the top plot seen in green, is due to plotting a power trend line to the data and is not indicative of a real result.*

By combining all three methods, our accuracy in determining the total height of Tube A is within $\pm 60 \mu\text{m}$, well within tolerance. While the Faro arm demonstrates reliability from measurement to measurement, slight discrepancies may arise due to the instrument operating at its maximum reach or systematic errors in calibrating the plane utilised by the Faro arm.

3.11.0.2 Distance of L1 cell mating surface (top of tube A) to L3 OBP top

The distance from the L1 cell mating surface to the L3 outer bearing plate was determined by measuring the heights of both parts of Tube A (part i and ii), as illustrated in Figure 3.33. Combining these measurements with those from the Faro arm yields an accuracy of $\pm 30 \mu\text{m}$ for the overall height of Tube A.

$$\begin{aligned} & \textit{Height of Tube A (part i)} + \textit{Height of Tube A (part ii)} \\ & = (573.030 \pm 0.021) + (572.971 \pm 0.011) \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

$$\textit{Total Height of Tube A} = 1146.001 \pm 0.032\text{mm}$$

To calculate the total distance from the L1 cell mating surface to the L3 OBP, the height of Tube A was added to the distance from Tube C to the L3 plate, resulting in:

$$\text{L1 cell mating surface to the L3 OBP distance} = 1218.067 \pm 0.049 \text{ mm}$$

The overall flatness of the L1 lens flange along with the L1 cell top surface was compared with the underside of Tube C (see Figure 3.34) showing similar peaks and troughs when bolted on Tube A, which suggests a possible projection affect taking place, with all surfaces displaying a tilt of $\sim \pm 5 \mu\text{m}$.

3.11.0.3 Distance of L2 IBP cell mating surface to L3 OBP top

To establish the distance from L2 to the L3 OBP, it was necessary to conduct multiple individual measurements due to accessibility limitations preventing a single measurement. This section describes the various measurements required to determine the final value. These measurements encompassed the distance from the L2 Inner Bearing Plate (IBP) to the L3 IBP (see Figure 3.35), the distance from the L3 IBP to the rotary table (see Figure 3.36), and finally, the distance from the L3 IBP cell mating surface to the L3 OBP top surface.

Figure 3.34: Plot showing the flatness variation of the L1 flange surface compared to both L1 cell top surface run out and Tube C. The three surfaces exhibit a comparable pattern, with the L1 flange top surface and L1 cell top surface run-out showing a variation of $\sim \pm 20 \mu\text{m}$. All surfaces exhibit a slight tilt of $\sim \pm 5 \mu\text{m}$.

3.11.0.4 Distance of L3 IBP cell mating surface to L3 OBP top

This measurement was calculated from ‘Distance from L3 Inner Flange (top surface) to Rotary Table’ minus ‘Distance of Tube C (underside) to L3 Outer Bearing Plate (Top)’

$$\text{Height of L3 Inner diameter to L3 Outer diameter} = 31.816 \pm 0.019 \text{ mm}$$

3.11.0.5 Distance of L4 cell mating surface (bottom of tube D) to L3 OBP top

The height measurements of Tube D were obtained using both a micrometer and the Faro gage arm, with the rotary table serving as a reference point. The results, depicted in Figure 3.37, indicate a variation of approximately $\pm 20 \mu\text{m}$ between the measurements. A value of $180.961 \pm 0.022 \text{ mm}$ was derived by averaging these two measurements. This distance corresponds to the distance between the L4 cell mating surface and the top surface of the L3 outer bearing plate.

3.11.0.6 Comparison of Tube C (underside) flatness to L3 OBP (Top) Flatness

The flatness of Tube C and the L3 OBP were analysed (Figure 3.38). Since these surfaces exhibit a comparable trend, with peaks and troughs generally aligning (ex-

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.35: (a) Illustrates the variation in distance between the mating surface of the L2 bearing plate cell and the inner bearing plate of L3 *when rotating L2*. Additionally, (b) demonstrates the difference in distance between the mating surface of the L2 bearing plate cell and the inner bearing plate of L3 *while rotating L3*. Measurements were conducted using vernier calipers, with four repetitions for each measurement, and the averages were calculated.

cept for two discrepant points), it is uncertain whether there is a tilt in the measurements of Tube C flatness. Consequently, the observed variations in Tube C flatness ($\pm 10\mu\text{m}$) and L3 OBP flatness ($\pm 20\mu\text{m}$) are considered genuine surface variations.

Combining these measurements with those previously outlined enables us to precisely calculate the overall distances between the WFC elements. This com-

Figure 3.36: Plot showing the distance from L3 inner bearing plate top surface to the rotary table. Measurements were taken using vernier calipers and repeated 4 times to give an average. This surface is measured flat to $\pm 22 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 3.37: Tube D Height measured using the two different measurements of the micrometer and the Faro arm.

prehensive analysis aids in identifying surface variations that could potentially influence offsets or tilts during the assembly process and lens potting within their respective cells.

Figure 3.38: Tube C flatness compared with L3 OBP flatness.

3.12 All Heights Measurements

Table 3.6 shows a summary of all the measured and calculated distances and heights, and illustrates that most of the measured distances/heights align closely with the uncertainties specified in the drawing, except for the MSP height. The measured thickness of the MSP is 29.692 ± 0.01 mm, indicating a difference of approximately $300 \mu\text{m}$ from the drawing measurement. However, this variation has been acknowledged and is a recognised discrepancy. The error tabulated also encompasses rotational errors, representing an average across multiple rotational positions of the bearing plate.

3.12.1 Lens Cell Flange Measurements

The vertical positions of the cell flanges from the MSP surface were gauged to determine the distance between the crown of the lenses and the base of the cell flanges upon insertion into their respective cells. This enabled the precise determination of each lens's absolute distance relative to the MSP surface.

All measurements displayed in the table 3.7 align closely with the drawing measurements, with discrepancies generally within $\sim 100 \mu\text{m}$. However, the measurement for the L3 flange to MSP deviates by approximately $300 \mu\text{m}$. To rectify these variances, shims of specified thicknesses were fabricated and utilised. Further details on the shim thicknesses will be discussed in section 3.17.

Table 3.6: Height measurements from the WFC CAD drawings to the actual measured heights for the WFC constituents' parts, along with the instruments used for measurements.

WFC Element Measurement	Production Drawing Specs (mm)	Measured Distance (mm)	Instrument Used
Tube C Thickness	47.00 ± 0.1	47.06 ± 0.005	Vernier Calipers
Tube C to L3OBP	72.00 ± 0.2	72.066 ± 0.018	Vernier Calipers
Tube C Bottom to Rotary Table		31.816 ± 0.019	Calculated
Height of L3OBP	25.00 ± 0.1	25.006 ± 0.017	Vernier Calipers
Height of L3 Inner to Outer Diam		31.816 ± 0.019	Vernier Calipers
Tube A Height	1146.00 ± 0.1	1146.001 ± 0.032	Vernier Calipers +
Part i) Front	573.00 ± 0.1	573.030 ± 0.021	Micrometer +
Part ii) Rear	573.00 ± 0.1	572.971 ± 0.011	Faro arm
Tube D Height (L4 cell mating surface to L3 OBP top)	181.00 ± 0.1	180.962 ± 0.02	Micrometer + Faro arm
MSP Thickness	* 30.00 ± 0.1	29.684 ± 0.011	Micrometer
Distance from L2 IBP to L3 IBP †		129.776 ± 0.044	Vernier Calipers
Distance from L3 IBP Rotary Table		93.717 ± 0.022	Vernier Calipers
Distance from L3 Inner Flange to Rotary Table		103.882 ± 0.008	Vernier Calipers

* - The MSP measured thickness is 29.684 ± 0.01 where there is $\sim 300\mu\text{m}$ of difference from the drawing measurement.

† - This error includes rotational errors, which is an average over several rotational positions of the bearing plate.

Lens Flange to MSP	Nominal positions (mm)	Measured Distance (mm)
L1 Flange to MSP	1218.0	1218.067 ± 0.049
L2 Flange to MSP	191.5	191.677 ± 0.085
L3 Flange to MSP	61.6	61.901 ± 0.041
L4 Flange to MSP	-134.0	-133.902 ± 0.03

Table 3.7: Calculated vertical distance measurements from the lens cell flanges relative to the MSP surface. L4 flange distance is negative as its position is below the MSP.

3.13 Painting

Several layers of paint (Aeroglaze two-component epoxy primer 9741A and Aeroglaze Z306 black paint) were applied to both the outer and inner components of the WFC barrel and cells. The first priming coat served as a foundational layer upon which the black paint was subsequently applied. Figure 3.39 depicts some of the components with the first primer coat applied (in red) before the second black coat was added once dry. The following surfaces were painted:

- Tube A sections inner and outer surfaces (including inspection port covers).
- Tube A baffle brackets
- L1 cell outer and inner surfaces
- L4 cell outer and inner surface
- Retaining rings for L1 and L4
- Oil guard inner surface
- Permanent baffle

The L2 outer bearing plate's surface was found too smooth for adhesion of the Aeroglaze paint so this was blackened with Edding 800 permanent marker. This was done after the installation of the L2 and L3 during final assembly.

Figure 3.39: (a) Aeroglaze two-component epoxy primer 9741A applied to the Tube A components (*top*: part ii, *bottom*: part i). (b) Aeroglaze Z306 black paint applied to the Tube A components and baffle brackets.

3.14 Lens to Cell Alignment: L1 and L4

3.14.1 RTV pads

Lenses were mounted to their cells using pads made from RTV560 silicone rubber. RTV rubbers are known to have high CTE value and so a thin layer of RTV can compensate for the difference in the CTEs between the lens and the cell (Antonik et al., 2009). Two types of pads, axial and radial, are employed in the potting process for the lenses. The procedure for creating the RTV pads in this study has been extensively described in prior research (Doel et al., 2012; Fata et al., 2004), and illustrated in Figure 3.40. The thicknesses of both axial and radial pads utilised for potting lenses (L1 and L4) in this study play a crucial role in WFC assembly. Before this study, finite element analysis (FEA) was conducted to ascertain the thickness and dimensions of the RTV pads. The pad thickness was engineered to render the lens-cell assembly nearly athermal, thereby minimising induced stresses. A methodology akin to that validated in previous literature (Antonik et al., 2009) was

used for the potting of the L1 and L4 lenses at UCL. The process of making the RTV involved mixing the RTV560 base compound and the curing agent together as shown in Figure 3.40, which was then degassed in a vacuum until the bubbling of the mixture stopped. The mixture was then placed into a mould (to ensure that all the pads were of uniform thickness, which was subsequently tested) where it was then left for 24 hours to cure at room temperature. Once cured, and released from the mould the RTV radial pads were trimmed to the appropriate dimensions for subsequent attachment onto the lens cell inserts using adhesive. Each lens was cleaned using Isopropyl alcohol (Propan-2) before adding Momentive SS4004P³ as a primer to help with adhesion. The glue used for this process was RTV560 itself. The addition of primers such as Momentive SS4004P to the metal and glass allows the RTV to cure to these materials and creates a strong bond. Besides applying adhesive, the designated areas on the cell surface where the pads were to be attached were scored to improve the adhesion of the pads. The radial pads were then inserted through the cell and glued to the lens (24 for L1 and 36 for L4). This procedure was carried out for both the radial and axial pads for L1 and L4. The axial pads for L4 can be seen in Figure 3.41.

Following the initial measurement of lens cell flatness and surface characteristics of the WFC elements, the lenses were affixed into their respective cells using RTV pads as an interface between the lens and cells. The axial pads were securely bonded into the cells with a thin layer of RTV. These axial pads serve the purpose of uniformly supporting the lens and compensating for any irregularities in the cell support surface (RTV pads are designed to compress by about 70-100 μ m under the weight of the lenses). Ensuring the axial pads can compress to accommodate any variations in pad height and lens positioning is crucial. However, they must also maintain sufficient stiffness to secure the lens in place as the telescope moves away from its zenith position. The axial pads were situated to ensure their surfaces aligned with the cell flange and remained parallel to it. The aim was to get the surfaces of the axial pads within a tolerance of $\pm 25\mu$ m. Post-installation, the surface posi-

³SS4004P is a pink primer from Momentive Performance Materials formulated for use with RTV silicone rubber adhesive sealants.

tion and height of the axial pads were verified using the Laser Displacement Sensor (LDS), revealing them to be within $10\mu m$ of the same plane (see Figure 3.42). If a pad was discovered to be outside of this range, it was removed and sanded to the appropriate height, before undergoing re-measurement. The dimensions of the RTV pads were carefully selected to provide consistent support for each lens, effectively mitigating irregularities of the mounting surface.

Figure 3.40: (a) Image showing the RTV silicone rubber mixture before it would be placed into its moulds and left to cure for 24 hours. Images (b) and (c) show the L1 and L4 cell radial pads respectively, that have been glued to the radial inserts for L1 and L4. (d) shows the inserts being given another coat of the silicone rubber mixture before being glued to the lens.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.41: (a) Image showing the process of scoring the surface of a cell where an RTV will be placed. The scratching of the cell aids in the RTV pad sticking to the cell along with the use of a primer. (b) Image showing the L4 cell with its 12 axial RTV pads (red squares) in place on the L4 angled surface, where the L4 lens will rest.

Figure 3.42: Image of the L1 axial pads being measured using the Laser Displacement Sensor. Measurements were taken in the centre of the pad as can be seen from bright spot on the pad where the laser beam hits. Figure also shows the angled surface where the axial pads rest along with the radial insert holes.

3.14.2 Lenses into cells

The cell design for L1 and L4 are discussed in section 3.3.2 and closely resemble that of DECam (Doel et al., 2012). L1 and L4 differ slightly in that L4 features an angled surface where the axial pads are affixed and where the lens is positioned whereas for L1 cell the axial pads are on a flat surface. Additionally, there are periodic holes on the sides of the cell where the radial pads are inserted to secure the lens in place (see Figures 3.42 and 3.44). To insert a lens into its cell, the lens is placed on a distributive load support system (whiffletree-like stage, shown in Figure 3.43). Extreme care was taken to space the support points of the 12-point whiffletree system so that the lens did not distort in anyway. Further information on a comparable procedure can be located in the literature regarding a similar WFC project on DECam on the Blanco Telescope (Doel et al., 2012; Honscheid et al., 2008).

Positioning the lenses within their cells is a complex and intricate procedure. The precision screw jacks integrated into the whiffletree (seen in Figure 3.43) reg-

Figure 3.43: (a) L4 lens being supported by the 12-point whiffletree structure on the rotary table, while the L4 cell rests on the red jack before being elevated to align with the lens. (b) A bird's-eye view of the L4 lens as the jacks elevate the lens cell. Dial gauges are visible, measuring the lens cell to ensure level raising. The axial pads of the L4 lens cell are also depicted in red on the inner surface of the lens cell.

ulate the tip and tilt of the lens. Centering of the lens/whiffletree assembly is facilitated by translation stages with the assistance of sprung adjustment screws. This setup provides excellent control over the optical surfaces, achieving accuracy down to the micrometer level. The cell is gradually elevated to support the lens, ensuring the cell remains level on all sides. This is achieved by incrementally adjusting each jack to achieve the correct height until the axial pads within the cell make contact with the lens. The larger jacks move the lens cell into place by carrying out larger movements ($\sim 100\mu\text{m}$).

Once the lens cell was close enough to the lens (within 2mm), the jacks were replaced with aluminium posts and precision screw jacks to raise the lens cell in finer incremental steps ($5\text{-}10\mu\text{m}$). A dial gauge was used to check the run-out to ensure all sides were raised equally until the pads began to make contact with the lens. The dial gauge would run at the edge of the optical surface, outside of the clear aperture of the lens. At this stage, the positions of both the lens and the cell were re-measured to establish their positions before the radial pads were glued in place.

Figure 3.44: (a) L1 lens being supported on the 12-point whiffletree structure on the rotary table before being put into its cell. (b) L1 lens resting on the axial pads in L1 cell before the RTV pads are inserted (the white visible circles shown are where the whiffletree structure is supporting the lens).

If the positioning did not meet specifications, the cell was retracted and realigned. Contact between the RTV axial pad and glass was easily visible through the glass, providing a clear indication of the alignment and contact between the cell and lens.

3.14.2.1 Radial pad procedure

The procedure for attaching the radial pads involved the following steps. Initially, the radial pads were screwed into their inserts without being glued to the lens. Instead, a paper of appropriate thickness (approximately $40\mu\text{m}$) was inserted to fill the gap between the RTV of the radial pads and the outer diameter of the lens (Figure 3.45). This action effectively secured the entire system in place. Opposite pairs of the radial pads were removed and the glass was primed with adhesive before the freshly glued RTV pads were reinserted. Two pairs of opposing pads at 90° to each other were glued in at a time and allowed to cure before moving on to the next set of radial pads. This procedure continued until all pads were inserted to ensure minimal movement in any one direction of the lens until the process was complete and the lens was fully glued to the cell. The same procedure was carried out for both L1 and L4.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.45: (a) L4 lens in its cell with the 40 μm paper stopping the RTV pad inserts from touching the lens before they get glued in place. (b) Final assembly of L1 lens in L1 cell after RTV pads have been inserted and rest of the L1 cell has been painted black.

3.14.2.2 L4 lens into cell

While remeasuring the L4 cell with the added axial pads, we also returned to the centre of the L3 OBP to take measurements, as this served as our reference point. This measurement was compared to the previous measurement of the L3 OBP to assess any displacement (see Figure 3.46). It appeared that the L3 OBP had become slightly more circular, possibly due to improved support compared to the previous

Figure 3.46: Measurement of the centre of the L3 outer bearing plate diameter alongside the previous measurement. This graph illustrates the remarkable stability of the L3 outer bearing plate, with the centre showing minimal movement of no more than approximately $10\mu\text{m}$ between measurements.

measurement. This indicates the stability of the L3 OBP, with movement not exceeding approximately $10\mu\text{m}$ between measurements.

The heights of the L4 axial pads on the angled surface were assessed using the LDS. Initially, the pad heights were measured to examine the variation in height, depicted by the blue line in Figure 3.47 of which there was a variation of $\sim \pm 50\mu\text{m}$. Subsequently, a procedure was developed to 'machine' the pads, removing material by sanding them, removing microns at a time and remeasured to ensure that they all fell within the range of $\pm 10\mu\text{m}$, as illustrated by the orange line.

The measured flatness of the L4 cell's top surface (depicted in Figure 3.48) exhibits a variation of approximately $\pm 50\mu\text{m}$, consistent with previous measurements. This consistency underscores the repeatability of our results and suggests no significant alteration in the structure of the cell.

Measurements were then conducted on the outer wall of the L4 cell to verify alignment and compare it with previous results. The centres shown in Figure 3.49 are referenced to the centre of the L3 OBP. These measurements were taken after L4 was put into the ADC set up. It's observed that the outer wall of the L4 cell

Figure 3.47: The heights of the L4 cells axial pads on the angled surface assessed using the LDS. The plot displays measurements of pad heights before (blue line) and after sanding (orange line).

Figure 3.48: Plot showing the L4 cell top surface flatness, and demonstrates that it varies by around $\pm 50 \mu\text{m}$ and follows the same trend as our previous measurement which ensures that there has been no damage or change in the cell.

has shifted in the +X direction by approximately $30 \mu\text{m}$ compared to the previous measurement. The shift in these measurements from before and after in ADC set up could be attributed to the repositioning resulting from the use of fiducials, which may cause a slight movement when bolted up. Furthermore, as the system is loaded and elements are bolted together, the entire system flexes and stresses are introduced, which may result in a possible tilt that could also explain some of the differences observed. Time constraints prevented us from conducting multiple measurements to ascertain repeatability for this measurement. Nevertheless, these measurements affirm that we remain comfortably within the established tolerance

Figure 3.49: L4 cell outer cell wall centred on the L3 outer bearing plate. It's noticeable that the outer wall of the L4 cell has shifted in the +X direction by approximately $30\mu\text{m}$, as indicated by the blue circle and its centre. However, the overall shape appears to remain unchanged.

limits.

3.14.2.3 L1 Lens into cell

All lenses were put into their cells to minimise the bottom surface run-out (bottom surface refers to the surface closest to the FSP), so that a wedge (if any) would be expressed on the top surface. The L1 lens was deliberately offset in the cell by $\sim 70\mu\text{m}$ in X and $\sim 30\mu\text{m}$ in Y (see Figure 3.50) to ensure the L1 asphere was centred such that the bottom surface run-out was zeroed (see Figure 3.51). This left a wedge expressed on the upper surface with a run-out of $\pm 40\mu\text{m}$ on the top surface (well within the wedge tolerance). When put into the full final assembly, this changed to $\pm 80\mu\text{m}$ (Figure 3.53). This enhanced run-out may stem from either lens decentering or lens tilt, both of which remain well within tolerance levels. The additional run-out observed during final assembly may be attributed to variations in the flatness of the mating surfaces and a projection effect. Since L1 is positioned atop the tall barrel, even a slight tilt at the bottom could result in increased run-out at the top.

Figure 3.50: Showing the L1 lens in L1 cell, here it is shown that the L1 lens (orange) is displaced from L1 cell (blue) by ~70-80 µm which ensured that the concave surface of L1 was centred to have zero-run out in the cell and ready to be glued with the RTV pads.

Figure 3.51: L1 lens asphere surface (bottom of L1/concave surface) run-out measured using a dial gauge to be within $\pm 1 \mu\text{m}$.

Upon measuring the centre of the L1 lens and comparing it with our reference surface, the L3 OBP, we obtained a centre of (-110.29, 48.21) (Figure 3.52, which once again falls within the specified tolerances for L1. The decentre of L1 relative to its nominal position is reported as (-41.75, 15.13). This decentre is calculated by subtracting the final lens centre from the set position where the lens was initially

Figure 3.52: Plot showing the centre of the L1 lens after it has been glued into the cell, in comparison with the L3 OBP. The coordinates for the L1 lens centre in relation to the L3 outer bearing plate are (-110.29, 48.21), falling within the specified tolerance for the L1 lens centre.

placed in the cell, (-68.54, 33.08), see Table 3.8 for a breakdown. The additional decentre observed in the final assembly may stem from pinning the cell during assembly, which could lead to the cell not returning to its exact position. Additionally, tensions within the system throughout the assembly process may also contribute to cell movement.

In Figure 3.53, it is evident that the wedge is manifested at positions 9-10 of the L1 lens. These positions correspond to the wedge being present in both the X and Y directions.

(Note: Position No.1 denotes +X, approximately No.6 denotes -Y, approximately No.12 denotes -X, and approximately No.18 denotes +Y.)

Figure 3.53: Example showing the L1 lens top surface variation comparing flatness before and after being put into full assembly, along with the difference between them. Measurements taken using a dial gauge, showing the assembled L1 lens top surface to be within $\pm 80\mu m$.

Table 3.8: Table showing the coordinates of the centres for the L1 lens, L1 cell and L3 outer bearing plate relative to each other.

L1	X Coordinate (μm)	Y Coordinate (μm)
Target decentre	-68.54	33.08
Final measured decentre*	-110.29	48.21
Offset from target	-41.75	15.13

* The final position of L1 lens compared to L3 OBP was a direct measurement, as both could be reached in full assembly.

3.14.3 L4 Lens into cell

The process of mating the L4 lens to the L4 cell followed the same procedure as described in the previous section for L1. Both the outer diameter of the L4 lens and the outer diameter of the L4 cell were measured using dial gauges to assess the run-out. This revealed that the lens was centred to the cell with a precision of approximately $10\mu m$, as depicted in Figure 3.54.

In Figure 3.55, it is evident that both the L4 lens and the L4 cell top surface exhibit a similar trend. The surface variation for the L4 lens is approximately $\pm 30\mu m$, which is caused by a tilt giving the smooth sine wave shown, while for the L4 cell, it is around $\pm 40\mu m$. The top surface of the L4 cell has the same tilt (shown by the

Figure 3.54: L4 lens is centred in the lens to within 10 μm . The L4 lens centre was (-0.74, -1.83) while the centre of the L4 cell was (-11.46, -11.30).

Figure 3.55: The graph depicts the variations in the top surfaces of the L4 lens (blue) and the L4 cell (orange) after alignment and mating. These surfaces were measured on the rotary table using a dial gauge and exhibit a similar overall trend. The top surface of the L4 lens shows a variation of $\pm 30\mu\text{m}$, showing a sine wave while the top surface of the L4 cell shows a variation of $\pm 40\mu\text{m}$, both caused by a tilt.

sine wave) with additional noise with discrepant points between positions 19-21, this is due to the L4 cell top surface not being a polished surface. By comparing the measurement of the L4 cell to the L4 lens, we can detect any changes that may indicate a tilt in this surface. Moreover, the run-out observed on the lens's top surface provides insights into the position of the wedge. It suggests that the wedge is predominantly aligned in the X direction, as evidenced by the notable run-out observed around position ~ 3 .

Figure 3.56: The graph illustrates the surface of the L4 lens in two scenarios: during the ADC setup (blue) and when it wasn't in the ADC setup (orange). Both sets of measurements were conducted on the rotary table using a dial gauge.

The data presented in Figure 3.56 outlines the disparity in the surface characteristics of the L4 lens before and after its integration into the Tube D/ADC setup. A variation of $\pm 34\mu\text{m}$ is observed for the top surface of the L4 lens pre-ADC assembly, while a variation of also $\pm 34\mu\text{m}$ is evident for the L4 lens surface during the ADC assembly. This consistency in measurements indicates that the lens position remains unchanged following integration into the ADC assembly, thus affirming its stability.

Direct measurement of L4 in the final assembly was not feasible due to accessibility limitation, and therefore the lens centre had to be deduced by comparing it to the L4 cell. Table 3.9 illustrates that the L4 lens, in relation to the L3 OBP, is centred at (22.27, -7.65). The specified tolerance for the decentre of L4 is $\pm 200\mu\text{m}$, and the provided centre for the alignment of the L4 lens in the cell, compared to the L3 OBP, falls comfortably within this range. With this slight shift in X and Y, it suggests a tilt of approximately $20\mu\text{m}$, evident from the disparity between the two surfaces.

Similarly to L1, when aligning L4, we mounted the lens such that the wedge is expressed on the top surfaces, mainly in the X direction and the bottom surface was flat.

Figure 3.57: Plot showing the L4 cell outer diameter centred on the L3 OBP. This gives a centre of (11.54, -17.12).

Table 3.9: Table showing the coordinates of the centres for the L4 lens, L4 cell and L3 outer bearing plate relative to each other.

L4	X Coordinate (μm)	Y Coordinate (μm)
L4 Lens centre compared to L4 Cell	10.72	9.47
L4 Cell centre compared to L3 OBP	11.54	-17.12
L4 Lens centre compared to L3 OBP	22.27	-7.65

3.15 Laser Alignment Test

3.15.1 Set up

As an additional measure to validate the contact metrology measurements used for the alignment of the lenses, a Laser Alignment System (LAS) (Doel et al., 2012) was developed at UCL. This system aimed to evaluate the relationship between L1 and L4 within the assembled setup, excluding the ADC optics (refer to Figure 3.58 and 3.59). The WFC underwent assembly in two variations on the rotary table to facilitate testing on L1 and L4 separately (one configuration with both L1 and L4, and another solely with L4).

Prior to the lens assembly, meticulous tests were conducted using a retro-reflector and a corner-cube to verify the parallelism and centring of the laser on

the rotary table. Once the system under examination was set up and aligned with L1 and L4 lenses in place, it underwent a complete rotation of 360° , with measurements taken at every 90° . Two cameras were strategically positioned: one below the rotary table to capture the transmitted laser beam and another above to capture the reflected beam.

This comprehensive test aimed to assess four crucial aspects: the transmitted beam of L4, the reflected beam of L4, the combined transmitted beam of L1 and L4, and finally, the reflected beam of L1. The primary objective was to ensure alignment within the measured uncertainties between L1 and L4, to validate L1's consistency with L4 when assembled in the barrel, and to ensure that the results were consistent with the contact metrology measurements. Due to challenges in system alignment, these measurements serve as an independent verification, confirming that all lenses are comfortably within their tolerance limits, and there are no errors in our previous measurements. The centroids of both L1 and L4 determined using the LAS system confirmed that our centres and tilts were well within the required tolerances for both lenses (see Table 3.15).

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.58: (a) Labeled schematic of the laser alignment system employed for testing the optics. The red arrow depicts the trajectory of the laser beam, traversing two 45° mirrors before passing through the WFC system, the rotary table, and finally reaching the camera for the through beam. The green arrows illustrate the reflected path of the laser beam captured by the second camera. (b) Photograph depicting the physical layout of the LAS system in the laboratory (without the WFC) and the path that the laser beam takes.

Figure 3.59: An aerial perspective of the WFC assembly atop the rotary table is depicted, with L1 lens positioned at the apex, serving as the entry point for the laser. Directly beneath L1, a layer of polystyrene foam is strategically placed to prevent any reflections from the L4 lens from interfering with the L1 reflected beam. Additionally, this foam serves as a protective barrier to prevent debris from inadvertently contacting the L4 lens.

Simplified Zemax files were crafted to mimic the Laser Alignment System (LAS) configuration, incorporating L1, L4, and precise distances to the cameras. Subsequently, the outcomes obtained from the LAS were duplicated within Zemax by introducing adjustments to the lens positions to replicate the observed results captured by the cameras.

It's important to note that errors and fluctuations in the laser beam and spot position were highly probable, given the dynamic nature of the system influenced by temperature variations in the laboratory during the measurement period. Moreover, the presence of a sizable metal framework supporting the lasers increases the

likelihood of slight movements within the system, potentially impacting the overall position of the laser spot. An example of the LAS camera image is shown in Figure 3.60.

Figure 3.60: LAS alignment camera image example, showing the diffuse through beam.

3.15.2 LAS: L4 through beam

The first lens tested with the LAS was L4. With the L4 system set up on the rotary table and rotated through 360°.

Figure 3.61: Optical layout from the Zemax file showing the L4 lens through beam set up. In the figure you can see beam passing through the L4 lens reaching the focal plane. The distances in the optical layout correspond to the distances in the LAS system.

LAS Camera position

Figure 3.62: Schematic showing the first position of the L4 through beam on the camera in the +X, -Y quadrant.

LAS			Zemax		
Spot position on camera	Spot motion radius (pixels)	Phase angle for 1st pos.	Lens decentre to reproduce spot	Spot radius (pixels)	Phase angle
+X/-Y	~ 10	~ 52°	(50, -80)	10.2	~ 55°

Table 3.10: Showing the L4 LAS spot position, spot radius and phase angle compared to the Zemax decentre data that reproduced a comparative phase angle and spot size.

The phase angle and spot size of the laser beam on the camera was calculated and compared to the Zemax spot output for a given lens decentre. To match the values given by the LAS system, a decentre of the L4 lens by 50 μ m in +X and 80 μ m in -Y was feed into Zemax which gave a comparable radius size and phase angle as shown in Table 3.10. This gave an output of (30, -44) for the position of the spot which also corresponds to a +X, -Y position. With the known decentre of the L4 lens compared to the L3 OBP to be (22.37, -7.65) μ m, the Zemax data and LAS suggests there is more of a decentre in the -Y direction compared to where we think the lens is. This is still however well within the decentre tolerances for L4 and acts as an independent confirmation that the lens is still within tolerance.

The discrepancy in the LAS system compared to the metrology measurements is possibly due to misalignment of the beam.

3.15.3 LAS: L4 reflected beam

After taking the through beam measurements of L4, we then took measurements of the reflected beam. With the same set up as previous, the rotary table was rotated through 360°.

Figure 3.63: Optical arrangement depicted in the Zemax file illustrating the configuration of the L4 lens reflected beam. Within the figure, the reflection of the beam off the surface of the L4 lens is visible.

Figure 3.64: Schematic showing the first position of the L4 reflected beam on the camera in the -X, -Y quadrant.

LAS			Zemax		
Spot position on camera	Spot motion radius (pixels)	Phase angle for 1st pos.	Lens decentre to reproduce spot	Spot radius (pixels)	Phase angle
-X/-Y	~ 14	~ 27°	(50, -80)	13.5	~ 38°

Table 3.11: Table showing the L4 LAS reflected spot position, spot radius and phase angle compared to the Zemax decentre data that reproduced a comparative phase angle and spot size.

The Zemax spot diagram indicates the spot's position to be at (-333, 260) μm . When considering the reflected beam in Zemax, a flip occurs in the Y-axis due to the mirror setup. Therefore, to align with the LAS beam position on the camera, the Zemax spot position corresponds in the -X, -Y direction.

Any deviation in the beam's position can be attributed to the previously discussed misalignment in the laser system. The laser system experienced fluctuations caused by fringing effects, leading to variability in the spot quality, primarily due to the overall instability of the system. However, employing the same lens decentre values of (50, -80) in Zemax for the L4 reflected beam ensured alignment consistency with the L4 through beam decentre. This alignment yielded a comparable spot radius and phase angle, as illustrated in Table 3.11.

As detailed earlier in the thesis, L4 exhibits a run-out in the +X direction. Testing has confirmed that a tilt in the +X direction results in beam movement in the -Y direction, which of verified by both the LAS beam position and the Zemax spot position. This further validates our contact metrology measurements and independently confirms the precise alignment of the L4 lens well within tolerance.

3.15.4 LAS: L1 and L4 through beam

To facilitate the alignment testing of L1 and L4 with the LAS, the WFC assembly was configured without L2 and L3 (Figure 3.59).

The Zemax spot diagram indicates the spot's position to be at (31, -38) μm , corresponding to a +X, -Y position. It's worth noting that while the primary movement of the beam position occurred in the Y direction, a slight X component has been introduced. Nevertheless, this deviation remains well within tolerance.

As the beam passed through the L4 lens, the same L4 decentering parameters

Figure 3.65: Optical layout from the Zemax file showing the L1 and L4 lens through beam set up. The figure shows the beam passing through both the L1 and L4 lens reaching the focal plane.

Figure 3.66: Schematic showing the first position of the L1 and L4 through beam on the camera in the -X, -Y quadrant.

established previously in Zemax, (50, -80), were utilised for these measurements to assess the impact of the L1 lens. A decentering of (-70, 70) was implemented in Zemax for L1, resulting in a comparable spot radius and phase angle, as demonstrated in the table above. The slightly lower phase angle in Zemax can be attributed to the additional X direction. Given the extensive distances within the setup (exceeding 3 meters) and the beam's trajectory, it's plausible that some movement may induce this X direction shift.

LAS			Zemax		
Spot position on camera	Spot motion radius (pixels)	Phase angle for 1st pos.	Lens decentre to reproduce spot	Spot radius (pixels)	Phase angle
-X/-Y	~ 12	~ 78°	(-70, 70) for L1 & (50, -80) for L4	12	~ 50°

Table 3.12: Table showing the L1 and L4 LAS through beam spot position, spot radius and phase angle compared to the Zemax decentre data that reproduced a comparative phase angle and spot size.

As illustrated in Section 3.14.2.3, where the L1 wedge exhibited not only an expression in the -X direction but also a Y component, this discrepancy could explain the divergence between the LAS beam position on the camera and the Zemax spot position in terms of their exact spatial alignment. This test further confirms that the lenses are well within tolerance.

3.15.5 LAS: L1 reflected beam

Figure 3.67: The optical arrangement depicted in the Zemax file illustrates the setup of the L1 reflected beam. In the figure, you can observe the beam being reflected from the L1 lens.

LAS Camera position

Figure 3.68: Schematic showing the first position of the L1 reflected beam on the camera in the -X, +Y quadrant (looking from the back of the camera).

The Zemax spot diagram reveals the spot's position to be at $(425, -425) \mu\text{m}$, indicating a +X, -Y orientation. In contrast, the LAS camera spot position is reported as -X, +Y.

In the reflected beam analysis in Zemax, a Y-axis flip must be considered due

LAS			Zemax		
Spot position on camera	Spot motion radius (pixels)	Phase angle for 1st pos.	Lens decentre to reproduce spot	Spot radius (pixels)	Phase angle
-X/+Y	~ 101	~ 48°	(425, -425)	115	~ 45°

Table 3.13: Table showing the L1 reflected LAS reflected spot position, spot radius and phase angle compared to the Zemax decentre data that reproduced a comparative phase angle and spot size.

to the mirror setup and camera axis. Consequently, the LAS beam position on the camera aligns with the Zemax spot position in the Y-axis, yet there exists a discrepancy in the X position, likely attributable to laser beam alignment in the LAS setup.

From these LAS and Zemax measurements, it can be concluded that there are no significant errors in the lenses, as comparable spots motions, sizes and phase angles were achieved for both L1 and L4. Since the run-out of the L1 lens primarily occurs in the -X, -Y position, as depicted in Section 3.14.2.3, Figure 3.53, this tilt accounts for the observed camera position, thus validating our metrology measurements. As mentioned at the start of the section, these measurements serve as an independent verification, confirming that all lenses are well within their tolerance limits.

3.16 ADC Lens measurements

3.16.1 L3 Lens in ADC

Figure 3.69: (a) Image showing an overview of the L3 element as it was lowered into in the ADC unit using the in house crane and straps. Demonstrating the cautious placement of L3 into the ADC assembly, ensuring it is held securely with the lifting tool until properly positioned. (b) L3 lens surface being measured with a dial gauge. Additionally, in this image, the exposed gear system for the ADC is visible, coated with a thick layer of grease to promote smooth operation.

Figure 3.70: Surface variation of the lens is approximately $\pm 24\mu\text{m}$, measured while L3 was in the ADC setup.

Figure 3.71: Plot (a) shows three circles representing the L3 Lens run-out at different positions as it was rotated through 90 degrees using the ADC motors, corrected using the L3 outer bearing centre. Plot (b) displays the three centres of the L3 Lens corrected using the L3 outer bearing centre, with an average centre of (6.79, 7.10).

Due to the layout of the ADC, L3 had to be measured and assembled into the system prior to the placement of L2, as L2 sat above L3. L3 can be seen being put into position in Figure 3.69.

Once L3 was securely positioned, the top surface of L3 lens was measured and a variation of $\sim\pm 24\mu\text{m}$ was found (Figure 3.70). These measurements provided assurance that L3 met the required tolerance levels. Figure 3.71 displays the three centres of the L3 Lens corresponding to its different positions as it was rotated through 90 degrees using the ADC motors, corrected using the L3 outer bearing centre. The centre of these corrected positions is given by fitting the coordinates of the three points, resulting in (6.79, 7.10) as the corrected centre for the L3 lens.

3.16.2 L2 Lens in ADC

After successfully mating L2 with the bearing plate (as shown in Figure 3.72), we used dial gauges to measure a run-out of about $500\mu\text{m}$ on the top surface of L2 compared to its mating surface on the L2 cell (see Figure 3.73). Initial assessments revealed that this run-out was caused by a $450\mu\text{m}$ wedge on the surface of L2, along with an additional $50\mu\text{m}$ of tilt.

To determine this extra tilt, we zeroed the bottom surface of L2. By doing so, we found that there was indeed a wedge present when measuring the top surface.

Subsequently, we flattened the cell flange and took measurements again for both the top and bottom surfaces. It turned out that the bottom surface displayed a tilt, resulting in a run-out of approximately $50\mu\text{m}$, predominately in the same direction as the wedge.

After everything was bolted in the final setup, an additional $40\mu\text{m}$ of run-out was measured, likely attributable to the roughness of the mating surface.

Figure 3.72: (a) Image showing the L2 bearing plate being lowered onto tube C with the gears of the ADC exposed. (b) Showing L2 lens and cell being lowered into the ADC unit.

Figure 3.74 displays the four centres of the L2 Lens corresponding to its different positions as it was rotated through 90 degrees using the ADC motors, adjusted using the L3 outer bearing centre. Ideally, these points should form a square, reflecting the 90-degree rotation at each position. On repeatability measurements, we found an accuracy of $\sim \pm 5\mu\text{m}$ and indicates our measurement accuracy, which may represent our limit of precision. Assuming an error of approximately $5\mu\text{m}$ for each measurement, the desired square shape is achieved. The centre of these four corrected positions is determined by averaging the coordinates of the four points, resulting in (19.51, -16.04).

Figure 3.73: L2 lens top surface measurements taken using a dial gauge. This plot shows the variation on the surface of the lens to be approximately $\pm 250 \mu\text{m}$ which is consistent over the two dates that what measurements were taken. The mismatch in the two lines is due to a shift in the starting position of the measurements.

Figure 3.74: (a) Four circles representing the run-out of the L2 Lens at different positions as it was rotated through 90 degrees using the ADC motors. These circles are adjusted using the L3 outer bearing centre. A chosen diameter of 100 was used to plot the data. Subsequently, the centres of these four circles would be determined and averaged to ascertain the true centre. (b) L2 Lens centres corrected using the L3 outer bearing centre, with a centre of (19.51, -16.04).

Lens to FSP	Zemax Measurements (mm)	Measured Distance (mm)	Shim Thickness (mm)
L1 to FSP	1925.458	1917.8797	7.578
L2 to FSP	625.229	620.281	4.948
L3 to FSP	434.969	429.232	5.737
L4 to FSP	333.278	335.237	1.959

Table 3.14: Lens to Focal Surface Point (FSP) as defined by Zemax V8 2022-01-25, to work out the necessary Shim thicknesses to be added to the WFC.

3.17 Shim Thickness Verification

Measurements were conducted for each lens to ascertain the required shim thicknesses necessary to achieve the correct focal length distances. Additionally, the vertical positions of the cell flanges from the MSP surface were measured as discussed in section 3.12.1. This enabled the determination of the distance between the crown of the lenses and the base of the cell flanges upon insertion into their respective cells, thereby establishing the absolute distance of each lens relative to the MSP surface.

The calculated shim thickness measurements are available in Table 3.14.

3.18 Alignment Results and Final Assembly

The assembly requirements were dictated by the lens alignment and lens tolerances (can be found in Table 3.3). After all lenses were potted in their cells and all measurements of the components taken, including distances from each lens to the focal surface, and shim thicknesses, the first step in final assembly was aligning the L2/L3 lenses to the L3 OBP and integrating it into the ADC unit. The L3 OBP was our main reference surface as this was one of the few surfaces we could reach for the majority of the measurements. L4 and Tube D were subsequently integrated to the ADC and together the whole ADC unit including L4 and Tube D were bolted to the

MSP. This initial assembly of the lower section of the WFC was carried out on the rotary table and supported using jacks. After the lower section had been integrated to the MSP, the outward facing surface of L2 cell was blackened using a Edding 800 permanent black marker to ensure no other stray light missed by the internal baffles could reach L3/L4. The system was then moved off the rotary table and onto the WFC trolley for the rest of the assembly due to height restrictions of the crane, which was used to move the elements. Tube A, along with it's baffles was added to the MSP before finally the L1 lens and cell were added. Tests were carried out at each stage of the final assembly to ensure everything was consistent with our previous measurements. 'Loctite 243' was applied to the bolts before insertion to ensure bolts were secure and to prevent loosening. Images of final assembly process can be found in the Appendix A.

3.18.1 Lens Centres

The final lens centre positions for each lens in the final set up are shown in the table below. All lenses were compared to the L3 OBP as this was our reference centre. All lenses fall within the decentring tolerances given for each lens.

Table 3.15: 4MOST Lens alignment results

Lens	Lens decentre (X,Y) (μm)	Tolerance (X,Y) (μm)	
L1	(-41.75, 15.13)	200	(section 3.14.2.3)
L2	(19.51, -16.04)	1000	(section 3.16.2)
L3	(6.79, 7.10)	100	(section 3.16.1)
L4	(22.27, -7.65)	200	(section 3.14.3)

3.18.2 Lens tilts

As previously described, each lens's bottom surface run-out was minimised when put into its cell, this left any lens wedge and any residual tilt to be expressed on the top surface measured as a run-out (Figure [3.76](#)). When the lenses were installed

Figure 3.75: Plot showing the WFC lens centres after installation in barrel relative to the target centre of the L3 OBP. Blue circle outlining a 60 μm radius encompassing all points.

into the full assembly, the top surface run-out was remeasured. Table 3.16 describes the initial lens surface variations in the cell pre-assembly after the lenses have been mated into their cells and the lens surface variations after the lenses have been put into the full WFC assembly. The difference between the two variations was calculated (this accounted for positional variation also) and the tilt angle found. All lens tilts lay well within the given tolerances.

Considering that each lens possesses a wedge, the overall tilt cannot solely be attributed to surface run-out; decentering also plays a role. Due to the inaccessibility of all lenses in the final assembly for direct measurement, the run-outs observed on the lens surfaces may result from a combination of decentering and tilt, making

them indistinguishable. Therefore, the values provided in Table 3.16 represent the maximum tilt derived from the surface run-out values measured in the lenses, all of which fall within the specified tolerances.

Table 3.16: Table showing the Initial lens surface variations in the cell pre-assembly after the lenses have been mated into their cells. WFC Lens tilts are calculated from the lens surface run-outs. All lens tilts lay within the given tolerances.

Lens	Initial lens surface variation (μm)	Lens surface in full assembly (μm)	Change in variation (μm)	Tilt angle (μrad)	Tilt Tolerance ($\pm \mu rad$)
L1	80	155	75	83.33	785
L2	489	647	78.46	83.33	945
L3	8	47	75	60	95
L4	67	68	19	29.23	142

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 3.76: Comparing the run-out of each lens within its cell against the run-out in the final assembly, alongside the difference between the two measurements for (a) L1, (b) L2, (c) L3, and (d) L4.

3.19 Lens to FSP Measurements

With the lens spacers thickness calculated and inserted, measurements were taken to work out the distance from lens (sag of L2 and L3, and back of L4) to the Focal Surface Plane (FSP) for L2, L3 and L4 (see Table 3.17) using the faro gauge arm as can be seen in an example in Figure 3.77.

Figure 3.77: Mapping and measuring the L2 lens surface with the Faro-arm, to find the centre of the sag so that a height position could be calculated from the lens sag to a reference surface.

Lens	Expected distance to MSP/Tube C interface (mm)	Measured distance to MSP/Tube C interface (mm)	\pm (mm)	Difference in measured to expected
L1 front	1501.337	1501.338	0.023	0.001
L2 sag	201.109	201.138	0.015	0.029
L3 sag	10.906	10.849	0.011	-0.0574
L4 back	174.306	174.348	0.015	0.042

Lens	Expected distance to FSP (mm)	Measured distance to FSP (mm)	\pm (mm)	Difference in measured to expected
L1 front	1925.457	1925.458	0.023	0.001
L2 sag	625.229	625.258	0.015	0.029
L3 sag	435.0264	434.969	0.011	-0.0574
L4 back	249.814	249.772	0.015	-0.042

Table 3.17: Table showing the expected distances from specified lens surface to the MSP/Tube C interface along with the FSP distances.

3.20 Summary

All lenses were successfully installed into the corrector, without damage and within the specified tolerances. Given the time constraints and deadlines in the ESO/AIP schedule for delivering the WFC, a comprehensive optical test was not carried out at UCL. While a full optical test would have been preferable, it was deemed impractical due to cost and time constraints. However, given the precision of our measurements, all of which fell within their tolerances, we were content with the positioning of the lenses. The corrector was successfully shipped to AIP in May 2022 with no movement of the optics during transportation and began integration with the AE-SOP fibre positioning unit. Further tests were carried out on the WFC while at AIP such as transmission tests and integration with various subsystems. At the time of writing (April 2024), the initial shipments of subsystems are beginning their journey to the telescope, marking a significant milestone in the 4MOST timeline, edging ever closer to first light. Notably, the Cable Wrap system, responsible for routing all fibres and service cables to the rotating Cassegrain focal surface, was dispatched ahead of other subsystems. Upon the WFC's transfer to Paranal, additional on-site integration and testing will be necessary to verify the optical integrity of the WFC, ensuring that the instrument remains aligned, thus fulfilling its scientific objectives. In future alignments, stricter environmental controls, improved stability of alignment fixtures, and comprehensive documentation of alignment procedures could further enhance precision and consistency, ensuring optimal performance of the WFC under a range of operating conditions.

3.21 Acknowledgements

We would like to acknowledge that sections of this chapter were submitted to SPIE Proceedings for the Astronomical Telescopes + Instrumentation 2022 conference held in Montreal, and subsequently published in JATIS which can be found in Cunningham et al. (2023). For the purpose of open access, the author has applied a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) licence to any Author Accepted Manuscript version arising.

Chapter 4

Assembly, Integration and Verification (AIV) at AIP and the telescope

Where the magic happens

A view of the integration hall at AIP.

(Photo taken by author)

4.1 Subsequent testing at AIP

Following the successful shipment of the WFC to the Leibniz Institute for Astrophysics, Potsdam (AIP), a series of comprehensive tests were conducted on the integrated system alongside the other subsystems. The AIP integration hall housed all of other subsystems, and testing was conducted prior to the final acceptance review by ESO, paving the way for final shipment to Chile. The Test Readiness Review (TRR) convened in Potsdam, bringing together ESO and the 4MOST Project Office. This critical review underscored a key milestone in the project's progression, symbolising the shift from system integration to systematic verification. Fundamentally, the TRR aimed to validate the preparedness of hardware and documentation before embarking on formal verification procedures. Seamless integration of the WFC with other subsystems remained a top priority, guaranteeing flawless operation upon the instrument's arrival at the telescope in Chile. This subsequent testing, verification, and integration of subsystems at AIP served as a practical trial run, enabling the execution of risk mitigation measures and safety protocols. Additionally, it provided valuable experience to the relevant personnel, ensuring that they are equipped to conduct accurate and efficient operations when working at the telescope. This chapter outlines those verification and testing procedures conducted at AIP related to the WFC (which the author was a part of though multiple visits to Germany from June 2022 to January 2023), as well as those scheduled for execution at the telescope.

4.1.1 Laser Pencil Beam Tool

After final assembly was complete at UCL, a Laser Pencil Beam Tool (LPBT) was used to test the optics of the WFC for pre and post delivery from UCL to AIP. This LBPT performs a verification and relative measurements of the WFC lenses during transportation and handling. It is not used for obtaining alignment status of the lenses however it is able to detect translation and tilts in the optical surfaces.

The laser was set up as shown in Figure 4.1 by the authro and Daniel Sablowski. An off-axis laser beam was sent through the system and the reflection of each lens surface was captured by a built-in camera which recorded the reflected im-

age positions. Laser light enters L1 first and proceeds through the assembly to L4. The beam is mounted on an X/Y translation stage so that it can be variably offset from the optical axis so as to separate the individual reflections from the optical surfaces. The WFC is placed in its upright position along the vertical axis to minimise distortions of the optics due to the gravity for all transportation measurements. The rotation of the ADC can be also checked via the LPBT as the returning spots from the specific two surfaces of the ADC will be displaced accordingly to the rotation, making this a comprehensive test of the overall system. An exaggerated schematic of the reflected positions can be seen in Figure 4.2 along with an example column plot from ZEMAX of where the positions should be using the as-built model of the lenses. If the lenses move during transportation, this would be revealed in the reflections and compared to both prior reflections and ZEMAX positioning. After testing both at UCL and AIP, the WFC was successfully delivered and all lenses were found to be within the measurement tolerances.

The test will be conducted once more upon the WFC's departure from AIP and its safe arrival at Paranal, allowing for a comparison to confirm any potential movement. It should be noted that it is not possible to distinguish between decentre and tilts.

A further test that will be performed with the LPBT is with the WFC on the Cassegrain Test Stand (CTS) where the WFC will be in its horizontal position. The team at the telescope plan to mount the LPB system onto the CTS for measuring deflection on the optical surfaces resulting from gravitational effects during WFC rotation. They will aim to verify alignment in both vertical and horizontal orientations of the WFC. Additionally, they will assess alignment at various rotation angles around the axis when the WFC is positioned horizontally.

Figure 4.1: (a) Drawing of the LPBT that was used to test the movement of the lenses pre and post delivery to AIP. The L1 lens is visible in the drawing while the LPBT rests on the permanent baffle. (b) Image of the LPBT during testing prior to shipping in the UCL lab.

Figure 4.2: (a) Schematic showing the LPBT reflections. The illumination system is significantly off-axis in this illustration to exaggerate the deviations of the reflected images. (b) Example column plot of the detector for the LPBT for an offset of 3 mm in ZEMAX showing the reflection of each surface for each of the lenses in the WFC. (*4MOST internal documentation*)

4.1.2 Transmission test for WFC

Due to time constraints and the necessity to conduct testing of the WFC alongside other subsystems in Germany, performing a thorough end-to-end test of the system at UCL was not possible. Consequently, a transmission test was conducted at AIP to address this limitation under the supervision of Daniel Sablowski.

The WFC/ADC optics are expected to have a transmission greater than 82% on average and greater than 79% at all wavelengths within the required range. The optics are designed to function over the continuous wavelength span of 390-885nm (with a goal of 370-950nm). To test this, a single beam transmission was directed through the WFC, spanning a range of wavelengths from 405nm up to 820nm, targeting the L1 lens at 7 equidistant positions across the lens with 0 being in the centre and measuring the throughput with a photo diode sensor (Figure 4.3). The wavelengths are bound to readily available laser sources and are selected such that an exchange can be done without any change of mechanics or electronics. The laser source is mounted in front of L1 and a photodiode is used to detect light fluctuations during the measurement via a beam splitter. Another photodiode is positioned after L4 to capture the throughput and to enable calibration and comparison of measurements between the two photodiodes. This facilitates the determination of input energy relative to transmission energy. The setup, consisting of the source with the beam splitter and photodiode, is mounted on a rod equipped with seven mounting positions. This rod is subsequently positioned at three different locations, in azimuthal steps of 60 degrees. This results in 21 positions, with transmission measurements taken at each position for five wavelengths, repeated three times, totaling 315 measurements. The measurements, depicted in Figure 4.3 and summarised in Table 4.1, indicate that the WFC meets the throughput requirements, with the overall average for each wavelength demonstrating compliance.

Interestingly a reduction in transmission was noted both at the centre and the edges of the lens across all wavelengths. The observed decrease of approximately 10% at the centre may be influenced by various factors.

One potential explanation for this discrepancy could be attributed to the typical

Figure 4.3: WFC Transmission test conducted at AIP by Daniel Sablowski. The figure displays the throughput for various wavelengths across the L1 lens at equidistant positions, indicating the average throughput for each wavelength over three measurements at each position.

angular dependence of a coating. Taking an average over a ray ensemble that covers the entire beam provides a more accurate representation of the actual behavior. Another possible explanation for the dip in the centre of the lens could stem from the coating process. This could potentially result in an accumulation of material at the centre of the lens, leading to non-uniformity in the coating or polishing.

The average transmission across the wavelength range stands at around ~ 80 - 89% . Accounting for a $\sim 2\%$ decrease at each surface due to reflections, our calculations suggest an overall transmission of approximately 88% across the WFC, which broadly corresponds with the observations.

Table 4.1: Table showing the average transmission % throughput for different wavelengths across the WFC.

Wavelength (nm)	Transmission Average %	Variation over field %
405	84	1.5
520	89	1
650	87	1
780	87	1
850	80	1

4.2 Integration with other subsystems

Given its pivotal role as a primary subsystem of 4MOST, the WFC underwent integration with several other subsystems at AIP. This comprehensive process included rigorous testing and rehearsal of procedures for execution at the telescope. The WFC MSP is specifically designed to accommodate other subsystems for testing, such as AESOP, the Acquisition & Guidance/Wavefront Sensing (A&G/WFS) unit, and the Focal Surface Test Tool (FSTT). During the integration phase (AIT), various tools were employed, including reference fiducial fibres and retro-reflectors (SMRs) for aligning the AESOP fibre positioners and instrument focal surface. A Focal Surface Alignment Stand (FSA) facilitated the alignment and testing of the WFC, A&G/WFS unit, AESOP, and FSTT in Potsdam before delivery to the telescope. The integration of key subsystems on the telescope is illustrated in Figure 4.4.

Preliminary Alignment Tasks at AIP:

- Aligning the WFS/A&G camera unit with the AIT WFC MSP on the Focal Surface Alignment stand (FSA).
- Aligning the Focal Surface Test Tools with the AIT WFC MSP on the FSA.
- Calibrating WFS/A&G cameras with FSTT.
- Integrating AESOP with the AIT WFC MSP on the FSA.
- Measuring Fiducial Fibre Tips using a traveling microscope referenced to laser trackers.

Figure 4.4: Cassegrain components of how the WFC will be integrated with other subsystems at the telescope. (4MOST internal documentation)

4.2.1 Centre of Gravity

Before being integrated with other subsystems, the centre of gravity (CoG) of the WFC had to be determined at AIP. This measurement ensures that the WFC is properly balanced and supported on the telescope to help prevent mechanical stress on the telescope's mount and structure, minimising risk of sagging, flexure, or deformation over time. There is also a safety element to measuring the CoG; an incorrectly balanced or unstable WFC poses safety risks during installation, maintenance, and operation. Knowing the centre of gravity helps technicians and astronomers plan these activities safely, minimising the likelihood of accidents or damage to any equipment.

Figure 4.5 shows the WFC in its horizontal position in the handling tool, and also being lifted by the WFC lifting tool, which was used to determine the balancing point. Throughout integration, the centre of gravity had to be determined when other subsystems were attached to the back of the WFC MSP such as the A&G unit.

4.2.2 AIT plate

Measurements of the SMR positions on the back surface of the MSP and AIT plate, conducted during the AIT phase at UCL by the author, play a critical role in aligning various integration systems. The SMRs serve as reference points to spatially align

Figure 4.5: (a) Image of the WFC mounted on the handling trolley that allows for vertical or horizontal orientation of the WFC by rotating the self-locking worm gear. (b) The WFC being lifted by the lifting hook to measure the centre of gravity of the WFC in the AIP integration Hall by the author and Michael Shröck.

the AIT plate with the FSTT, aiming to determine the focal surface accurately for shim manufacturing.

During the AIT phase at AIP, these measurements become indispensable. The AIT plate, acting as a surrogate for the actual MSP on the WFC, is integrated with the FSTT and the A&G/WFS. This integration process enables the determination of shim thicknesses, essential for ensuring the correct distance to the focal plane once the WFC and actual MSP are installed.

The SMR's are placed on the AIT plate and throughout the other subsystems, positioned strategically so that a laser tracker can access them throughout AIT measurements. From this, a 3D point cloud can be formed as illustrated in Figure 4.6. This SMR mapping allows for testing repeatability and is accurate to around $10\mu\text{m}$.

Figure 4.6: (a) Point cloud of formed using the SMR's and laser tracker measurements of the MSP plate. (b) Photo of the laser tracker taking measurements of the IWST and SMR's on the AIT plate while integrated with the FSTT.

4.2.3 Cassegrain Test Stand

The Cassegrain Test Stand (CTS), which was built at AIP, facilitates integration by providing the instrument interface flange, hand-cranked instrument rotation, and the CaCW mounting interface. This replica test stand is at the same height above the floor as the VISTA structure and allows horizontal integration of all components at the instrument flange and the telescope's back end. Figure 4.7 and 4.8 demonstrate the WFC being lifted and mated with the CTS to check both the mating surfaces if any shims are needed and to check the rotation of the WFC while on the CTS, mimicking the telescope rotator.

4.2.4 Focal Surface Test Tool

The FSTT subsystem (Figure 4.9), which is attached to the MSP/AIT plate, is to be used in place of the AESOP fibre positioner to characterise and calibrate the technical cameras which perform guiding and wavefront sensing. Additional commissioning responsibilities are delegated to the FSTT subsystem, including the cre-

Figure 4.7: WFC being lifted into the Cassegrain Test Stand for the first time.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.8: (a) The WFC fully mounted on the CTS. (b) The WFC sitting on the CTS V-Blocks for alignment.

ation of calibration look-up tables for the telescope. The FSTT incorporates two Shack-Hartmann wavefront sensors (known as the Imaging and Wavefront Sensing Tool (IWST)), with one positioned on-axis and the other off-axis. Each wavefront sensor (WFS) is accompanied by an imaging detector connected via a beam-splitter. The on-axis sensor unit of the IWST has a focus stage and the off-axis unit a fo-

Figure 4.9: (a) FSTT with AIT plate and IWST attached. (b) Birds eye view of the IWST on-axis and off-axis WFS.

cus and radial stage. Both stages can be rotated by $\pm 180^\circ$ by a rotation stage the whole IWST is mounted to. By precisely controlling the positions of the two wavefront sensors to mimic the AESOP fibres, it becomes feasible to conduct a thorough assessment of 4MOST's imaging capabilities, in a way that AESOP alone cannot offer.

Figure 4.10: Image showing the AIT plate with the Star-Telescope-Simulator (STS) attached.

4.3 Testing at the Telescope

4.3.1 Installation at the Telescope

After the instrument is transported, the necessary subsystems will be reassembled in the Paranal integration hall. These subsystems will then be integrated with the telescope according to a detailed installation plan, which includes various verification steps. The first task that will be performed upon arrival of the WFC to the telescope will be the LPBT, to assess and monitor any movement during transportation. Another crucial component in this process is the FSTT as outline previously, with its primary objective to facilitate the recommissioning of the telescope equipped with the new WFC. To achieve this, the FSTT, along with its imager and wavefront sensor combination, are installed on a rotation and linear (X/Y) stage, allowing for the analysis of image performance across the focal surface. Additionally, the FSTT includes a test plate for measuring the alignment of the Calibration System illumination units on the M2 spider and the back-illuminated plate with small holes used to calibrate the cameras of the Metrology System (de Jong et al., 2022). The inte-

gration techniques employed at the telescope are familiar and have been practiced at AIP using the AIT plate. This familiarity streamlines the engineers' tasks, as they anticipate what to expect during telescope integration.

The WFC will be aligned and put in position using the V-blocks on the Cassegrain rotator and the 'flat faces' located on the MSP, as detailed in Chapter 3. Should testing reveal any misalignment of the WFC with the Cassegrain rotator axis at the telescope, whether due to decentration, tilting, or incorrect axial positioning, adjustments can be made by altering the thickness of shim pieces. These shims will be inserted to fine-tune the spacing between the WFC and the V-block.

The shim thickness for the z position at VISTA will be optimised by initially mounting with a nominal shim thickness of 25mm (to be confirmed). The resulting initial system spacing will be measured using the FSTT IWST across various combinations of M2 piston and back focal length. The optimal shim thickness, aimed at minimising the difference between the nominal spherical aberration residual and the measured spherical aberration, will be calculated based on these measurements, and the final shim will be manufactured accordingly.

The primary alignment tasks at VISTA include:

- Aligning the WFC/ADC to the telescope at the MSP interface (optical axis being z , radial (x/y) and tip/tilt (R_x/R_y)).
- Verifying image quality using the FSTT.
- Cross-checking WFC aberration measurements.
- Optimising the thickness of instrument flange shims to minimise telescope spherical aberration resulting from incorrect focus accommodations between mirrors M1 and M2. These accommodations are influenced by incorrect WFC and WFS axial positions relative to each other and to the telescope primary mirror.
- If necessary, adjusting the radial and tip/tilt alignment of the WFC/ADC.
- Upon achieving acceptable FSTT results, removing and installing AESOP.

- Aligning AESOP to acquire a star with the guide fibre bundle.
- Calibrating fibre positions through raster scans to optimise throughput.

4.3.2 Alignment with AESOP

The AESOP fibre positioner will be installed at AIP on the FSA tool and the CTS, prior to shipping to the telescope. It will then be uninstalled and reinstalled on the telescope using the same procedure and interfaces. In the first stage a laser tracker installation at AIP on the FSA is followed by a precise measurement of fiducial fibre tips with a fiducialised alignment telescope on a X/Y stage, the same as used for the FSTT. Following the precise measurement of fiducial fibre tips to MSP with the X/Y stage, this state of alignment is recorded by measuring reference SMRs mounted on the rear of AESOP directly with respect to the MSP. On the telescope it is this measurement, reference SMRs to the MSP made with a laser tracker that shall establish the final alignment with respect to the telescope. On the telescope a set of temporary SMRs are to be installed on the telescope structure and measured with respect to the AIT WFC MSP reference. These temporary SMRs will be measured with respect to the SMRs located on the rear of AESOP to guide the alignment to AIT MSP. At the telescope this alignment will be repeated to recover the recorded relative positions as those carried out at AIP, and using the WFS and guide fibres, alignment will be verified. The alignment of the AESOP fibre tips to the telescope focal surface relies on a metrology chain, summarised as follows:

Completed Tasks at AAO:

- Internal assembly/alignment of individual fibres and fibre modules in AESOP.
- Metrology of fiducial fibre tips to four characterised reference planes on AESOP.
- Laser Tracker Metrology of Reference SMRs (front and rear side) to the reference planes.

Tasks at AIP:

- Laser tracker installation/alignment of AESOP to AIT WFC MSP using SMR fiducials.
- Direct measurement of fiducial fibre tips with the travelling microscope used in the FSTT alignment.
- Recording of rear Laser Tracker fiducials with respect to MSP fiducials following travelling microscope measurement of fiducial fibre tips.

Tasks at Paranal:

- Identical Laser Tracker Installation/alignment of AESOP to AIT WFC MSP using SMR fiducials.

4.4 Schedule

At the time of writing the Cable Wrap has been shipped to Chile while activities for the WFC subsystem are finishing, with last software tests pending. After these tests are complete, the WFC will be ready to make its voyage to the Atacama desert. A container with the WFC tools (Handling Trolley, Lifting Tool etc)) will be packed and sent to the telescope ahead of the WFC, which is transported via airfreight, with the goal to have the WFC tools in Paranal when the WFC is shipped.

Finally the team expects shipment of all subsystems to be completed by the end of 2024, with First light scheduled for early 2025.

Chapter 5

C III] λ 1909 emission as an alternative to Ly α in the reionisation era

Where did the time go?

13.8 Billion years(-ish). From the Big Bang through to present day.

The work described in this chapter was published in (Cunningham et al., 2024) Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society "C III] λ 1909 emission as an alternative to Ly α in the reionisation era: the dependence of C III] and Ly α at $3 < z < 4$ from the VANDELS survey"

5.1 Overview

The velocity offset of Ly α emission relative to a galaxy's systemic redshift can provide a valuable tracer of conditions that permit Ly α photons to escape the galaxy, potentially offering insights into the escape of hydrogen-ionising Lyman continuum photons. However, at high redshifts ($z \geq 6$), Ly α emissions are often strongly attenuated by the neutral intergalactic medium. To address this, we explore the potential of C III] emission, specifically the $\lambda\lambda$ 1907, 1909 doublet, as a proxy for estimating the Ly α velocity offset ($\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$), given that C III] is generally the brightest ultraviolet (UV) emission line following Ly α .

Our analysis draws from 52 star-forming galaxies with robust C III] detections in the VANDELS survey, selected as analogues for galaxies in the reionisation era. The sample spans a UV magnitude range of $-18.5 < M_{\text{UV}} < -22.0$ and has an average equivalent width (EW) of C III] of 5.3 \AA . We observe a slight trend of increasing EW(C III]) with rising EW(Ly α), though the equivalent width of C III] spans a broad range from ~ 1 to 13 \AA , particularly at low EW(Ly α) values ($< 10 \text{ \AA}$).

Utilising the C III] peak as a reference for systemic redshift, we calculate $\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$ and observe the established trend of $\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$ decreasing with increasing EW(Ly α). Notably, an anti-correlation emerges between $\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$ and EW(C III]), alongside a dependency on UV absolute magnitude. Our findings suggest that $\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$ is more sensitive to EW(C III]) than to M_{UV} , though the latter still exerts a measurable influence. Furthermore, UV-bright galaxies with Ly α emission exhibit smaller values of $\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$ for a fixed EW(C III]), implying that these galaxies may experience more bursty star formation than their UV-fainter counterparts, akin to extremely UV-bright galaxies identified at $z > 10$.

5.2 Introduction

In the preceding chapters, we delved into the intricate opto-mechanical processes of constructing the 4MOST Wide Field Corrector and touched on the spectroscopic capabilities that 4MOST will deliver throughout its ambitious science goals. 4MOST's wide field-of-view positions it as a powerhouse of spectroscopic follow-up in the southern hemisphere, seamlessly complementing and enriching both space-based and ground-based observatories. With its unparalleled combination of high resolution and expansive coverage, 4MOST will cast its gaze across a substantial portion of the southern skies during its initial years of operation emerging as an indispensable tool for spectroscopic follow-up investigations. Through the AGN survey on 4MOST (see Section 2.2), with over ~ 1.5 million quasar targets, this survey aims to probe the universe up to a redshift of 6.

Despite the unparalleled promise, 4MOST awaits its imminent installation at the VISTA telescope. It is within this context, that we explore the use of another multi-object spectroscopic instrument to investigate the early Universe at high redshifts ($3 < z < 4$), with a specific focus on the Epoch of Reionisation (EoR). To accomplish this, we utilise the VIMOS and the VANDELS Survey. VIMOS, despite its lower resolution, offers significant advantages in deep imaging compared to 4MOST. Further details on VIMOS and the VANDELS survey will be provided in sections 5.4.1 and 5.4.2.

5.3 The Epoch of Reionisation: a brief overview

With the advent of the *James Webb Space Telescope (JWST)*, we can now conduct a detailed exploration of the largely uncharted epoch in the Universe's history known as the Epoch of Reionisation (EoR). This era began approximately 300 million years after the Big Bang, as the first stars and galaxies emerged (Figure 5.1). Through *JWST*'s near-infrared imaging (NIRCam) and spectroscopy (NIRSpec), **along with mid-infrared observations from MIRI**, we can now observe galaxies as far back as redshift ~ 14 , representing some of the **farthest** spectroscopically confirmed sources currently known (Carniani et al., 2024). **Additionally, the Mid-**

Infrared Instrument (MIRI) onboard JWST has allowed astronomers to detect H-alpha emission from the Epoch of Reionisation.

During the EoR, ionisation of the intergalactic medium (IGM) occurred as photons with energies exceeding 13.6 eV interacted with neutral hydrogen, leading to electron stripping and the thermalisation of excess energy. This process effectively marked the end of the cosmic dark ages. It is widely accepted that ultraviolet (UV) radiation from early luminous sources ionised the surrounding medium, a process thought to have been completed by $z \sim 5.5 - 6$ (Becker et al., 2013; Bosman et al., 2022; Fan et al., 2006; McGreer et al., 2015; Salvador-Solé et al., 2017). However, the exact sources driving reionisation, as well as their relative contributions to the ionising photon budget, remain uncertain and have historically been debated.

Current theories propose several primary candidates for early ionising radiation:

Population III Stars: The first generation of stars, known as Population III stars (Pop III), are theorised to have been massive (up to hundreds of solar masses) and short-lived, producing intense UV radiation due to their high temperatures and low metallicity. Although Pop III stars were likely influential, their impact on reionisation might have been limited by their low number density and short lifespan. JWST observations continue to search for potential indirect signatures of Pop III stars (Curti et al., 2023; Vanzella et al., 2023 and references therein).

Star-forming Galaxies: Early galaxies with high star-formation rates are considered major contributors to the reionising UV background. Recent JWST observations reveal that even galaxies with relatively modest UV magnitudes at high redshifts (e.g., $z \sim 10 - 12$) have potentially significant ionising capabilities. These galaxies may have undergone bursty star formation episodes, which could have amplified their ionising photon output. The role of these galaxies has been reinforced by JWST's detections of numerous high-redshift candidates, suggesting that an abundance of low-mass, UV-faint galaxies may have provided a significant portion of the ionising photons needed for reionisation (Endsley et al., 2023) (*Discussed further in section 5.3.2*).

Figure 5.1: Diagram depicting the timeline of the Universe’s evolution. Approximately 400,000 years after the Big Bang, the Universe transitions into a neutral state, followed by the onset of hydrogen ionisation by the first generation of stars’ light. Over several hundred million years, the gas within the Universe becomes fully ionised. (Credit: NAOJ)

Quasars and Active Galactic Nuclei (AGN): Quasars and AGN, driven by supermassive black holes, are capable of producing substantial amounts of ionising radiation. Although they are typically considered too sparse at high redshifts to account for most of the ionising photons necessary for reionisation, recent deep-field imaging from JWST has identified a greater number of high-redshift AGN candidates than initially expected, (Harikane et al., 2023). Nevertheless, star-forming galaxies remain far more abundant and coupled with measurements indicating low Lyman continuum (LyC) escape fractions from AGNs, this reinforces the view that quasars likely had a more limited impact on early reionisation compared to star-forming galaxies Dayal et al., 2020; Maiolino et al., 2023 and references therein.

Exotic Sources: Some theories suggest exotic sources, such as dark-matter annihilation or decaying particles, could have contributed to early ionisation. However, these remain speculative, and there is currently no direct evidence from JWST or other telescopes to support their involvement.

In summary, while the primary candidates for reionisation are early star-forming galaxies, Pop III stars, and AGN, JWST observations are actively reshaping our understanding by confirming the abundance and properties of galaxies at $z > 6$.

5.3.1 The Reionisation Equation

As noted earlier, star-forming galaxies (SFGs) are, if not the, key contributor of ionising photons, and current AGN luminosity functions suggest there are too few AGN to reionise the early universe (Hopkins et al., 2008; Matsuoka et al., 2023; Onoue et al., 2017). However, recent JWST findings have begun to challenge this view by uncovering more high-redshift AGN candidates than previously anticipated (Harikane et al., 2023). That being said, the sparse distribution of these quasars at high redshifts, coupled with the absence of convincing evidence for alternative ionising sources, positions SFGs as the most compelling and physically well motivated sources of ionising photons. If SFGs did in fact dominate the reionisation process, then the ionisation rate can be calculated using the cosmic reionisation equation (B. Robertson et al., 2015):

$$n_{ion} = f_{esc} \cdot \xi_{ion} \cdot \rho, \quad (5.1)$$

where n_{ion} is the ionising photon production rate, f_{esc} is the escape fraction of photons into the IGM, ξ_{ion} is the rate of production of ionising photons for a stellar population, and ρ is the density of luminous objects. All three parameters influence the rate at which the IGM is ionised. If star forming galaxies are expected to be a driving force in ionising, to effectively utilise the equation and delve into the intricacies of star formation, we rely on a comprehensive understanding of the parameters involved, which necessitates the ability to identify and study galaxy spectra.

It's essential to acknowledge that measuring each component of the reionisation equation is non trivial.

f_{esc} - The escape fraction of ionising radiation from galaxies plays a critical role in the evolution of gas in galaxies, and the heating and ionisation history of the IGM and Inter-Stellar Medium (ISM) (Benson et al., 2013). Observational constraints suggest that $f_{esc} \sim 0.1 - 0.2$ ($z \sim 3$) (Bouwens et al., 2015; B. Robertson et al., 2015), if stars reionised the Universe. The low f_{esc} of ionising photons from galaxies is largely due to absorption by the hydrogen-rich ISM. Estimating f_{esc} is challenging, as the ISM's clumpy structure and line-of-sight effects can obscure how photons propagate. At redshifts $z < 4$, some ionising radiation can be observed

just below the Lyman limit of 912\AA (Lyman continuum) as the photons are allowed to propagate undisturbed. However, beyond this redshift, nearly all ionising photons are absorbed by extensive clouds of atomic hydrogen in the IGM, making detection above $z = 4$ extremely difficult.

ξ_{ion} - The parameter ξ_{ion} can be described as the intrinsic production rate of ionising photons per unit volume per unit time. Ionising photon emission of wavelength 912\AA corresponds to an ionisation energy of 13.6eV . A photon emitted with wavelength shorter than this will be completely absorbed by hydrogen gas both in a galaxy and along the line of sight to us. As it has been suggested that SFG's are the dominant sources of ionising photons due to their large number density, for them to be the lead candidates, these galaxies must contain very hot, young stars, to be able to produce enough ionisation power. To be able to work out this elusive parameter, ξ_{ion} can be estimated using two methods, (i) photometrically using Spectral Energy Distribution fitting (SED) and (ii) spectroscopically using the presence of diagnostic lines. In this work I will be focusing on diagnostic line emission.

ρ - This parameter can be described as the density of luminous objects or the integral of the luminosity function of the given sources (i.e SFG's). In order to accurately assess this parameter, a fundamental understanding of the Luminosity function is imperative. This function represents the distribution of luminosities among objects within a given sample. However, measuring luminosity poses significant challenges, as it necessitates precise distance measurements (allows astronomers to derive the true luminosity by correcting for the effects of distance on the observed flux) and the integration of each object's spectrum across all frequencies to compute the total or bolometric luminosity. As this function is generally measured over a given band of wavelength or frequencies, constraints based on minimum detectable fluxes are imposed. One strategy to circumvent limitations posed by flux-limited samples involves assuming a homogeneous distribution of sources, which is presumed to hold true when averaged over vast scales.

5.3.2 Constraining Cosmic Reionisation

The duration of the EoR can be constrained by, amongst other probes, measures of the scattering and polarisation of the cosmic microwave background (CMB) (Bennett et al., 2013; Choudhury et al., 2021; Haiman et al., 1999; Planck Collaboration et al., 2016; Zahn et al., 2012), the opacity of hydrogen absorption in the spectra of distant quasars (Bosman et al., 2022; Erb et al., 2010; Garaldi et al., 2019; Rigby et al., 2015; Stark et al., 2014; Weisz et al., 2017), and the visibility or otherwise of Lyman- α ($\text{Ly}\alpha$) emission in star-forming galaxies (SFGs) since this is resonantly scattered by neutral gas, along with the 21cm hydrogen signal (Jones et al., 2023; Pentericci et al., 2011; Pritchard et al., 2012; Trapp et al., 2023). Constraining the sources responsible for reionisation requires knowing their abundances and ionising capabilities.

With *JWST*, at least constraining the average production rate of ionising photons in galaxies at $z > 6$ is now within reach (Cameron et al., 2023; Curti et al., 2023; Katz et al., 2023; Saxena et al., 2024; Tang et al., 2023). However, as the neutral fraction of the IGM increases, it becomes impractical to directly observe the escaping ionising photons from galaxies beyond $z \simeq 4$ (e.g. Inoue et al., 2014). Direct measures of the leakage of Lyman continuum (LyC) photons is only possible in lower redshift analogues, where such observations can be linked to other observables (e.g. Fletcher et al., 2019; Flury et al., 2022; Izotov et al., 2021; Pahl et al., 2023; Saxena et al., 2022). There has been a great effort to use spectroscopy to further investigate nearby galaxies that could be used as an analog for primitive galaxies in the early Universe (Erb et al., 2010; Stark et al., 2014, 2015). It has been suggested that large numbers of low mass galaxies are likely to have been required to reionise the universe (Kuhlen et al., 2012; Robertson et al., 2013). As these young, low mass galaxies with low metallicity are comparable to the typical unevolved galaxy at high redshifts ($z > 6$), comprehensive studies of similar objects at lower redshifts ($z < 6$) have the potential to unlock an abundance of information about our early Universe. This has the potential to unravel details about the nature of the first luminous stars (Pop III) and their evolution, providing an insight to the

census of star formation activity in what is thought to be the core of the reionisation era. (Erb et al., 2010; Stark et al., 2017). A further tool in understanding the physics of how LyC photons may escape is via high-resolution cosmological hydrodynamical simulations (e.g. Choustikov et al., 2023; Maji et al., 2022).

5.3.3 The Ly α Problem

Ly α emission, 1215.7Å produced by hydrogen atoms when electrons transition from the second to the first energy level, has historically been used to explore how ionising radiation can escape, since both Ly α and LyC photons rely on relatively dust-free environments and pre-ionised regions to escape (Hayes et al., 2023; Izotov et al., 2021; Maji et al., 2022; Naidu et al., 2022; Verhamme et al., 2017). Both types of photons depend on relatively dust-free regions to avoid absorption, as dust can scatter or absorb these photons and prevent them from traveling through the ISM and IGM. However, a unique characteristic of Ly α is its high susceptibility to absorption by neutral hydrogen, which often causes Ly α photons to undergo multiple scatterings before finally escaping a galaxy. This scattering process, influenced by interactions with both the ISM and CGM, results in frequency shifts and spatial diffusion, which significantly alters the line's profile and can introduce asymmetrical line shapes, such as double peaks or redshifted emissions.

The velocity offset of Ly α with respect to the systemic velocity determined from other nebular lines in particular can trace the geometry of the distribution of neutral gas in an H II region, with Ly α peaking close to the systemic velocity probing relatively low column densities that facilitate both the escape of Ly α as well as LyC photons from galaxies (Dijkstra et al., 2006; Dijkstra, 2014; Verhamme et al., 2015, 2017). The Ly α velocity offset with respect to other nebular lines was initially investigated by Adelberger et al. (2003), and studies such as Haiman (2002) and Mesinger et al. (2015) found that velocity offsets in the Ly α line caused by the ISM and circum-galactic medium (CGM) heavily influence the transmission of Ly α through the IGM. Overall, Ly α sensitivity to environmental factors within and around galaxies, combined with its resonance and redshifted observability, makes it an indispensable tool for studying galaxy formation, evolution, and the cosmic

reionisation epoch.

The abundance of neutral hydrogen surrounding galaxies during the epoch of reionisation hinders the detection of Ly α emission originating from the earliest epochs. Surprisingly however, with *JWST*, unexpected Ly α detections have emerged from galaxies situated deep within the epoch of reionisation, $z \sim 7-11$ (Bunker et al., 2023; Hashimoto et al., 2018; Zitrin et al., 2015). A recent examination comparing observations from the *JWST* with simulations offers a hypothesis for the detection of Ly α at redshifts of $z > 7$, attributing it to processes instigated by interacting galaxies (Witten et al., 2024). Fundamentally, however, the increasing neutrality of the IGM renders Ly α emission an unreliable tool in the EoR (e.g. Behrens et al., 2013; Dijkstra et al., 2006; Hayes et al., 2010; Inoue et al., 2014; Santos, 2004) and we must rely on other emission lines to infer the leakage of LyC photons. Rest-frame ultraviolet spectroscopy has revealed strong emission lines of the semi-forbidden C III] $\lambda\lambda$ 1907, 1909 doublet (referred to as C III] hereafter, see next section) over $z \sim 2 - 7$ (Erb et al., 2010; Shapley et al., 2003; Stark et al., 2014, 2015) and various authors have discussed whether studies of C III] emission may be a valuable probe as a substitute for Ly α (Ding et al., 2017; Stark et al., 2014, 2015, 2017). These observations however pre-date the launch of the *JWST*. With the success of *JWST* and the plethora of results delving deeper into the reionisation era with spectroscopy, we are already seeing how *JWST* is transforming identification of these emission lines (e.g Bunker et al., 2023; Saxena et al., 2023; Tang et al., 2023)

The drop seen in the Ly α fraction beyond $z > 6$ is strong evidence for reionisation (Mason et al., 2018; Pentericci et al., 2011); however, other studies have shown that the drop in the Ly α detected can be attributed to alternative mechanisms. One explanation that has been proposed to potentially elucidate the decline in Ly α emission during this period is the presence of spatial offsets within the Ly α line relative to the UV continuum; however, this aspect remains relatively unexplored in current research endeavours. This is especially relevant because most measurements of the Ly α fraction employ slit spectroscopy, currently the most efficient technique for

exploring the $z > 6$ universe spectroscopically. Radiative transfer of Ly α through the ISM and CGM is known to strongly influence both the spectral profile and spatial distribution of the line. Hoag et al. (2019) carried out a spatial offset survey within the VANDELS dataset that pointed towards slit losses caused by spatial offsets in the Ly α that may be responsible for some of the drop in Ly α fraction over the EoR. Although this finding offers a plausible explanation for a portion of the Ly α depletion, further exploration into the nature of these offsets is required.

5.3.3.1 Carbon III]

Line diagnostics are a major tool in understanding the inner workings of a galaxy. Diverse galaxy populations and their inherent properties give rise to unique intrinsic Spectral Energy Distributions (SEDs). By employing line ratio diagnostics derived from these SEDs, as indicated by the transitions outlined in Figure 5.2 (e.g. [O III]/[O II], [O III]/[N II], C III]/[He II]), one can effectively infer the specific properties characterising these galaxies. Carbon, being the fourth most abundant element in the universe, assumes a crucial role within galaxies, offering valuable constraints on processes and insights into the timescales of structure formation. Diagnostic lines such as C III] , C IV, and He II (Figure 5.2), along with their respective ratios, provide even deeper insights into the nature of the radiation field. The high ionisation energy needed to produce these transition lines, makes them very good candidates for tracing young, hot SFG's in the early universe. By examining the line ratios of different emission lines such as C III] / He II versus C III] / O III], one can infer both the nature of the object (whether it is a SFG or an AGN) and establish constraints (either upper or lower limits) on its ionising potency (Feltre et al., 2016).

Doubly-ionised Carbon (C III]) is a key UV nebular lines that encodes precious information on the physical conditions of the ionised gas in galaxies (Llerena et al., 2021). The semi forbidden C III] $\lambda\lambda$ 1907, 1909 doublet, that is typically the brightest UV metal line in SFG's at intermediate redshifts ($z \sim 3$), requires an ionisation energy of 24.38eV to doubly ionise Carbon (see Figure 5.2) (Shapley et al., 2003). Here, "semi-forbidden" refers to a type of atomic transition that is less likely to occur than an allowed transition but more probable than a fully forbidden transi-

Figure 5.2: Ionising radiation can be thermally produced from hot stars or non-thermal from AGN. UV metal lines of high ionisation potential probe the nature of the radiation field. This figure shows example SED's expressed in units of luminosity per frequency at the Lyman limit) for the incident ionising radiation within both AGN and SF models. The shaded grey region represents the range of AGN ionising spectra with power-law indices between $\alpha = -2.0$ (bottom edge) and -1.2 (top edge). Additionally, the blue and orange lines depict the ionising spectra of stellar populations. Vertical lines denote the ionising energies corresponding to different species of ions. (*Reproduced from Feltre et al., 2016.*)

tion. Semi-forbidden transitions, also known as intercombination lines, have a low probability due to the involvement of a change in the electron spin state or other quantum properties, making them rare under typical conditions. However, they can occur in low-density environments, like the ionised gas in galaxies, where collisions that typically prevent these transitions are minimal. In comparison to other lines depicted, C III] possesses relatively low energy, nearing the Ly α transition. Hence, correlations between these two lines are anticipated, particularly when Ly α remains unattenuated by the IGM.

Several studies have previously explored correlations between the equivalent widths (EW) of Ly α and C III] (Cullen et al., 2020; Ding et al., 2017; Erb et al., 2010; Hutchison et al., 2019; Le Fèvre et al., 2019; Llerena et al., 2021; Marchi et al., 2019; Ravindranath et al., 2020; Rigby et al., 2015; Schaerer et al., 2018; Shapley et al., 2003; Stark et al., 2014, 2015) in low redshift SFGs where Ly α is

unattenuated by the neutral IGM. Marchi et al. (2019) found a strong correlation between the two lines, but noted that their sample may be biased as the sample was selected to have both Ly α and C III] emission, questioning whether this relation could change if the entire population of galaxies with C III] emission were considered. The basic idea behind any possible correlation is that the conditions which support the efficient production and escape of Ly α radiation (i.e. low dust content, low metallicity, partial coverage of neutral hydrogen) may be similar to those required for the production of collisionally-excited emission lines such as C III]. However, Rigby et al. (2015) pointed out that the correlation is driven primarily by the strongest emitters of Ly α and C III] ($EW(\text{Ly}\alpha) \sim 50\text{\AA}$ & $EW(\text{C III])} \sim 5\text{\AA}$), whereas for weaker emitters there is no convincing correlation. Moreover, at low metallicities ($Z = 0.1 - 0.2Z_{\odot}$), the correlation may weaken further as predicted by Nakajima et al., 2018b.

Regardless, any correlation between Ly α and C III] may offer the prospect of using C III] emission from galaxies at $z > 6$, now feasible with *JWST*, to constrain the Ly α properties and therefore the nature of the ionising sources and their environment. Using spectroscopic data from the VANDELS survey for SFGs in the redshift range $z \sim 3 - 4$ where both Ly α and C III] are visible, we examine in further detail the utility of C III] as a proxy for Ly α .

The work explored in this chapter complements earlier studies by Marchi et al. (2019) and Llerena et al. (2021) that have used VANDELS data to investigate these emission lines. Llerena et al. (2021) explored the global properties of C III] derived from stacked spectra within the VANDELS dataset. The unique aspect of this work is the emphasis on a larger sample of individual emitters compared to Llerena et al. (2021) and, crucially, the offset between C III] and Ly α and its connection with Lyman continuum leakage. Marchi et al. (2019) studied C III] and Ly α including offsets; however, a key difference in this work is that we do not pre-select for Ly α .

The layout of this chapter is as follows: In Section 5.4 we describe the VIMOS instrument and the VANDELS data used in this work and the various line measurement methods employed. We present the main results based on this spectroscopic

data in Section 5.5. Finally, we summarise the findings of this work in Section 5.6 and place the results into context with those in the literature and discuss the C III] and Ly α relationship along with the implications of the Ly α offsets in the reionisation era.

Throughout the chapter, we assume the following cosmology: $\Omega_m = 0.3$, $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$, $H_0 = 70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$. We use the notation of a positive EW to imply emission, and all logarithms are in base 10 unless otherwise specified.

5.4 Data and measurements

5.4.1 VIMOS

The spectra analysed in this study originate exclusively from the VANDELS survey, a comprehensive spectroscopic survey conducted within the CANDELS fields, using the Visible Multi-Object Spectrograph (VIMOS) on ESO's Very Large Telescope (VLT) (Le Fèvre et al., 2003). VIMOS is a wide-field imager and multi-object spectrograph located at ESO's VLT facility in Chile on the Nasmyth focus B of the Melipal VLT-UT3. This sophisticated instrument, designed for conducting deep astronomical surveys, is capable of capturing visible images and spectra from as many as 1,000 galaxies. Functioning across three distinct observation modes—direct imaging, multi-slit spectroscopy, and integral field spectroscopy—the primary aim of the instrument is to explore the early universe through extensive redshift surveys, exemplified by the VIMOS-VLT Deep Survey (Le Fèvre et al., 2003; Nakajima et al., 2018b).

5.4.2 VANDELS survey

The VANDELS survey (McLure et al., 2018; Pentericci et al., 2018) covers a total area of 0.2 deg^2 centred on the CANDELS UDS (*UKIDSS* Ultra Deep Survey, RA=2:18, Dec=-5:10) and CDFS (*Chandra* Deep Field South, RA=3:32, Dec=-27:48) (see Figure 5.3). It secured high signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) spectra at optical wavelengths ($0.48 < \lambda < 1.0 \mu\text{m}$) for 2100 galaxies in the redshift interval $1.0 \leq z \leq 7.0$ (Garilli et al., 2021). Around 85% of the galaxies targeted by VANDELS are at $z \sim 3$. The unique aspect of the VANDELS survey is that each source has a signif-

icant exposure time, ranging from 20hrs to a maximum of 80hrs (Pentericci et al., 2018). Full details and description of the survey and target selection can be found in McLure et al., 2018. The CANDELS fields utilised in this study boast exceptionally deep ground-based data, complemented by observations from HST, Spitzer, and X-ray sources. This comprehensive dataset not only facilitates precise SED fitting for measuring crucial galaxy properties such as stellar mass, star formation rates, and ages, but also aids in distinguishing between SFGs and AGN. Some of the most robust C III] emitters discussed later in this text may fall into the later categories. The wealth of ancillary data available was a driving force behind the decision to utilise the VANDELS dataset.

5.4.3 C III] and Ly α emitter selection and line measurement

In this work, we focus on spectroscopically confirmed star-forming galaxies from VANDELS data release 4 (DR4) across both UDS and CDFS fields (Garilli et al., 2021) in the redshift range of $3 \leq z \leq 4$, only selecting those galaxies that have a redshift probability of being 95% correct (a redshift reliability flag of 3 or 4, see Pentericci et al. 2018 for more details). This redshift range ensures that both the C III] and Ly α emission lines lie within the spectral range. These initial selection criteria resulted in a sample of 773 objects.

To identify C III] and Ly α emission from this parent sample, both the 1D and 2D spectra were visually inspected by the author using the PANDORA software ¹. Based on the robustness of the C III] emission from visual inspection, the sample was split into three different groups based on the ‘confidence level’ (CL hereafter). CL 3 was assigned to those sources with clear C III] emission in both their 1D and 2D spectra, unaffected by sky features or residual noise. Spectra that showed clear C III] emission in either 1D or 2D spectra (but not both) were assigned a CL of 2, whereas possible line detections likely contaminated by residual noise/sky features were assigned a CL of 1. CL ratings were used for initial ratings, this allowed the author to quickly go through the data visually. While S/N provides a straightforward measure of signal quality, it doesn’t necessarily account for underlying distri-

¹<https://www.iasf-milano.inaf.it/software/>

Figure 5.3: VANDELS final data release pointings for both the *Left*: CDFS, and *Right*: UDS. Each section is displayed twice for clarity, illustrating the arrangement of the four VIMOS pointings with colored squares. The greyscale image showcases HST H-band imaging from the CANDELS survey in central regions, complemented by ground-based H-band imaging from UKIDSS UDS and VISTA VIDEO in the broader area. (*Reproduced from Garilli et al., 2021.*)

butional assumptions or detection thresholds as thoroughly as a CL-based approach might. In complex spectral data, line profiles can vary significantly depending on astrophysical conditions, such as gas density or temperature, and the noise is often non-Gaussian. A CL-based rating considers this variability more robustly than S/N alone, which assumes that high values mean a line is detected regardless of noise characteristics. A S/N ratio was introduced later for the CL3 sample.

Out of an initial parent sample of 773 galaxies, C III] emission (CL 1-3) was identified in 280 galaxies, with 139 galaxies assigned the highest confidence level of CL3. Figure 5.4 displays example spectra for all 3 confidence level ratings as how the 2D spectra data was initially inspected in PANDORA to make a judgment on whether or not the emission line was real. Figures 5.5 and 5.6 showcase distinct C III] and Ly α emissions captured in both the 1D and 2D spectra using PANDORA and MPDAF.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5.4: Shown are example rest-frame spectra of VANDELS galaxies categorised by confidence levels for CIII] emission: (a) *Confidence Level 1* exhibits low CIII] emission accompanied by significant noise; (b) *Confidence Level 2* displays higher CIII] emission amidst considerable noise; and (c) *Confidence Level 3* showcases a distinct peak in CIII] emission. These plots provide insight into the application of confidence level ratings throughout the analysis.

Figure 5.5: Example VANDELS galaxy spectra in observed rest frame as shown in PANDORA focusing on the CIII] emission line in its observed wavelength. These four images are arranged in a single vertical column for direct comparison, with each image illustrating a key aspect of the spectral analysis, (a) Reduced 2D spectrum showing clearly the CIII] line that aided in the confidence level assignment; (b) CIII] line emission flux showing clear detection; (c) Sky emission around the CIII] line of which there is little to none; and (d) Noise flux around the CIII] line. This particular example was given a C.L. 3.

As the main aim of this chapter is to study the dependence of C III] emission on $\text{Ly}\alpha$, we then proceeded to identify $\text{Ly}\alpha$ emission from all those galaxies that had possible C III] emission. We did not introduce a confidence level criterion for $\text{Ly}\alpha$ emission, as the reliability and significance of any $\text{Ly}\alpha$ emission was deter-

mined using emission line fitting (as discussed later). Across our parent sample, 62 galaxies were found to exhibit both Ly α and C III] (CL3) via visual inspection.

We then measured the strength of the emission lines in these 62 objects using a MUSE Python Data Analysis Framework (MPDAF)² code, which is an open-source python package. The first step involved determining a ‘systemic’ redshift using the C III] line, for which we used a single Gaussian fit (other Gaussian fits such as asymmetric and double were available to use however were not needed in this sample) and the systemic redshift was determined from the peak of this Gaussian (see Saxena et al., 2020, for example). Using the systemic redshift, each spectrum was de-redshifted and a single Gaussian was fitted to Ly α , C III] and all other rest-UV lines (such as He II and C IV) visible in the spectra, with the local continuum value for each line estimated by polynomial fitting to nearby regions free from other emission or absorption features. EWs and integrated fluxes were determined from these Gaussian fits. If the S/N ratio of the continuum was below 2σ , the 2σ noise level was used to determine a lower limit for the line EW.

Thanks to accurate systemic redshifts measured from the C III] line, we could also accurately measure the Ly α velocity offset from the systemic velocity. By comparing the centroid of the observed Ly α emission with that expected for a rest-frame wavelength of 1215.67Å using the galaxy systemic redshift, the velocity offset of the Ly α peak was determined for all galaxies in our sample using equation 5.2 (see Figure 5.7).

$$\Delta v_{Ly\alpha} = c \left(\frac{\lambda_{Ly\alpha_{rest}} - \lambda_{Ly\alpha_{obs}}}{\lambda_{Ly\alpha_{rest}}} \right) \quad (5.2)$$

where $\Delta v_{Ly\alpha}$ is the Ly α velocity offset, $\lambda_{Ly\alpha_{rest}}$ is the rest frame wavelength, $\lambda_{Ly\alpha_{obs}}$ is the observed wavelength and c is the speed of light.

The emission line fluxes, widths, EWs and the velocity offset of Ly α compared to systemic redshift are listed in Table B.1.

²<https://mpdaf.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

Figure 5.6: Sample spectra illustrating a Confidence Level 3 emitter characterized by strong C III] and Ly α emissions as highlighted in blue within the 1D spectra. The spectra is in its rest-frame showing line emission of object UDS020394 at $z = 3.3018$. The corresponding 2D spectra above exhibits the prominent emission features. The dashed lines indicate Ly α , He II and C III] emission respectively. Additionally, the Gaussian fit, represented by the red dashed line, is generated using the MPDAF code ($EW(CIII)] = 7.4\text{\AA} \pm 0.9$).

Figure 5.7: Example VANDELS UDS field spectra displaying the $\text{Ly}\alpha$ emission line at both observed peak emission (blue dashed line) and expected peak emission (green dotted line), accompanied by the Gaussian fit outlined in red. The $\text{Ly}\alpha$ line is offset due to resonant scattering, gas flows within and around the galaxy, and the optical depth effects in both the ISM and IGM. These factors vary across galaxies, resulting in unique offsets in the observed $\text{Ly}\alpha$ emission. The velocity offset ($\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$) is determined by assessing the deviation between these two lines using equation 5.2.

5.4.4 Identification of possible AGN

Prior to further analysis, we considered it important to identify possible AGN in our sample to remove any biases. As C III] has a high ionisation potential (24.4 eV), it is possible that some of the stronger C III] emitters are AGN. To explore this, we searched for another high ionisation line, He II λ 1640 (54.4 eV), which is also commonly seen in AGN.

We then attempted to identify possible AGN using rest-UV line ratio diagnostics. Specifically, we used $\text{EW}(\text{C III])}$ versus $\text{C III] } \lambda 1909 / \text{He II } \lambda 1640$ proposed by Nakajima et al. (2018b), which is shown in Figure 5.8. This resulted in the identification of 9 possible AGN out of the 62 CL3 C III] and $\text{Ly}\alpha$ emitters, which were

removed from our sample. Further, cross-matching with the deep X-ray deep catalogue that exists in CDFS (Luo et al., 2017) revealed one more source identified to be an AGN, which was also removed from our sample. We note that using the C III] and He II based AGN selection, we have reported 7 new possible AGN from VANDELS (Table B.1), which were not identified in previous studies (e.g Saxena et al., 2020).

For those galaxies with no clear He II detection, we estimated an upper flux limit by integrating the 1σ continuum-subtracted flux at the expected position (red stars with arrows in Figure 5.8). Since these values were consistent for star-forming galaxies, they were retained in the sample.

Figure 5.8: C III]/He II flux ratio vs EW(C III]) for CL3 C III] and Ly α emitting sources in our sample, with the dashed line representing the boundary between SFGs and AGN according to the photoionisation models of Nakajima et al. (2018b). Red stars indicate those classified as SFGs according to the boundaries. The red stars with arrows are C III] and Ly α emitters with no He II detection in their emission spectra and illustrate upper limits for those sources, which are consistent with photoionisation via star formation. Blue stars are objects with He II detections likely photoionised by AGN. Using this diagnostic (along with the CDFS deep X-ray catalogue, Luo et al. 2017), we identify 9 objects from our sample of 139 CL3 C III] and Ly α emitters likely dominated by AGN, and remove them from our sample going forward.

5.4.5 Final sample

The final sample of C III] and Ly α emitting SFGs in the redshift range $z \approx 3 - 4$ comprises of 52 galaxies. Figure 5.9 provides a breakdown of the overall sample and the various selection steps that were implemented to select the sources.

In Figure 5.10 we show the parameter space occupied by our C III] emitter sample. In the left panel we show the distribution of M_{UV} and redshift for our final sample. As is evident from the Figure, our sample spans a relatively large range of UV magnitudes (-22 to -18.5), and the flux-limited nature of the survey naturally results in an incompleteness of fainter UV magnitudes at high redshifts. In the middle panel we show EW(C III]) as a function of M_{UV} , which shows a slight decrease in EW(C III]) at brighter M_{UV} . Finally in the right panel we show the EW(C III]) as a function of redshift, which also highlights the known overdensity in CDFS at $z \sim 3.5$ (Forrest et al., 2017; Guaita et al., 2020; Luo et al., 2017; Skelton et al., 2014; Straatman et al., 2016). Apart from two objects with relatively

Figure 5.9: Flowchart showing the various samples and the number of objects retained after each stage of inspection/selection. Our final sample comprises 52 SFGs that are CL3 C III] emitters with Ly α emission and unlikely to host an AGN.

Table 5.1: VANDELS sample comparing the full C III] emitters with the emitters that also show Ly α in their spectra. Comparisons include the total number of emitters, confidence level 3's, the average EW for C III] and Ly α with their respective ranges.

	C III] (full sample)	C III] & Ly α
Total number	173	44
CL3	72	14
Avg. EW(C III]) [\AA]	2.9	6.3
Range EW(C III]) [\AA]	1.07 – 12.1	1.5 – 9.8
Avg. EW(Ly α) [\AA]	-	14.2
Range EW(Ly α) [\AA]	-	2.6 – 79.9

Figure 5.10: This figure outlines the parameter space which our VANDELS sample occupies. (*left*): Absolute UV magnitudes as a function of redshift for our final sample, demonstrating a wide range of M_{UV} covered by our sample as well as the incompleteness of fainter M_{UV} at high redshift. (*middle*): Rest-frame EW(C III]) as a function of M_{UV} , showing a mild decrease in the EW(C III]) at brighter M_{UV} . (*right*): The distribution of EW(C III]) with redshift for sources in the UDS (green) and CDFS (orange) field. The shaded region highlights the known overdensity in the CDFS field at $z \sim 3.5$, where we do find a slight excess of C III] emitters.

high EW(C III]) at $z \sim 3.5$, we do not find any strong indication that there is an overall increase in the EW(C III]) in the overdense region compared to the rest of the sample. There is also no appreciable clear trend between EW(C III]) and redshift, although we acknowledge the possibility that C III] detections may be influenced by sample incompleteness.

5.5 Results

5.5.1 Strength of C III] emission

Across our sample of 52 C III] and Ly α emitting galaxies, we measure an average EW(C III]) of 5.0 Å. In Figure 5.10 we have highlighted the possible UV magnitude incompleteness resulting at higher redshifts because of the flux-limited nature of the sample. To address this, we divided our total sample of 52 galaxies into two sets based on M_{UV} , with the ‘Bright’ subsample with $M_{UV} < -20.4$ containing 24 galaxies and the ‘Faint’ subsample with $M_{UV} \geq -20.4$ containing 28 galaxies. This cut-of point was chosen as this reflected the completeness limit of our sample.

The galaxies in the Bright subsample have EW(C III]) in the range 1.6 – 9.8 Å and an average EW(C III]) of 5 Å. Galaxies in the Faint subsample contains 28 galaxies showing a much larger range of EW(C III]) in the range 2.2 – 12.8 Å, with an average value of 5.6 Å, which is marginally larger than that of the Bright subsample. These values along with those from other C III]-selected samples in the literature are given in Table 5.2.

In Table 5.2, we also compare our sample with similar samples targeting C III] emitters available in the literature (Cullen et al., 2020; Le Fèvre et al., 2019; Llerena et al., 2021; Shapley et al., 2003; Stark et al., 2014). Our VANDELS sample represents a valuable increase in the total number of galaxies with both C III] and Ly α EWs over the full redshift range ($z \sim 0 - 10.6$) (as quoted in Ravindranath et al., 2020) from 59 to 111. Specifically, within the redshift range $z \sim 3 - 4$, the sample increases from 38 to 80 galaxies with EW(C III])’s ranging from 1.6 – 12.8 Å. Within our own sample we find that the UV-faint galaxies have a slightly higher average compared to the UV-bright galaxies.

We note that although the Bright subsample is more complete across higher redshifts, the Faint subsample may be more representative of typical star-forming galaxies at $z > 6$ that are now being routinely discovered by various *JWST* surveys (Cameron et al., 2023; Curti et al., 2023; R. Endsley et al., 2023; Saxena et al., 2023; Tacchella et al., 2022). Therefore, going forward, we colour code the VANDELS sample using their UV absolute magnitude when studying their Ly α and

Table 5.2: Average EW(C III]) and the range for C III] emitters that also show Ly α emission in this work and from other studies in the literature at redshifts $z \sim 2 - 5$ (Dashes represent no data publicly available).

Data	EW(C III]) [\AA]	Range [\AA]	N
VANDELS (<i>this work</i>)	5.3	1.6 - 12.8	52
BRIGHT (<i>this work</i>)	5.0	1.6 - 9.8	24
FAINT (<i>this work</i>)	5.6	2.2 - 12.8	28
Nakajima et al., 2018b	2.0	-	-
Stark et al., 2014	8.8	1.8 - 13.5	11
Shapley et al., 2003	3.6	1.9 - 5.7	2.0
Rigby et al., 2015	1.6	0.1 - 4.0	20
Le Fèvre et al., 2019 (<i>stacked</i>)	2.0	-	-
Le Fèvre et al., 2019 (<i>stacked</i>)	2.2	-	-
Llerena et al., 2021 (<i>stacked</i>)	3.9	-	-

C III] properties where appropriate.

5.5.2 Relationship between C III] and Ly α line strengths

In this section we explore the relationships between C III] and Ly α emission in the VANDELS data from $3 < z < 4$ and compare our results to earlier studies at similar redshifts in the literature. We also discuss the dependence of Ly α velocity offsets.

Comparing with our original sample of only C III]-selected galaxies from VANDELS, we find that C III] emitters that show Ly α emission have higher C III] EWs overall compared to only C III] emitters. This can be seen in Figure 5.11 where we compare the histogram of the full CL3 C III] emitters in the full VANDELS dataset (blue) and C III] emitters with detectable Ly α (green). The median C III] EW of galaxies with both C III] and Ly α is $\sim 5 \text{\AA} (\pm 2.5)$, compared to a median C III] EW of only $2.9 \text{\AA} (\pm 4)$ for those across the full CL.3 sample (see also Cullen et al., 2020). These Ly α emitters having systematically higher EW(C III]) may be explained by the presence of harder ionising radiation fields in such galaxies, tracing low metallicities and young stellar ages, as was also discussed by Cullen et al. (2020).

To explore any dependence of C III] and Ly α strengths on the absolute UV magnitudes of our final sample, we also investigate the line flux ratio between these

Figure 5.11: Histogram showing the distribution of $EW(C\text{ III]})$ for CL3 C III]-emitters in our analysis. The blue histogram illustrates the full CL3 sample of C III], while the green illustrates the subsample of galaxies that have both C III] and $\text{Ly}\alpha$ emission. We find that C III] emitters that also have $\text{Ly}\alpha$ emission tend to have higher $EW(C\text{ III]})$ when compared to C III] emitters that do not have strong $\text{Ly}\alpha$ emission.

two lines in both the Bright and Faint subsamples that we had created above. This reveals an average $\text{Ly}\alpha / C\text{ III]}$ flux ratio of 8.42 for Bright ($M_{\text{UV}} < -20.4$) galaxies, and a ratio of 5.99 for Faint ($M_{\text{UV}} > -20.4$) galaxies in our final sample. This implies that, while possessing similar $\text{Ly}\alpha$ strengths, UV-faint galaxies exhibit a more pronounced C III] line intensity, once again potentially tracing the presence of younger stars and perhaps more ‘bursty’ star-formation histories.

To further explore correlations between $\text{Ly}\alpha$ and C III] strengths in our sample, in Figure 5.12 we show the distribution of $EW(C\text{ III]})$ and $EW(\text{Ly}\alpha)$, colour-coded by M_{UV} . For demonstration purposes, we show the line of best fit as obtained by Ravindranath et al. (2020) for a combined sample from the literature of $\text{Ly}\alpha$ -selected star-forming galaxies at $z \simeq 0 - 7$ (depicted as the blue dashed line). From our sample alone, we do not find a clear correlation between $EW(C\text{ III]})$ and

Figure 5.12: Rest-frame EWs of C III] and Ly α in our VANDELS sample, colour coded by absolute UV magnitude, compared with samples from the literature spanning a redshift range $z \simeq 2-4$ (Cullen et al., 2020; Le Fèvre et al., 2019; Llerena et al., 2021; Shapley et al., 2003; Stark et al., 2014). We also include in the figure $z > 7$ measurements from *JWST*/NIRSpec from Tang et al., 2023 ($z \simeq 7-9$). The blue dashed line shown represents the line of best fit outlined in Ravindranath et al., 2020 while the vertical grey line and shaded region presents a cut off at $\text{EW}(\text{Ly}\alpha) \leq 10 \text{ \AA}$ where our sample has a number of strong C III] emitters with weak Ly α emission.

$\text{EW}(\text{Ly}\alpha)$, which may be expected given how our sample has been selected. Compared to other literature samples, we have selected our galaxies based on C III] detections alone. This means that there may be a number of Ly α -emitting galaxies with no C III] detection, which will be missed by our selection, rendering our sample relatively incomplete for any statistical analysis. These galaxies were not included as we were focusing on solely those with both C III] and Ly α . The origin of the high UV flux in this case could potentially be caused by low gas and dust content in these galaxies which could enhance UV transparency, allowing more of the UV flux to escape and making the galaxies appear more UV-luminous without accompanying high EWs in emission lines.

Interestingly however, at $\text{EW}(\text{Ly}\alpha) < 10 \text{ \AA}$, we observe a large scatter in $\text{EW}(\text{C III]})$ shown via the grey dashed line and shaded region. The $\text{EW}(\text{C III]})$ of galaxies in this regime ranges from $\sim 1.6 - 13.0 \text{ \AA}$, which represents the widest

range of $\text{EW}(\text{C III])}$ for any given $\text{EW}(\text{Ly}\alpha)$ bin. Large $\text{EW}(\text{C III])}$ values often indicate conditions with high ionisation parameters and low metallicities, whereas $\text{Ly}\alpha$ emission is affected by line-of-sight attenuation from regions of high neutral gas or dust. These effects may explain the low observed $\text{EW}(\text{Ly}\alpha)$. Another possible explanation is offered by the presence of AGN powering the C III]) emission in this regime, which could perhaps have been missed by the UV line ratio diagnostics that we employed earlier.

We note that UV luminous galaxies in our sample (red points in Figure 5.12) occupy the lower part of the distribution, with low $\text{EW}(\text{C III])}$ as well as low $\text{EW}(\text{Ly}\alpha)$. These luminous galaxies are perhaps tracing more evolved, less star-forming systems in our sample, which would explain the weak EWs.

We further show C III]) detections reported from galaxies at $z > 7$ from Tang et al. (2023) using *JWST*/NIRSpec spectroscopy (Figure 5.12 shown as grey 'x's). Interestingly, the galaxies from Tang et al. (2023) also show very high $\text{EW}(\text{C III])}$ values with low $\text{EW}(\text{Ly}\alpha)$. At these redshifts, the low $\text{EW}(\text{Ly}\alpha)$ can be explained by near complete attenuation of $\text{Ly}\alpha$ emission by the intervening neutral IGM. This highlights that at the highest redshifts, we would expect to see strong C III]) even in the absence of strong $\text{Ly}\alpha$, as is the case for a handful of our VANDELS galaxies at intermediate redshifts.

5.5.3 $\text{Ly}\alpha$ velocity offset as a function of $\text{Ly}\alpha$ equivalent width

In this section we briefly explore the $\text{Ly}\alpha$ properties of our galaxies. Across our sample, we measure $\text{Ly}\alpha$ velocity offsets ranging from $166 - 1051 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, with an average value of $\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha} \simeq 533 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. In Figure 5.13 we show the velocity offset from systematic redshift as a function of $\text{EW}(\text{Ly}\alpha)$, colour-coded by M_{UV} , finding qualitatively an anti-correlation between the $\text{Ly}\alpha$ velocity offset and strength. This anti-correlation has also been previously reported in the literature for star-forming galaxies across redshifts (e.g. Erb et al., 2010; Nakajima et al., 2018a; Prieto-Lyon et al., 2023; Roy et al., 2023; Saxena et al., 2024; Tang et al., 2023).

We also compare our $\text{Ly}\alpha$ measurements with those available for a handful of reionisation era $\text{Ly}\alpha$ -emitting galaxies at $z > 6$ that likely reside in ionised bubbles.

Figure 5.13: Ly α EW vs Ly α velocity offset for the VANDELS C III] data in the context of *JWST* literature (Bunker et al., 2023; R. Endsley et al., 2023; Jung et al., 2023; Saxena et al., 2024; Tang et al., 2023), colour coded using M_{UV} . Overall, we find a declining Ly α velocity offset from systemic redshift with increasing Ly α EWs, consistent with earlier work (e.g. Erb et al., 2010; Nakajima et al., 2018a; Prieto-Lyon et al., 2023; Saxena et al., 2024). We further note that UV-bright galaxies often tend to have weaker Ly α EWs and higher velocity offsets.

Shown in the figure are Ly α velocity offsets measured from LAEs as compiled by R. Endsley et al. (2023) using ground-based observations with systemic redshifts measured from other rest-UV lines or far-infrared lines from ALMA. Additionally, we show measurements from LAEs at $z > 6$ from the latest *JWST* surveys, which include the faint LAEs presented in Saxena et al. (2024) using deep spectroscopy from the JADES survey, and relatively brighter LAEs selected from CEERS (Jung et al., 2023; Tang et al., 2023). We additionally show the measurement from GN-z11 at $z = 10.6$ from Bunker et al. (2023).

Overall, the $z > 6$ LAEs agree with the general trend observed between EW(Ly α) and $\Delta v_{Ly\alpha}$ in our sample, and the scatter we find in our sample is highly consistent with other high redshift LAE observations (e.g. Choudhury et al.,

2021; Erb et al., 2010; Nakajima et al., 2018a; Prieto-Lyon et al., 2023; Stark et al., 2014; Tang et al., 2023; Willott et al., 2015). This demonstrates that the $z > 6$ LAEs must likely reside in patches of relatively ionised IGM, where the Ly α attenuation and profile is largely being determined by scattering through the ISM. The relatively low number of VANDELS sources with velocity offsets below ($< 200 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) is primarily due to our sample selection: strong Ly α emission that lacked C III] detections were deliberately removed from the dataset. These excluded sources would have otherwise populated this region.

As has been noted by other studies, the anti-correlation between Ly α velocity offset and EW is likely driven by the density and geometry of neutral gas in the systems, where a higher density leads to increased absorption/scattering of Ly α photons along a line of sight, leading to a reduction in the observed EW and an increase in the velocity offset from systemic, which can be explained using the ‘expanding shell model’ described in Dijkstra et al. (2016) and Verhamme et al. (2006) (see Figure 5.14). This explanation is supported by Marchi et al. (2019), who used a similar VANDELS dataset and found a correlation between the Ly α velocity offset and the shift in the interstellar absorption lines, where galaxies with high ISM outflow velocities also showed small Ly α velocity offsets.

Prieto-Lyon et al. (2023) identified a notably reduced mean value of $\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$ at 205 km s^{-1} for some of the faintest galaxies (avg. $M_{\text{UV}} \sim -17.8$) within a similar redshift range ($3 < z < 5$). This observation is expected since their sample primarily encompasses galaxies with limited diversity in terms of their stellar masses and consequently lower neutral gas densities, where a higher $\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$ may be less frequently observed.

Assuming that the observed Ly α properties in our sample of galaxies are regulated by attenuation/scattering by neutral gas in the ISM at redshifts where the neutral IGM is not expected to attenuate Ly α significantly, we can now attempt to understand the physical conditions that regulate both the strength and velocity profiles of Ly α emission as well as the strength of C III] emission. This can then be used to understand how C III] emission may potentially be used as a diagnostic

Figure 5.14: Here we can see a schematic describing the 'Expanding Shell Model'. As the light blue shell (gas) moves away from the central emitting region, the $\text{Ly}\alpha$ line shifts out of resonance with the absorbing gas. Consequently, it no longer gets absorbed by neutral hydrogen. Additionally, we note the back-scattering of the $\text{Ly}\alpha$ line at the back of the galaxy, leading to a redshift of the $\text{Ly}\alpha$ line and once more moving out of resonance with the neutral gas, allowing it to escape. The observer is at the right hand side at infinity and will observe a shift in the $\text{Ly}\alpha$ profile. In this illustration, C III] would not be affected by the neutral hydrogen gas cloud. (*Illustration created by author*)

for $\text{Ly}\alpha$ properties in reionisation era galaxies that do not reside in ionised bubbles, and therefore do not show $\text{Ly}\alpha$ emission.

5.5.4 C III] as a tracer of $\text{Ly}\alpha$ velocity offset

Having confirmed that the $\text{Ly}\alpha$ properties are indeed sensitive to the neutral gas density that controls the escape of $\text{Ly}\alpha$ photons along a line of sight, we now compare the velocity offset of $\text{Ly}\alpha$ with the strength of C III] emission to investigate whether the observed $\text{EW}(\text{C III]})$ can be used as a diagnostic of neutral gas content, and consequently $\text{Ly}\alpha$ and LyC escape from the ISM of high redshift galaxies.

In Figure 5.15 we show the distribution of $\text{Ly}\alpha$ velocity offset as a function of $\text{EW}(\text{C III]})$, once again colour-coded by M_{UV} for galaxies in our sample. Qualitatively speaking, there appears to be a tentative anti-correlation between the observed $\text{Ly}\alpha$ offset and $\text{EW}(\text{C III]})$, with UV-faint galaxies showing less scatter and UV-bright galaxies showing a larger scatter. Therefore, any possible correlation be-

Figure 5.15: C III] EW vs Ly α velocity offset for the VANDELS C III] data, colour coded using M_{UV} . The blue dashed line represents a non-weighted linear regression fit, and the shaded area represent the 1σ error for the VANDELS C III] data. The bright UV galaxies have a larger scatter due to the increased gas compared to the faint UV galaxies.

tween Ly α velocity offset and EW(C III]) must take into account the UV absolute magnitudes which seem to affect the relation.

In light of this, we derive a correlation between C III] and $\Delta v_{Ly\alpha}$, taking into account M_{UV} . To do this, we employ a multi-variate fit to quantify $\Delta v_{Ly\alpha}$ as a function of both EW(C III]) and M_{UV} , standardising the independent variables (x_i), which takes the form:

$$\frac{\Delta v_{Ly\alpha} - \bar{\Delta v}_{Ly\alpha}}{\sigma_{\Delta v}} = \sum_{i=1}^2 A_i \frac{x_i - \bar{x}_i}{\sigma_i} \quad (5.3)$$

where A_i are the coefficients for EW(C III]) and M_{UV} , \bar{x}_i and σ_i are the mean and standard deviation, respectively, of the independent variables. Performing a linear regression on this equation gives us the coefficients -0.388 for EW(C III]) and 0.16

Table 5.3: Best-fitting coefficients to predict Ly α velocity offset from the systemic redshift using EW(C III]) and M_{UV} .

Variable	A_i	\bar{x}_i	σ_i
$\Delta v_{Ly\alpha}$		539.5	158.6
EW(C III])	-0.388	5.3	2.5
M_{UV}	+0.16	-20.4	0.7

for M_{UV} . The values of the coefficients as well as the mean and standard deviations of the independent variables are given in Table 5.3.

The dashed blue line in Figure 5.15 shows the relationship that we have derived between Ly α velocity offset and EW(C III]) only, which shows a more promising anti-correlation between the two quantities with a Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient = -0.36 and p-value = 0.0008. The shaded region represents the 1σ uncertainty on this relation. The influence of M_{UV} on this relationship is evident in the Figure, with a notable split observed between the majority of UV luminous points falling below the trend line.

Interestingly, the $z > 7$ Ly α and C III] emitting galaxies from Tang et al. (2023) appear to line up well within the 1σ uncertainty on the relation that we have derived, as shown in Figure 5.15, suggesting the presence of large ionised bubbles around them. GN-z11 on the other hand seems to lie just outside the 1σ band. This may be consistent with the very low Ly α escape fraction reported in Bunker et al. (2023), which in combination with a relatively large velocity offset of ~ 500 , km s $^{-1}$ suggests that GN-z11 is likely not situated within an ionised bubble (see also Hayes et al., 2023), and the emergent Ly α has been heavily attenuated by the neutral IGM surrounding it. Based on the relations that we have derived, the Ly α velocity offset emerging from the ISM will be predicted to be much lower (up to 300 km s $^{-1}$ lower) based on our multivariate regression.

We find that for a fixed M_{UV} , an increase in EW(C III]) results in a decreasing $\Delta v_{Ly\alpha}$. However, interestingly, at a fixed EW(C III]) emission, UV-bright galaxies tend to exhibit a lower Ly α velocity offset compared to UV-faint galaxies. Notably, as mentioned previously, the UV-bright galaxies tend to lie below the best-fit line

we show in Figure 5.15. This behaviour suggests that for the same $\text{EW}(\text{C III])}$, UV-bright galaxies may be in a more ‘bursty’ phase of star-formation, potentially facilitating a more efficient clearing of channels through which $\text{Ly}\alpha$ can escape. It has indeed been shown that galaxies in the early Universe may be expected to follow a more bursty star-formation that boosts their observed UV magnitudes (e.g. R. Endsley et al., 2023; Simmonds et al., 2024). Stronger outflows driven by a stronger starburst aligns with expectations from $\text{Ly}\alpha$ escape in an expanding shell model (e.g. Dijkstra et al., 2016; Verhamme et al., 2006), where neutral gas is expelled, allowing the $\text{Ly}\alpha$ emission to escape close its systemic velocity.

Overall, our results indicate that the C III] emission is likely originating from an ionising radiation field likely driven by young stars. In such a scenario, the UV magnitude serves as a measure of the number of stars undergoing formation. To validate this observation comprehensively, additional UV-bright galaxies with strong C III] and $\text{Ly}\alpha$ signals are required. Erb et al. (2014) also noted velocity offset to be correlated with UV luminosity, however found that their faint LAE selected sub-sample of galaxies had smaller $\text{Ly}\alpha$ velocity offsets and did not see the correlations present in their UV-brighter comparison sample possibly due to lack of dynamical range in mass and luminosity.

In summary, our findings indicate that for a fixed M_{UV} , a higher $\text{EW}(\text{C III])}$ is associated with a lower velocity offset. Conversely, for a fixed $\text{EW}(\text{C III])}$, a brighter M_{UV} results in a lower velocity offset. We propose that this effect may be contributing to the observed patterns. The observed inverse correlation between $\text{EW}(\text{C III])}$, $\text{Ly}\alpha$ velocity offset and its dependence on galaxy UV magnitude, therefore, promotes the utility of C III] as a proxy for $\text{Ly}\alpha$ from galaxies in the epoch of reionisation. With increased C III] line detections across samples of $z > 6$ galaxies with NIRSpect, our derived correlations may lead to an additional albeit indirect estimate of the leakage of $\text{Ly}\alpha$ and from that potentially the LyC photons from star-forming galaxies in the early Universe.

5.6 Discussion and Summary

By employing alternative indicators in the absence of direct Ly α observations, we can still make significant strides in studying the processes that regulate the escape of Ly α as well as LyC photons, essential to understand the key drivers of reionisation. While Ly α remains a crucial component for understanding reionisation, its unavailability limits our capacity to obtain velocity offsets, which are crucial in estimating parameters such as Ly α /Lyman continuum escape fractions and bubble sizes (Jones et al., 2023; Prieto-Lyon et al., 2023; Saxena et al., 2024; Witstok et al., 2023).

Latest results constraining the Ly α fractions and EW distributions at $z > 6$ from *JWST* have found the Ly α fractions to be low, which is expected given the increasing neutral fraction of the IGM (e.g. Jones et al., 2023). This means that at the highest redshifts, unless SFG's are surrounded by ionised regions, observing Ly α emission will become increasingly challenging. Particularly beyond $z > 9.5$ as the prominent O and H lines shift beyond the detectable range of the *JWST* NIR-Spec, C III] may emerge as a next best feature to both confirm redshifts and deduce additional properties. Therefore, we propose a potential solution to use the relatively bright C III] emission line in rest-UV, coupled with M_{UV} , as a tracer for Ly α velocity offsets from systemic through the equation provided in Eq. 5.3.

With an increase in the number of detections of rest-UV lines at $z > 8$ (Bunker et al., 2023; Fujimoto et al., 2023; Hsiao et al., 2023; Tang et al., 2023; Topping et al., 2024), including the detection of C III] emission at $z = 12.5$ reported by D'Eugenio et al. (2023), it is becoming essential to maximize the utility of these emission lines in inferring all possible properties of galaxies and their surroundings. Our proposal to employ C III] as an indirect tracer of Ly α velocity offsets (Figure 5.15) represents an approach to utilise insights from this strong rest-UV line to better understand the escape of Ly α photons from the ISM of galaxies in the reionisation era, possibly evaluating their contribution towards reionising their local bubble.

In this study, we have used the rest-UV spectra for a sample of star-forming

galaxies in the redshift range 3 – 4 from the VANDELS survey with confirmed detections of Ly α and C III] lines, to explore the utility of using the C III] λ 1909 line, often the second brightest emission line after Ly α in the rest-UV, to infer the intrinsic Ly α properties of galaxies in the reionisation epoch, where Ly α is significantly attenuated by the neutral IGM. Starting with the detection of C III] emission from 391 objects in the UDS and CDFS fields from the VANDELS survey, we find that 36% of objects show C III] emission, with an average EW $\sim 3\text{\AA}$ across the total C III] population. Using the C III] line as a prerequisite, we have then searched for Ly α emission in the sample, recovering a final sample of 52 star-forming galaxies with robust detections of both Ly α and C III] in their spectra.

We find that the equivalent widths of Ly α and C III] are not significantly correlated, finding an increased scatter in EW(C III]) for galaxies with particularly low EW(Ly α) $< 10\text{\AA}$, in agreement with previous studies. We show that galaxies with strong Ly α emission have a higher EW(C III]) on average ($\sim 5\text{\AA}$) compared to those without Ly α , highlighting that Ly α emitting galaxies that also show C III] emission are likely tracing galaxies undergoing rapid star-formation. In this work we report some of the highest EW(C III]) values (ranging from 1.6 – 12.8 \AA) when compared with those published in the literature at comparable redshifts with a range of $z \sim 2 - 4$.

Using the peak of the C III] emission as an indicator of the systemic redshift of galaxies in our sample, we calculate Ly α velocity offsets, $\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$, in the range 166 – 1051 km s $^{-1}$, with an average of 533 km s $^{-1}$. We find a weak anti-correlation between EW(Ly α) and $\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$, as has been previously reported in the literature, attributed to the role of scattering of Ly α photons by the neutral gas in the ISM. Interestingly, we report an anti-correlation between EW(C III]) and $\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$, which appears to also depend on the absolute UV magnitude of the galaxy. This dependence of EW(C III]) on both $\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$ and M_{UV} is captured using a multi-variate equation, as shown in Equation 5.3 and Table 5.3, where we find that $\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$ anti-correlates more strongly with EW(C III]) (coefficient of -0.388), with a comparatively weaker but non-negligible correlation with M_{UV} (coefficient of +0.16).

From our multivariate equation, we find that for a fixed M_{UV} , an increase in $\text{EW}(\text{C III]})$ leads to a decrease in $\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$. At a fixed $\text{EW}(\text{C III]})$, on the other hand, UV-bright galaxies show lower $\text{Ly}\alpha$ velocity offsets compared to UV-faint galaxies. In our sample, we find that UV-bright galaxies tend to lie below the best-fitting relationship between only $\text{EW}(\text{C III]})$ and $\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$, suggesting that UV-bright galaxies with strong $\text{Ly}\alpha$ and C III] emission may be undergoing a more ‘bursty’ phase of star-formation, aiding the efficient clearing of channels through which $\text{Ly}\alpha$ can escape, consistent with the ‘expanding shell model’. Although this is promising within the context of a population of extremely UV-bright galaxies that are now being discovered $z \gtrsim 10$, to validate this trend, additional spectroscopy for galaxies at $z < 6$ with comparably bright absolute UV magnitudes is essential.

Thanks to *JWST* spectroscopy, it is now possible to detect C III] emission out to $z \gtrsim 10$, and therefore the relationship between $\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$ on $\text{EW}(\text{C III]})$ and M_{UV} that we have presented in this work may provide insights into the nature of the intrinsic $\text{Ly}\alpha$ emission that may be escaping from the ISM of these galaxies, before it encounters a relatively neutral IGM and gets attenuated along the line of sight. Obtaining a better handle on the intrinsic production and escape of $\text{Ly}\alpha$ photons from galaxies in the reionisation era can provide unprecedented insights into the dominant contributors of ionising photon towards cosmic reionisation.

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(Astropy Collaboration et al., 2013), MATPLOTLIB (Hunter, 2007), MPDAF (Bacon et al., 2016), PANDAS (The Pandas Development Team, 2020) and TOPCAT (Taylor, 2005).

Data Availability

The data underlying this paper are publicly available from the VANDELS data release page <http://vandels.inaf.it/dr4.html> and from the European Southern Observatory (ESO) archive <http://archive.eso.org/cms.html>. The PYTHON code used to analyse the data will be made available upon request.

Chapter 6

Conclusions and the Future of MOS

What's next?

6.1 Future Facilities

In 2002, Dey (2002) presented a thought-provoking series of questions about predicting future science problems and the instruments needed to solve them. This underscored a significant challenge in instrumentation: keeping pace with the constantly evolving landscape of science, especially in rapidly advancing fields like astronomy. However, despite changes, two things have stayed constant in recent decades: the necessity for a deeper and more detailed view of the Universe.

As mentioned in the introduction, wide-field MOS has been highlighted as a high priority of European astronomy evidenced by the considerable progress made towards future facilities. This has led to the development of larger wide-field MOS facilities currently advancing through their design and construction phases. Examples include MOSAIC, a second-generation instrument slated for the Extremely Large Telescope (ELT) (Morris et al., 2018), and MOONS, currently in development for the VLT. Additionally, projects like the Maunakea Spectroscopic Explorer (MSE) (A. Hill et al., 2022; Sheinis et al., 2023), the Wide-Field Spectroscopic Telescope (WST) (Mainieri et al., 2024), among others (refer to Table 6.1), are poised to propel MOS instrumentation into its next phase of innovation.

MSE, a proposed 10-meter-class telescope (11.25m), boasts a 1.5 square degree field of view and serves as a versatile survey instrument. It's equipped with 3249 fibres for cosmology experiments, providing low to moderate resolution. WST, another 10-meter-class telescope (12m), also acts as a multi-purpose survey instrument with a larger 5 square degree field of view. It accommodates 15,000 fibres feeding spectrographs spanning from 360 to 1330 nm.

Further facilities that are in the pipeline include MegaMapper (Stage-5) and DESI-II (Schlegel et al., 2022). MegaMapper is a Stage-5 spectroscopic instrument concept for the study of inflation and dark energy, while DESI-II will be an upgrade on the current DESI instrument with an enhanced number of actuators and a twin DESI instrument in the Southern Hemisphere on a site in Chile. MegaMapper, designed specifically for cosmology, utilises a more cost-effective approach and features a smaller 6.5-meter telescope with a 7 square degree field of view, ac-

commodating 26,100 fibres. A Chinese telescope also under construction is that of the 6.5m MULTiplexed Survey Telescope (MUST) (Zhang et al., 2022). MUST will adopt a multiple-element WFC and ADC, with over 20,000 fibres, achieving an efficiency 19 times higher than that of DESI.

In a league of their own will be the Giant Magellan Telescope (GMT) currently under construction in Las Campanas Peak, Chile (25.4m) (Johns et al., 2014), the Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT) (30m) (Sanders, 2013) and the ELT (39m), each with dedicated MOS instruments, however, owing to technical constraints, they will be restricted to a very narrow field of view, thereby limiting multiplexing capabilities.

Dedicated wide-field spectroscopic telescopes (such as MSE and WST) are the next generation of spectroscopic powerhouses that have extraordinary MOS capabilities with unprecedented resolution, that will once again transform our understanding as we go ever deeper and ever wider into the cosmos. An overview of these upcoming and future facilities can be seen in Table 6.1 where you can find and compare their main properties. For a comprehensive review of current and upcoming instruments, refer to Mainieri et al. (2024) and the Astronet Strategic Plan for European Astronomy Roadmap 2022 – 2035 ¹.

However, as these telescopes aim to capture fainter or more distant objects with greater spatial and spectral resolutions, they grow larger, necessitating bigger and more expensive optics and components. Astrophotonics circumvents this by downsizing instruments, facilitating extensive multiplexing, and unlocking unprecedented technological advancements and photonic functionalities previously unattainable in astronomical instrumentation. Astrophotonics is the area where astronomy and photonics meet, and in the next decade and beyond, we will witness significant strides propelled by the demand for more compact instrument solutions, tailored for the upcoming era of exceedingly large telescopes such as the ELT, GMT and TMT mentioned above. Teams across the world are now dedicating time and effort into on-chip integrated astrophotonic spectrographs. This cutting-edge technology will allow astronomers and instrumentalists to massively miniaturise astro-

¹<https://www.astronet-eu.org>

nomical spectrometers, from the size of a room to the size of a shoebox (Gatkine et al., [2022](#)).

Technology has no plans of slowing down, and for any astronomer or enthusiast, this is a good thing. As our instruments become more sophisticated, our telescopes bigger and our appetite for discovery even more ambitious, there are plans decades in advance for the next big project. After all, it does no harm to start planning.

Table 6.1: An updated summary of telescopes and MOS instruments of that in McConnachie et al., 2016. The table shows the main properties of upcoming instruments and is sorted by Class type.

Facility / Instrument	First light	Aperture (M in m)	Field of View (sq. deg)	Etendue	Multiplexing	Wavelength coverage (μm)	Spectral resolution (approx)	IFU	Dedicated facility
4 metre									
WHT / WEAVE	2024	4	3.14	39.5	1000	0.37-1.00 3 windows	5000 20000	Yes	Yes
VISTA / 4MOST	2024	4	4.2	52.8	1600 800	0.37-0.95 3 windows	4000-8000 18000-20000	No	Yes
6.5 metre									
MUST	2030+	6.5	5	166	10,000	0.36-1.0	2000-4000	No	Yes
MegaMapper	2030+	6.5	7.1	235	26000	0.36-0.98	4000	No	Yes
8 metre									
VLT / MOONS	2025	8.2	0.14	7.4	1000	0.8-1.8	4000	No	No
Subaru / PFS	2024	8.2	1.25	65.9	2400	0.38-1.26	2000-5000	No	No
10 metre +									
MSE	2030+	11.25	1.5	149	20000	0.36-0.95 0.36-1.8	6500 3000	Yes	Yes
WST	2030+	12	3.1	359	20000	3 windows 0.37-0.97 windows	30000 4000 40000	Yes	Yes
GMT / MANIFEST	2030+	24.5	0.09	45.5	250	0.35-0.95	2000-6000	Yes	No
TMT / WFOS	2030+	30	0.007	4.9	80	0.3-1.0	1500-3500	Yes	No
ELT / MOSAIC	2030+	39	0.009	10.7	200	0.39-1.80 windows	5000 20000	Yes	No

Etendue is defined as the product of the area of the telescope's entrance pupil and the solid angle over which it collects light.

6.2 Conclusion

The research carried out in the thesis spans two sides of astronomy, a hybrid of spectroscopic instrument development and the analysis of spectroscopic data for exploring the early Universe. Due to the nature of the thesis, this research had a broad set of goals, first to assemble, align and integrate the 4MOST WFC and secondly to explore data from the VANDELS survey in the context of the Epoch of Reionisation.

The first part of this thesis introduced the 4-metre Multi-Object Spectroscopic Telescope (4MOST). A facility *"for most"* of the astronomy community. The capabilities of the 4MOST instrument will significantly augment the findings of prominent large-sky surveys, both space-based and many ground-based, which have been outlined previously. The science programme of the 4MOST consortium is structured into ten surveys, each pursuing different science cases, ranging from Galactic Archaeology to Extragalactic objects, including one of the most complete spectroscopic surveys of AGN ever undertaken. In addition, fifteen science programmes led by ESO community scientists will be executed during the first 5-year survey of 4MOST (de Jong et al., 2016). Through meticulous alignment and measurement of the WFC elements, we were able to deliver the completed WFC with all lenses centered well within their specified tolerances. The results and measurements documented throughout this thesis have become a cornerstone and primary reference for further integration with the rest of the 4MOST subsystems, as well as for developing detailed 'as-built' models to better understand the potential performance.

As 4MOST progresses through its final integration process, and prepares for shipment to Chile, the latter portion of this thesis delves into the utilisation of another MOS instrument to explore the early Universe at high redshifts, particularly focusing on the Epoch of Reionisation. Leveraging data from VIMOS and the VANDELS Survey, we examine the robust C III] emission from an initial parent sample of 773 galaxies. From our detailed study, 52 of those C III] emitters also showed strong Ly α emission, while we deemed 10 to be AGN removing them from our sample. Among these, we discovered 7 new potential AGN that had not been pre-

viously detected. Using alternative indicators like C III] in the absence of direct Ly α observations, due to the increasing neutrality of the IGM, allows for significant progress in understanding the escape mechanisms of Ly α and LyC photons, crucial for studying reionisation.

Using a multi-variant equation we have established a connection between M_{UV} , EW(C III]) and $\Delta v_{Ly\alpha}$, finding a promising result that UV-bright galaxies exhibiting strong EW(Ly α) and EW(C III]) might be experiencing a phase of star formation characterised by bursts, facilitating the effective clearance of pathways through which Ly α can escape. As the number of detections of rest-UV lines above $z > 10$ increases, our proposal to utilise C III] as an indirect tracer of Ly α velocity offsets offers a means to leverage insights from rest-UV lines for a deeper understanding of Ly α photon escape. This becomes especially crucial beyond $z > 9.5$, as the prominent O and H lines move out of the detectable range for the JWST NIRSpec. C III] emerges as a valuable alternative.

Reflecting on the challenges introduced at the beginning, this thesis has made strides in addressing key questions about the utility of UV emission lines in studying early cosmic epochs, though certain challenges—such as disentangling AGN contributions—remain for future investigations. Overall the research detailed in this thesis has not only enhanced our comprehension of interpreting the relationship between C III] and Ly α velocity offset at intermediate redshifts, which can potentially provide unprecedented insights into the dominant contributors of ionising photons towards cosmic reionisation, but has also paved the way for the realisation of next-generation instruments. Through successful opto-mechanical work aligning and integrating the optics for the WFC, this thesis sets the stage for the emergence of the 4MOST instrument and the comprehensive and far-reaching science it aims to achieve.

6.3 Future work

As detailed in Chapter 4, thorough testing of the WFC optics is imperative to verify throughput and alignment once installed on the telescope. These tests are scheduled to be conducted in accordance with the AIV plan at the telescope. Additionally, it is recommended to conduct further testing using ZEMAX, comparing the as-built data derived from the measurements documented in this work with the initial design. Comprehensive testing will also involve aligning the AESOP fibre tips to the telescope focal surface and assessing the ADC at various zenith angles.

The methodologies employed at UCL in assembling and aligning the optics for the 4MOST WFC, and its thorough documentation outlined in this work, serve as a lasting legacy that details the construction and assembly of the 4MOST instrument. This documentation is poised to be an invaluable resource for forthcoming planned MOS projects in the field, including those previously outlined such as MSE, WST, and other wide-field surveys like MUST, all of which will incorporate their own corrector elements. It is highly probable that these projects will adopt our approach as a foundational framework for aligning their respective wide-field correctors elements.

Figure 5.15 revealed a new correlation with a multi-variant equation that described the interplay between C III] Ly α velocity offset and M_{UV} . As additional detections of C III] are emerging at higher redshifts, particularly through *JWST* observations, exploring the feasibility of utilising C III] as a proxy becomes increasingly valuable. To advance this work, larger samples of analogue galaxies with strong C III] emission would be useful and such investigation could offer valuable insights into confirming the correlations identified in this study.

Since 4MOST is limited in terms of ultra high- z science, it will be unable to tackle reionisation directly, primarily due to wavelength limitations, it is however well-suited to examine a broad array of AGN at lower- z through spectroscopic follow-up of eROSITA targets. Through its capabilities, 4MOST can shed light on pressing questions, such as whether low-mass galaxies harbour AGN—a question that currently lacks a definitive answer, but one that 4MOST can help eluci-

date. Furthermore, the implications for galaxy-Supermassive Black Hole (SMBH) co-evolution across redshifts and, ultimately, for AGN feedback mechanisms, are profound considerations that 4MOST's investigations could address. The 4MOST S6 AGN Survey offers a unique opportunity to statistically investigate AGN across the sky as a function of redshift, paving the way for studying AGN analogues at lower redshifts where 4MOST is particularly adept. While the focus of this thesis has predominantly been on examining the perspective of SFGs, the significance of AGN contributions is becoming increasingly apparent, especially in light of recent JWST findings. Recent JWST AGN studies suggest the presence of numerous faint AGN, surpassing previous estimations, indicating their potentially greater role in the process of reionisation.

Another avenue of interest lies in the relationship between C III] other UV lines and Ly α in the reionisation epoch, there is potential to use publicly available NIRSpect data to investigate UV lines from galaxies in the reionisation epoch and if detected, using the correlation found in our previous study to evaluate Ly α and potentially Ly-C emission, which would allow us to put a constraint on the ionising potential.

The technical foundation laid through the precise alignment and integration of the 4MOST WFC paves the way for future instruments aimed at high-redshift science, especially if combined with upcoming facilities like the Extremely Large Telescope to probe deeper into reionisation-era galaxies. With the vast datasets generated by surveys like 4MOST, integrating machine learning techniques could enhance our ability to detect subtle spectral features, potentially revealing new low-mass AGN or faint SFGs that current methods might overlook. By blending innovative instrument development with adaptable data analysis approaches, future astronomy will be well-equipped to address the complex questions of galaxy formation and evolution, solidifying the groundwork laid by this thesis for the next generation of extragalactic studies.

Figure 6.1: The author pictured with the final completed WFC before shipment to AIP.

Appendix A

Appendices to Chapter 3

A.1 4MOST WFC Assembly Process

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure A.1: Final assembly of the WFC after all lenses have been aligned to the system. (a) Main Structural Plate (MSP) (b) ADC being lowered into the MSP. (c) ADC unit integrated with MSP. (d) L2 bearing plate with blackened surface in ADC unit.

Figure A.2: Final assembly of the WFC after all lenses have been aligned to the system. (a) Tube A part (ii) integrated with MSP and ADC. (b) Tube A fully integrated. (c) Look down at the internal baffles of Tube A. (d) Fully assembled WFC with L1 integrated.

A.2 Packaging of WFC

For shipment of the WFC, both vertical and horizontal orientations were considered however to minimise risk of movement of the lenses, a vertical transportation was chosen. The WFC is positioned upright on the transport frame's base. The crate, measuring 184cm in length, 184cm in width, and 231cm in height, is made of wood

and insulated with 50mm thick foam for shock absorption. Wire rope isolators are employed to mount the WFC for shock protection. The MSP is bolted to the transport frame at the perimeter to provide support. This setup ensures that during transportation, the individual lenses receive uniform support pressure on surfaces, enhancing stability.

Figure A.3: (a) The WFC being secured and departing from the Optical Science Laboratory. (b) The WFC being carefully lifted out of the UCL lab with secure fastenings. (c) Lowering the WFC onto the platform, using in house crane. (d) The WFC securely packaged in it's transportation crate on the lorry, prepared for shipment to Germany.

Appendix B

Appendices to Chapter 5

B.1 Data table

Table B.1: Line measurements for confidence level 3 (CL3) C III] and Ly α emitters in the VANDELS sample.

Object ID	z_{spec}	C III] λ 1909			Ly α λ 1216			M_{UV}	
		EW ₀ (Å)	FWHM (km s ⁻¹)	Flux $\times 10^{-18}$ (erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²)	EW ₀ (Å)	FWHM (km s ⁻¹)	Flux $\times 10^{-18}$ (erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻²)		$\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$ (km s ⁻¹)
CDFS226606	4.0102	9.1 ± 1.5	678	1.28 ± 0.07	25.7 ± 1.7	894	5.69 ± 0.22	456 ± 17	-20.76
CDFS231741	4.0068	7.5 ± 1.4	671	0.71 ± 0.08	14.9 ± 1.5	1039	1.98 ± 0.13	558 ± 30	-20.51
CDFS226868	3.6884	4.3 ± 1.2	490	0.36 ± 0.09	28.6 ± 1.2	913	3.57 ± 0.05	577 ± 10	-20.19
CDFS000303	3.6137	5.5 ± 0.6	583	0.22 ± 0.02	26.8 ± 3.1	832	1.78 ± 0.01	570 ± 7	-19.87
CDFS017345	3.6052	4.28 ± 0.6	863	1.28 ± 0.2	33.4 ± 1.8	815	22.1 ± 0.85	560 ± 12	-21.73
CDFS233973	3.5913	6.1 ± 1.2	983	0.89 ± 0.12	2.5 ± 0.7	484	0.53 ± 0.15	693 ± 84	-20.24
CDFS015347	3.5124	7.1 ± 1.5	927	0.81 ± 0.1	11.9 ± 1.3	1257	1.85 ± 0.18	590 ± 59	-20.40
CDFS020583	3.4932	2.8 ± 0.4	552	0.30 ± 0.04	45.7 ± 3.5	787	8.49 ± 0.16	414 ± 7	-20.37
CDFS122764	3.492	1.8 ± 0.5	625	0.86 ± 0.05	2.5 ± 0.6	553	1.87 ± 0.43	700 ± 99	-21.83
CDFS128455	3.4813	3.3 ± 0.3	734	1.00 ± 0.06	23.4 ± 1.8	837	17.9 ± 0.88	730 ± 20	-21.73
CDFS004717	3.4756	4.2 ± 0.3	737	1.35 ± 0.07	4.2 ± 1.1	619	2.21 ± 0.56	481 ± 94	-21.62

CDFS

Continued on next page

Table B.1 continued from previous page

Object ID	z_{spec}	C III] λ 1909			Ly α λ 1216			M_{UV}	
		EW ₀	FWHM	Flux	EW ₀	FWHM	Flux		$\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$
CDFS140458	3.4708	3.7 ± 0.3	659	0.9 ± 0.03	46.9 ± 3.2	993	16.2 ± 0.33	528 ± 10	-21.16
CDFS009692	3.4698	10.4 ± 1.1	885	0.85 ± 0.02	56.8 ± 6.6	890	9.27 ± 0.19	491 ± 10	-20.11
CDFS012637	3.4655	5.6 ± 1.2	611	0.22 ± 0.03	51.8 ± 4.7	1609	3.10 ± 0.22	706 ± 52	-19.31
CDFS105360	3.4598	1.6 ± 0.4	416	0.54 ± 0.14	14.2 ± 1.7	756	8.79 ± 0.74	745 ± 44	-21.46
CDFS006417	3.4597	2.0 ± 0.2	706	0.33 ± 0.04	4.6 ± 1.2	667	1.03 ± 0.25	837 ± 106	-20.66
CDFS012448	3.4596	6.1 ± 1.0	464	1.04 ± 0.09	17.8 ± 2.1	1293	4.88 ± 0.30	679 ± 44	-20.72
CDFS103010	3.455	2.2 ± 0.4	468	0.40 ± 0.05	2.3 ± 0.9	524	0.49 ± 0.18	728 ± 155	-20.69
CDFS208906	3.4548	5.3 ± 1.1	708	0.54 ± 0.07	32.1 ± 4.1	835	5.68 ± 0.12	617 ± 7	-19.47
CDFS246390	3.4149	6.2 ± 1.6	596	0.97 ± 0.07	9.1 ± 1.1	884	2.64 ± 0.24	506 ± 42	-20.71
CDFS225147	3.3976	12.8 ± 2.8	564	0.61 ± 0.05	5.3 ± 0.7	597	0.58 ± 0.06	318 ± 49	-19.66
CDFS212043	3.395	4.7 ± 1.3	708	0.79 ± 0.11	33.1 ± 2.8	885	9.06 ± 0.15	410 ± 7	-20.43
CDFS215423	3.395	3.2 ± 1.2	313	0.51 ± 0.13	20.4 ± 2.8	1181	3.63 ± 0.26	511 ± 42	-20.02
CDFS206968	3.3808	2.7 ± 0.8	369	0.24 ± 0.07	8.2 ± 0.5	813	1.45 ± 0.01	405 ± 15	-20.13
CDFS024919	3.3528	5.9 ± 1.0	486	0.85 ± 0.09	58.6 ± 3.3	857	15.9 ± 0.22	520 ± 5	-20.57
CDFS229681	3.3291	7.1 ± 1.0	596	0.78 ± 0.04	6.0 ± 1.0	907	1.15 ± 0.16	538 ± 81	-19.95

Continued on next page

Table B.1 continued from previous page

Object ID	z_{spec}	C III] λ 1909			Ly α λ 1216			M_{UV}	
		EW ₀	FWHM	Flux	EW ₀	FWHM	Flux		$\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$
CDFS217955	3.327	7.7 ± 2.2	752	0.72 ± 0.11	14.0 ± 1.3	908	2.04 ± 0.07	444 ± 15	-19.77
CDFS209992	3.251	2.5 ± 0.8	426	0.27 ± 0.04	2.9 ± 1.1	612	0.41 ± 0.14	622 ± 205	-19.94
CDFS221849	3.2177	4.6 ± 2.3	630	0.42 ± 0.03	45.6 ± 9.0	965	5.69 ± 0.11	501 ± 10	-19.63
CDFS000598	3.1965	4.3 ± 0.9	576	0.44 ± 0.04	9.6 ± 1.4	1002	0.89 ± 0.10	1051 ± 104	-19.82
CDFS007847	3.1284	4.3 ± 0.8	480	0.58 ± 0.05	17.8 ± 2.5	1237	2.72 ± 0.32	632 ± 74	-20.06
CDFS113988	3.1246	2.1 ± 0.5	628	1.25 ± 0.28	5.3 ± 0.79	783	6.12 ± 0.70	434 ± 47	-21.72
CDFS023527	3.106	5.8 ± 1.3	682	1.95 ± 0.08	54.9 ± 5.2	1124	30.5 ± 1.23	550 ± 20	-21.16
CDFS032490	3.0747	4.4 ± 3.0	715	0.14 ± 0.01	60.4 ± 4.9	947	2.92 ± 0.09	573 ± 15	-18.72
CDFS206035	3.0578	5.1 ± 2.3	809	0.66 ± 0.10	9.0 ± 1.8	664	1.19 ± 0.22	466 ± 67	-19.42
CDFS003496	3.0253	4.9 ± 1.4	713	0.90 ± 0.10	6.7 ± 1.1	842	1.7 ± 0.26	795 ± 89	-20.34
CDFS015428	3.0037	2.2 ± 0.9	878	0.29 ± 0.03	33.2 ± 3.2	797	5.24 ± 0.13	548 ± 10	-19.79
CDFS022563	3.0004	6.8 ± 3.2	694	0.85 ± 0.06	28.5 ± 2.7	903	8.05 ± 0.27	656 ± 19	-20.14
UDS									
UDS026657 †	3.8161	†8.5	980	0.88 ± 0.09	6.6 ± 2.1	531	1.51 ± 0.17	389 ± 64	-20.62

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Table B.1 continued from previous page

Object ID	z_{spec}	C III] λ 1909			Ly α λ 1216			M_{UV}	
		EW ₀	FWHM	Flux	EW ₀	FWHM	Flux		$\Delta v_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$
UDS003783 †	3.8056	6.3	836	0.72 ± 0.15	22.1 ± 7.4	768	4.39 ± 0.43	369 ± 89	-20.78
UDS295074	3.7606	4.6 ± 0.5	1020	1.02 ± 0.08	14.2 ± 2.3	735	6.67 ± 0.66	443 ± 87	-21.53
UDS015507	3.61	9.8 ± 2.2	1224	1.65 ± 0.10	79.9 ± 12.8	841	24.9 ± 0.50	475 ± 19	-21.01
UDS151133	3.5628	4.9 ± 0.6	908	1.5 ± 0.13	11.5 ± 2.1	756	7.50 ± 0.91	332 ± 109	-21.62
UDS026015	3.497	3.3 ± 1.3	371	0.19 ± 0.06	17.9 ± 5.8	827	1.47 ± 0.05	566 ± 33	-19.59
UDS003724	3.4616	6.3 ± 1.3	793	0.74 ± 0.10	67.3 ± 21.8	1242	13.7 ± 0.17	443 ± 12	-20.45
UDS376176	3.3188	2.2 ± 0.6	404	0.25 ± 0.06	2.6 ± 1.5	514	0.36 ± 0.08	672 ± 172	-19.99
UDS020394	3.3018	7.4 ± 0.9	698	0.67 ± 0.06	12.6 ± 2.5	823	2.19 ± 0.09	456 ± 42	-20.05
UDS000166	3.24	6.5 ± 0.9	489	0.51 ± 0.05	9.0 ± 2.4	614	0.67 ± 0.08	170 ± 83	-19.83
UDS380039 †	3.23	9.6	649	0.78 ± 0.18	9.2 ± 3.9	744	2.26 ± 0.06	334 ± 20	-19.45
UDS026615	3.199	4.7 ± 0.8	739	0.50 ± 0.07	27.8 ± 10.2	915	6.0 ± 0.33	628 ± 58	-20.04
UDS019280	3.186	9.5 ± 1.5	841	1.03 ± 0.13	47.8 ± 19.9	945	7.06 ± 0.10	466 ± 16	-19.66
UDS197598	3.000	2.1 ± 0.4	827	1.34 ± 0.24	26.7 ± 3.1	516	40.7 ± 1.48	166 ± 52	-21.61
Average (1 σ)		5.3 (±2.5)	680 (±187)	0.76 (±0.39)	17.8 (±19.6)	836 (±226)	3.34 (±8.15)	533 (±158)	

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Table B.1 continued from previous page

Object ID	z_{spec}	C III] λ 1909			Ly α λ 1216			M_{UV}
		EW ₀	FWHM	Flux	EW ₀	FWHM	Flux	
AGN								
CDFS006905 *	3.6885	6.5 ± 1.5	749	0.85 ± 0.16	16.7 ± 1.9	2206	2.91 ± 0.31	442 ± 12
CDFS006327 *	3.4937	4.5 ± 1.4	678	0.19 ± 0.02	26.2 ± 2.4	976	1.39 ± 0.39	606 ± 12
CDFS025897 *	3.4706	5.0 ± 0.7	929	0.84 ± 0.08	13.6 ± 1.5	732	3.80 ± 0.22	522 ± 12
CDFS217560 *	3.4535	2.1 ± 0.8	534	0.19 ± 0.07	56.8 ± 6.9	827	8.52 ± 0.12	409 ± 12
CDFS247279 *	3.2959	14.1 ± 3.6	650	1.1 ± 0.05	7.3 ± 1.6	1161	1.49 ± 0.31	916 ± 96
CDFS020988 *	3.2638	3.8 ± 0.6	486	0.09 ± 0.01	51.7 ± 10.5	921	2.66 ± 0.05	498 ± 12
UDS300247 *	3.794	15.3 ± 3.9	923	1.03 ± 0.14	22.2 ± 4.0	778	5.24 ± 0.19	452 ± 30
UDS006692 *	3.7663	2.1 ± 0.5	471	0.34 ± 0.08	7.3 ± 1.2	748	2.03 ± 0.28	455 ± 132
UDS382631 *†	3.2176	†17.2	1178	2.45 ± 0.17	60.1 ± 6.9	826	29.4 ± 0.40	453 ± 12
UDS145830 *	3.2094	12.4 ± 1.0	1118	1.16 ± 0.06	81.2 ± 13.3	983	7.51 ± 0.99	66 ± 15

Note: '*' denotes an AGN candidate that was removed in the final sample and not included in the quoted average values.

'†' denotes those objects with a lower limit for C III].

Bibliography

- Adelberger, Kurt L. et al. (Feb. 2003). “Galaxies and Intergalactic Matter at Redshift $z=3$: Overview”. In: *ApJ* 584.1, pp. 45–75. DOI: [10.1086/345660](https://doi.org/10.1086/345660). arXiv: [astro-ph/0210314](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0210314) [astro-ph].
- Akiyama, Masayuki et al. (July 2008). “Performance of Echidna fiber positioner for FMOS on Subaru”. In: *Advanced Optical and Mechanical Technologies in Telescopes and Instrumentation*. Ed. by Eli Atad-Ettinger et al. Vol. 7018. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 70182V, p. 70182V. DOI: [10.1117/12.788968](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.788968).
- Allington-Smith, Jeremy R. et al. (July 1990). “Low dispersion survey spectrograph for the William Herschel Telescope”. In: *Instrumentation in Astronomy VII*. Ed. by David L. Crawford. Vol. 1235. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, pp. 691–701. DOI: [10.1117/12.19132](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.19132).
- Antonik, M. et al. (2009). “The design and alignment of the DECam lenses and modelling of the static shear pattern and its impact on weak lensing measurements”. In: *Optical System Alignment, Tolerancing, and Verification III*. Ed. by José Sasián et al. Vol. 7433. International Society for Optics and Photonics. SPIE, p. 74330M. DOI: [10.1117/12.825869](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.825869). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.825869>.
- Astropy Collaboration et al. (Oct. 2013). “Astropy: A community Python package for astronomy”. In: *A&A* 558, A33, A33. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201322068](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201322068). arXiv: [1307.6212](https://arxiv.org/abs/1307.6212) [astro-ph.IM].

- Azais, Nicolas et al. (June 2016). “Wide field corrector for 4MOST: design details and MAIV processes”. In: DOI: [10.1117/12.2232304](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2232304).
- Bacon, Roland et al. (Nov. 2016). “MPDAF: MUSE Python Data Analysis Framework”. In: ascl:1611.003, ascl:1611.003. ascl: [1611.003](https://arxiv.org/abs/1611.003).
- Balcells, Marc et al. (July 2010). “Design drivers for a wide-field multi-object spectrograph for the William Herschel Telescope”. In: *Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy III*. Ed. by Ian S. McLean et al. Vol. 7735. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 77357G, 77357G. DOI: [10.1117/12.856947](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.856947). arXiv: [1008.0600](https://arxiv.org/abs/1008.0600) [[astro-ph.IM](https://arxiv.org/abs/1008.0600)].
- Baldwin, J. A. et al. (Feb. 1981). “Classification parameters for the emission-line spectra of extragalactic objects.” In: *PASP* 93, pp. 5–19. DOI: [10.1086/130766](https://doi.org/10.1086/130766).
- Barden, Samuel C. et al. (Dec. 2020). “The 4MOST secondary guider imaging system”. In: *Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series*. Vol. 11447. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 114478Q, 114478Q. DOI: [10.1117/12.2562381](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2562381).
- Becker, George D. et al. (Dec. 2013). “New measurements of the ionizing ultraviolet background over $2 < z < 5$ and implications for hydrogen reionization”. In: *MNRAS* 436.2, pp. 1023–1039. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stt1610](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stt1610). arXiv: [1307.2259](https://arxiv.org/abs/1307.2259) [[astro-ph.CO](https://arxiv.org/abs/1307.2259)].
- Behrens, C. et al. (Aug. 2013). “Effects of Lyman-alpha scattering in the IGM on clustering statistics of Lyman-alpha emitters”. In: *A&A* 556, A5, A5. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201321172](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201321172). arXiv: [1306.0920](https://arxiv.org/abs/1306.0920) [[astro-ph.CO](https://arxiv.org/abs/1306.0920)].
- Bellido, Olga et al. (Sept. 2017). “4MOST optical system: presentation and design details”. In: p. 37. DOI: [10.1117/12.2272435](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2272435).
- Bellido-Tirado, Olga et al. (Aug. 2022). “4MOST guiding and wavefront sensing cameras: requirements and early testing”. In: *Ground-based and Airborne*

- Telescopes IX*. Ed. by Heather K. Marshall et al. Vol. 12182. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 1218223, p. 1218223. DOI: [10.1117/12.2629893](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2629893).
- Bennett, C. L. et al. (Oct. 2013). “Nine-year Wilkinson Microwave Anisotropy Probe (WMAP) Observations: Final Maps and Results”. In: *ApJSS* 208.2, 20, p. 20. DOI: [10.1088/0067-0049/208/2/20](https://doi.org/10.1088/0067-0049/208/2/20). arXiv: [1212.5225](https://arxiv.org/abs/1212.5225) [[astro-ph.CO](https://arxiv.org/archive/ph)].
- Bensby, T. et al. (Mar. 2019). “4MOST Consortium Survey 4: Milky Way Disc and Bulge High-Resolution Survey (4MIDABLE-HR)”. In: *The Messenger* 175, pp. 35–38. DOI: [10.18727/0722-6691/5123](https://doi.org/10.18727/0722-6691/5123). arXiv: [1903.02470](https://arxiv.org/abs/1903.02470) [[astro-ph.GA](https://arxiv.org/archive/ph)].
- Benson, Andrew et al. (June 2013). “The Escape Fraction of Ionizing Radiation from Galaxies”. In: *ApJ* 770.1, 76, p. 76. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/770/1/76](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/770/1/76). arXiv: [1212.4452](https://arxiv.org/abs/1212.4452) [[astro-ph.CO](https://arxiv.org/archive/ph)].
- Bode, M et al. (2008). “The ASTRONET Infrastructure Roadmap: A Twenty Year Strategy for European Astronomy”. In: *The Messenger* 134, pp. 2–4.
- Bosman, Sarah E. I. et al. (July 2022). “Hydrogen reionization ends by $z = 5.3$: Lyman- α optical depth measured by the XQR-30 sample”. In: *MNRAS* 514.1, pp. 55–76. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stac1046](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stac1046). arXiv: [2108.03699](https://arxiv.org/abs/2108.03699) [[astro-ph.CO](https://arxiv.org/archive/ph)].
- Bouwens, R. J. et al. (Apr. 2015). “UV Luminosity Functions at Redshifts $z \sim 4$ to $z \sim 10$: 10,000 Galaxies from HST Legacy Fields”. In: *ApJ* 803.1, 34, p. 34. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/803/1/34](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/803/1/34). arXiv: [1403.4295](https://arxiv.org/abs/1403.4295) [[astro-ph.CO](https://arxiv.org/archive/ph)].
- Brzeski et al. (2018). “AESOP: the 4MOST fiber positioner”. In: 10702. Ed. by Christopher J. Evans et al., pp. 2172–2188. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2310062>.
- (Aug. 2022). “AESOP, the 4MOST fibre positioner: engineering principles”. In: *Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy IX*. Ed. by Christopher J. Evans et al. Vol. 12184. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumen-

- tation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 121846N, 121846N. DOI: [10 . 1117/12.2627903](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2627903).
- Bunker, Andrew J. et al. (Feb. 2023). “JADES NIRSpec Spectroscopy of GN-z11: Lyman- α emission and possible enhanced nitrogen abundance in a $z = 10.60$ luminous galaxy”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2302.07256, arXiv:2302.07256. DOI: [10 . 48550 / arXiv . 2302 . 07256](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2302.07256). arXiv: [2302 . 07256](https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.07256) [[astro-ph.GA](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro-ph)].
- Caillier, Patrick et al. (July 2018). “4MOST low resolution spectrograph final design”. In: *Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy VII*. Ed. by Christopher J. Evans et al. Vol. 10702. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 1070287, p. 1070287. DOI: [10.1117/12.2313604](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2313604).
- Cameron, Alex J. et al. (Feb. 2023). “JADES: Probing interstellar medium conditions at $z \sim 5.5 - 9.5$ with ultra-deep JWST/NIRSpec spectroscopy”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2302.04298, arXiv:2302.04298. DOI: [10 . 48550 / arXiv . 2302 . 04298](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2302.04298). arXiv: [2302 . 04298](https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.04298) [[astro-ph.GA](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro-ph)].
- Carniani, Stefano et al. (Sept. 2024). “Spectroscopic confirmation of two luminous galaxies at a redshift of 14”. In: *Nature* 633.8029, pp. 318–322. DOI: [10 . 1038 / s41586 - 024 - 07860 - 9](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07860-9). arXiv: [2405 . 18485](https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.18485) [[astro-ph.GA](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro-ph)].
- Chiappini, C. et al. (Mar. 2019). “4MOST Consortium Survey 3: Milky Way Disc and Bulge Low-Resolution Survey (4MIDABLE-LR)”. In: *The Messenger* 175, pp. 30–34. DOI: [10 . 18727 / 0722 - 6691 / 5122](https://doi.org/10.18727/0722-6691/5122). arXiv: [1903 . 02469](https://arxiv.org/abs/1903.02469) [[astro-ph.GA](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro-ph)].
- Choudhury, Tirthankar Roy et al. (Jan. 2021). “Cosmic microwave background constraints on a physical model of reionization”. In: *MNRAS* 501.1, pp. L7–L11. DOI: [10 . 1093 / mnrasl / slaa185](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnrasl/slaa185). arXiv: [2007 . 03705](https://arxiv.org/abs/2007.03705) [[astro-ph.CO](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro-ph)].
- Choustikov, Nicholas et al. (Apr. 2023). “The Physics of Indirect Estimators of Lyman Continuum Escape and their Application to High-Redshift JWST

- Galaxies”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2304.08526, arXiv:2304.08526. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2304.08526](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2304.08526). arXiv: [2304.08526](https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.08526) [[astro-ph.GA](#)].
- Christlieb, N. et al. (Mar. 2019). “4MOST Consortium Survey 2: The Milky Way Halo High-Resolution Survey”. In: *The Messenger* 175, pp. 26–29. DOI: [10.18727/0722-6691/5121](https://doi.org/10.18727/0722-6691/5121). arXiv: [1903.02468](https://arxiv.org/abs/1903.02468) [[astro-ph.GA](#)].
- Cioni, M. - R. L. et al. (Mar. 2019). “4MOST Consortium Survey 9: One Thousand and One Magellanic Fields (1001MC)”. In: *The Messenger* 175, pp. 54–57. DOI: [10.18727/0722-6691/5128](https://doi.org/10.18727/0722-6691/5128). arXiv: [1903.02475](https://arxiv.org/abs/1903.02475) [[astro-ph.GA](#)].
- Cuby, Jean Gabriel et al. (July 1998). “Handling atmospheric dispersion and differential refraction effects in large-field multiobject spectroscopic observations”. In: *Optical Astronomical Instrumentation*. Ed. by Sandro D’Odorico. Vol. 3355. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, pp. 36–47. DOI: [10.1117/12.316769](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.316769).
- Cullen, F. et al. (June 2020). “The VANDELS survey: a strong correlation between Ly α equivalent width and stellar metallicity at $3 \leq z \leq 5$ ”. In: *MNRAS* 495.1, pp. 1501–1510. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/staa1260](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa1260). arXiv: [2001.11063](https://arxiv.org/abs/2001.11063) [[astro-ph.GA](#)].
- Cunningham et al. (Jan. 2023). “Assembly and alignment of the 4-metre multi-object spectroscopic telescope wide field corrector”. In: *Journal of Astronomical Telescopes, Instruments, and Systems* 9, 015002, p. 015002. DOI: [10.1117/1.JATIS.9.1.015002](https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JATIS.9.1.015002).
- (Apr. 2024). “C III] λ 1909 emission as an alternative to Ly α in the reionization era: the dependence of C III] and Ly α at $3 \leq z \leq 4$ from the VANDELS survey”. In: *MNRAS*. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stae939](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stae939).
- Curti, Mirko et al. (Apr. 2023). “JADES: Insights on the low-mass end of the mass–metallicity–star-formation rate relation at $3 < z < 10$ from deep JWST/NIRSpec spectroscopy”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2304.08516, arXiv:2304.08516. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2304.08516](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2304.08516). arXiv: [2304.08516](https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.08516) [[astro-ph.GA](#)].

- D'Eugenio, Francesco et al. (Nov. 2023). “JADES: Carbon enrichment 350 Myr after the Big Bang in a gas-rich galaxy”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2311.09908, arXiv:2311.09908. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2311.09908](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2311.09908). arXiv: [2311.09908](https://arxiv.org/abs/2311.09908) [[astro-ph.GA](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro-ph)].
- Dalton et al. (Sept. 2012). “WEAVE: the next generation wide-field spectroscopy facility for the William Herschel Telescope”. In: *Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy IV*. Ed. by Ian S. McLean et al. Vol. 8446. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 84460P, 84460P. DOI: [10.1117/12.925950](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.925950).
- (Aug. 2016). “Final design and progress of WEAVE: the next generation wide-field spectroscopy facility for the William Herschel Telescope”. In: *Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy VI*. Ed. by Christopher J. Evans et al. Vol. 9908. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 99081G, 99081G. DOI: [10.1117/12.2231078](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2231078).
- Dayal, Pratika et al. (July 2020). “Reionization with galaxies and active galactic nuclei”. In: *MNRAS* 495.3, pp. 3065–3078. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/staa1138](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa1138). arXiv: [2001.06021](https://arxiv.org/abs/2001.06021) [[astro-ph.GA](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro-ph)].
- de Jong et al. (Sept. 2012). “4MOST: 4-metre multi-object spectroscopic telescope”. In: *Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy IV*. Ed. by Ian S. McLean et al. Vol. 8446. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 84460T, 84460T. DOI: [10.1117/12.926239](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.926239). arXiv: [1206.6885](https://arxiv.org/abs/1206.6885) [[astro-ph.IM](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro-ph)].
- (Aug. 2016). “4MOST: the 4-metre Multi-Object Spectroscopic Telescope project at preliminary design review”. In: Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series 9908, 99081O. Ed. by Christopher J. Evans et al., 99081O. DOI: [10.1117/12.2232832](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2232832).
- (Aug. 2022). “4MOST: the 4-metre multi-object spectroscopic telescope project in the assembly, integration, and test phase”. In: *Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy IX*. Ed. by Christopher J. Evans et al.

- Vol. 12184. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 1218414, p. 1218414. DOI: [10.1117/12.2628965](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2628965).
- Dey, A. (Jan. 2002). “The Future of Wide-Field Multi-Object Spectroscopy”. In: *Next Generation Wide-Field Multi-Object Spectroscopy*. Ed. by Michael J. I. Brown et al. Vol. 280. Astronomical Society of the Pacific Conference Series, p. 7.
- Dijkstra et al. (Sept. 2006). “Ly α Radiation from Collapsing Protogalaxies. I. Characteristics of the Emergent Spectrum”. In: *ApJ* 649.1, pp. 14–36. DOI: [10.1086/506243](https://doi.org/10.1086/506243). arXiv: [astro-ph/0510407](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0510407) [astro-ph].
- Dijkstra (Oct. 2014). “Ly α Emitting Galaxies as a Probe of Reionisation”. In: 31, e040, e040. DOI: [10.1017/pasa.2014.33](https://doi.org/10.1017/pasa.2014.33). arXiv: [1406.7292](https://arxiv.org/abs/1406.7292) [astro-ph.CO].
- Dijkstra et al. (Sept. 2016). “The Ly α -LyC Connection: Evidence for an Enhanced Contribution of UV-faint Galaxies to Cosmic Reionization”. In: *ApJ* 828.2, 71, p. 71. DOI: [10.3847/0004-637X/828/2/71](https://doi.org/10.3847/0004-637X/828/2/71). arXiv: [1604.08208](https://arxiv.org/abs/1604.08208) [astro-ph.CO].
- Ding, Jiani et al. (Apr. 2017). “Constraining C III] Emission in a Sample of Five Luminous $z = 5.7$ Galaxies”. In: *ApJL* 838.2, L22, p. L22. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/aa6482](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/aa6482). arXiv: [1612.00902](https://arxiv.org/abs/1612.00902) [astro-ph.GA].
- Disseau, Karen et al. (Aug. 2022). “4MOST low resolution spectrograph performances”. In: *Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy IX*. Ed. by Christopher J. Evans et al. Vol. 12184. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 1218479, p. 1218479. DOI: [10.1117/12.2629787](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2629787).
- Doel, Peter et al. (Sept. 2012). “Assembly, alignment, and testing of the DECam wide field corrector optics”. In: *Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy IV*. Ed. by Ian S. McLean et al. Vol. 8446. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 84466F, 84466F. DOI: [10.1117/12.926590](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.926590).
- Draine, Bruce T. (2011). *Physics of the Interstellar and Intergalactic Medium*.

- Drew, J et al. (2010). “Report by the european telescope strategic review committee on Europe’s 2-4m telescopes over the decade to 2020”. In.
- Ellis (2022). *When Galaxies Were Born. The Quest for Cosmic Dawn*.
- Ellis et al. (Jan. 2017). “The Future of Multi-Object Spectroscopy: a ESO Working Group Report”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1701.01976, arXiv:1701.01976. DOI: [10 . 48550 / arXiv . 1701 . 01976](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1701.01976). arXiv: [1701 . 01976](https://arxiv.org/abs/1701.01976) [[astro-ph.IM](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro-ph)].
- Emerson, J. et al. (Sept. 2023). “VIRCAM Operations End at VISTA”. In: *The Messenger* 191, pp. 42–45. DOI: [10.18727/0722-6691/5341](https://doi.org/10.18727/0722-6691/5341).
- Endsley et al. (Sept. 2023). “A JWST/NIRCam study of key contributors to reionization: the star-forming and ionizing properties of UV-faint z 7-8 galaxies”. In: *MNRAS* 524.2, pp. 2312–2330. DOI: [10 . 1093 / mnras / stad1919](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stad1919). arXiv: [2208.14999](https://arxiv.org/abs/2208.14999) [[astro-ph.GA](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro-ph)].
- Endsley, Ryan et al. (June 2023). “The Star-forming and Ionizing Properties of Dwarf z~6-9 Galaxies in JADES: Insights on Bursty Star Formation and Ionized Bubble Growth”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2306.05295, arXiv:2306.05295. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2306.05295](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2306.05295). arXiv: [2306 . 05295](https://arxiv.org/abs/2306.05295) [[astro-ph.GA](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro-ph)].
- Erb et al. (Nov. 2014). “The Ly α Properties of Faint Galaxies at z ~2-3 with Systemic Redshifts and Velocity Dispersions from Keck-MOSFIRE”. In: *ApJ* 795.1, 33, p. 33. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/795/1/33](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/795/1/33). arXiv: [1408 . 3638](https://arxiv.org/abs/1408.3638) [[astro-ph.GA](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro-ph)].
- Erb et al. (Aug. 2010). “Physical Conditions in a Young, Unreddened, Low-metallicity Galaxy at High Redshift”. In: *ApJ* 719.2, pp. 1168–1190. DOI: [10 . 1088 / 0004 - 637X / 719 / 2 / 1168](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/719/2/1168). arXiv: [1006 . 5456](https://arxiv.org/abs/1006.5456) [[astro-ph.CO](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro-ph)].
- Fan, Xiaohui et al. (July 2006). “Constraining the Evolution of the Ionizing Background and the Epoch of Reionization with z~6 Quasars. II. A Sample of 19 Quasars”. In: *AJ* 132.1, pp. 117–136. DOI: [10 . 1086 / 504836](https://doi.org/10.1086/504836). arXiv: [astro-ph/0512082](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0512082) [[astro-ph](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro-ph)].

- Fata, Robert G. et al. (2004). “Mounting large lenses for the MMT’s f/5 wide-field corrector: lessons learned”. In: *Ground-based Instrumentation for Astronomy*. Ed. by Alan F. M. Moorwood et al. Vol. 5492. International Society for Optics and Photonics. SPIE, pp. 553–563. DOI: [10.1117/12.552289](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.552289). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.552289>.
- Feltre, A. et al. (Mar. 2016). “Nuclear activity versus star formation: emission-line diagnostics at ultraviolet and optical wavelengths”. In: *MNRAS* 456.3, pp. 3354–3374. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stv2794](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stv2794). arXiv: [1511.08217](https://arxiv.org/abs/1511.08217) [astro-ph.GA].
- Filippenko, A. V. (Aug. 1982). “The importance of atmospheric differential refraction in spectrophotometry.” In: *PASP* 94, pp. 715–721. DOI: [10.1086/131052](https://doi.org/10.1086/131052).
- Finoguenov, A. et al. (Mar. 2019). “4MOST Consortium Survey 5: eROSITA Galaxy Cluster Redshift Survey”. In: *The Messenger* 175, pp. 39–41. DOI: [10.18727/0722-6691/5124](https://doi.org/10.18727/0722-6691/5124). arXiv: [1903.02471](https://arxiv.org/abs/1903.02471) [astro-ph.CO].
- Fletcher, Thomas J. et al. (June 2019). “The Lyman Continuum Escape Survey: Ionizing Radiation from [O III]-strong Sources at a Redshift of 3.1”. In: *ApJ* 878.2, 87, p. 87. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab2045](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab2045). arXiv: [1806.01741](https://arxiv.org/abs/1806.01741) [astro-ph.GA].
- Flury, Sophia R. et al. (May 2022). “The Low-redshift Lyman Continuum Survey. II. New Insights into LyC Diagnostics”. In: *ApJ* 930.2, 126, p. 126. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ac61e4](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ac61e4). arXiv: [2203.15649](https://arxiv.org/abs/2203.15649) [astro-ph.GA].
- Forrest, Ben et al. (Mar. 2017). “Discovery of Extreme [O III]+H β Emitting Galaxies Tracing an Overdensity at $z \sim 3.5$ in CDF-South”. In: *ApJL* 838.1, L12, p. L12. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/aa653b](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/aa653b). arXiv: [1703.03814](https://arxiv.org/abs/1703.03814) [astro-ph.GA].
- Fujimoto, Seiji et al. (Aug. 2023). “UNCOVER: A NIRSpect Census of Lensed Galaxies at $z=8.50-13.08$ Probing a High AGN Fraction and Ionized Bubbles in the Shadow”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2308.11609, arXiv:2308.11609.

- DOI: [10 . 48550 / arXiv . 2308 . 11609](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2308.11609). arXiv: [2308 . 11609](https://arxiv.org/abs/2308.11609) [[astro-ph.GA](https://arxiv.org/abs/2308.11609)].
- Garaldi, Enrico et al. (May 2019). “Constraining the Tail End of Reionization Using Ly α Transmission Spikes”. In: *ApJ* 876.1, 31, p. 31. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab12dc](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab12dc). arXiv: [1902.07713](https://arxiv.org/abs/1902.07713) [[astro-ph.CO](https://arxiv.org/abs/1902.07713)].
- Garilli, B. et al. (Mar. 2021). “The VANDELS ESO public spectroscopic survey. Final data release of 2087 spectra and spectroscopic measurements”. In: *A&A* 647, A150, A150. DOI: [10 . 1051 / 0004 - 6361 / 202040059](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202040059). arXiv: [2101.07645](https://arxiv.org/abs/2101.07645) [[astro-ph.GA](https://arxiv.org/abs/2101.07645)].
- Gatkine, Pradip et al. (June 2022). “Astronomical spectrographs on a chip — Getting ready for the next-generation telescopes”. In: *American Astronomical Society Meeting #240*. Vol. 54. American Astronomical Society Meeting Abstracts, 337.03, p. 337.03.
- Gilbert, James et al. (Sept. 2012). “Starbugs: all-singing, all-dancing fibre positioning robots”. In: *Modern Technologies in Space- and Ground-based Telescopes and Instrumentation II*. Ed. by Ramón Navarro et al. Vol. 8450. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 84501A, 84501A. DOI: [10 . 1117 / 12 . 924502](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.924502). arXiv: [1311 . 7371](https://arxiv.org/abs/1311.7371) [[astro-ph.IM](https://arxiv.org/abs/1311.7371)].
- Gillingham et al. (July 2014). “A wide field corrector with loss-less and purely passive atmospheric dispersion correction”. In: *Advances in Optical and Mechanical Technologies for Telescopes and Instrumentation*. Ed. by Ramón Navarro et al. Vol. 9151. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 915161, p. 915161. DOI: [10 . 1117 / 12 . 2054707](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2054707). arXiv: [1407.2193](https://arxiv.org/abs/1407.2193) [[astro-ph.IM](https://arxiv.org/abs/1407.2193)].
- Gillingham et al. (Aug. 2000). “Echidna: a multifiber positioner for the Subaru prime focus”. In: *Optical and IR Telescope Instrumentation and Detectors*. Ed. by Masanori Iye et al. Vol. 4008. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, pp. 1395–1403. DOI: [10 . 1117 / 12 . 395458](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.395458).

- Glover, Simon C. O. et al. (Mar. 2012). “Is molecular gas necessary for star formation?” In: *MNRAS* 421.1, pp. 9–19. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.19648.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.19648.x). arXiv: [1105.3073](https://arxiv.org/abs/1105.3073) [astro-ph.GA].
- Goodwin, Michael et al. (July 2010). “Starbugs: focal plane fiber positioning technology”. In: *Modern Technologies in Space- and Ground-based Telescopes and Instrumentation*. Ed. by Eli Atad-Ettinger et al. Vol. 7739. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 77391E, 77391E. DOI: [10.1117/12.856777](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.856777).
- Guaita, L. et al. (Aug. 2020). “The VANDELS survey: Discovery of massive overdensities of galaxies at $z \lesssim 2$. Location of Ly α -emitting galaxies with respect to environment”. In: *A&A* 640, A107, A107. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201935855](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201935855). arXiv: [2007.12314](https://arxiv.org/abs/2007.12314) [astro-ph.GA].
- Haiman et al. (Jan. 1999). “Reionization of the Intergalactic Medium and its Effect on the CMB”. In: *Microwave Foregrounds*. Ed. by A. de Oliveira-Costa et al. Vol. 181. Astronomical Society of the Pacific Conference Series, p. 227. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.astro-ph/9902311](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.astro-ph/9902311). arXiv: [astro-ph/9902311](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/9902311) [astro-ph].
- Haiman (Sept. 2002). “The Detectability of High-Redshift Ly α Emission Lines prior to the Reionization of the Universe”. In: *ApJL* 576.1, pp. L1–L4. DOI: [10.1086/343101](https://doi.org/10.1086/343101). arXiv: [astro-ph/0205410](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0205410) [astro-ph].
- Harikane et al. (Dec. 2023). “A JWST/NIRSpec First Census of Broad-line AGNs at $z = 4-7$: Detection of 10 Faint AGNs with $M_{BH} 10^6-10^8 M_{\odot}$ and Their Host Galaxy Properties”. In: *ApJ* 959.1, 39, p. 39. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ad029e](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ad029e). arXiv: [2303.11946](https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.11946) [astro-ph.GA].
- Hashimoto, Takuya et al. (May 2018). “The onset of star formation 250 million years after the Big Bang”. In: *Nature* 557.7705, pp. 392–395. DOI: [10.1038/s41586-018-0117-z](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-018-0117-z). arXiv: [1805.05966](https://arxiv.org/abs/1805.05966) [astro-ph.GA].
- Hayes et al. (Mar. 2010). “Escape of about five per cent of Lyman- α photons from high-redshift star-forming galaxies”. In: *Nature* 464.7288, pp. 562–565. DOI: [10.1038/nature08881](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature08881). arXiv: [1002.4876](https://arxiv.org/abs/1002.4876) [astro-ph.CO].

- Hayes et al. (Mar. 2023). “On the sizes of ionized bubbles around the highest redshift galaxies. Spectral shapes of the Lyman-alpha emission from galaxies III”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2303.03160, arXiv:2303.03160. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2303.03160](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2303.03160). arXiv: [2303.03160](https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.03160) [astro-ph.GA].
- Helmi, A. et al. (Mar. 2019). “4MOST Consortium Survey 1: The Milky Way Halo Low-Resolution Survey”. In: *The Messenger* 175, pp. 23–25. DOI: [10.18727/0722-6691/5120](https://doi.org/10.18727/0722-6691/5120). arXiv: [1903.02467](https://arxiv.org/abs/1903.02467) [astro-ph.GA].
- Hill et al. (Dec. 1980). “Multiple object spectroscopy: the medusa spectrograph.” In: *ApJL* 242, pp. L69–L72. DOI: [10.1086/183405](https://doi.org/10.1086/183405).
- (Jan. 1986). “Deployment of the MX spectrometer.” In: *Instrumentation in astronomy VI*. Ed. by David L. Crawford. Vol. 627. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, pp. 303–320. DOI: [10.1117/12.968104](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.968104).
- Hill, Alexis et al. (2022). “MSE: Instrumentation for a massively multiplexed spectroscopic survey facility”. In: *Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy IX*. Ed. by Christopher J. Evans et al. Vol. 12184. International Society for Optics and Photonics. SPIE, 121841B. DOI: [10.1117/12.2630529](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2630529). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2630529>.
- Hoag, A. et al. (Sept. 2019). “Constraining Lyman-alpha spatial offsets at $3 < z < 5.5$ from VANDELS slit spectroscopy”. In: *MNRAS* 488.1, pp. 706–719. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stz1768](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stz1768). arXiv: [1905.09467](https://arxiv.org/abs/1905.09467) [astro-ph.GA].
- Honscheid, K. et al. (2008). *The Dark Energy Camera (DECam)*. DOI: [10.48550/ARXIV.0810.3600](https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.0810.3600). URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/0810.3600>.
- Hopkins, Philip F. et al. (Apr. 2008). “A Cosmological Framework for the Co-evolution of Quasars, Supermassive Black Holes, and Elliptical Galaxies. I. Galaxy Mergers and Quasar Activity”. In: *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series* 175.2, pp. 356–389. ISSN: 1538-4365. DOI: [10.1086/524362](https://doi.org/10.1086/524362). URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/524362>.

- Hsiao, Tiger Yu-Yang et al. (May 2023). “JWST NIRSpec spectroscopy of the triply-lensed $z = 10.17$ galaxy MACS0647–JD”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2305.03042, arXiv:2305.03042. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2305.03042](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2305.03042). arXiv: [2305.03042](https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.03042) [astro-ph.GA].
- Hubble, Edwin (Mar. 1929). “A Relation between Distance and Radial Velocity among Extra-Galactic Nebulae”. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Science* 15.3, pp. 168–173. DOI: [10.1073/pnas.15.3.168](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.15.3.168).
- Hunter, J. D. (2007). “Matplotlib: A 2D graphics environment”. In: *Computing in Science & Engineering* 9.3, pp. 90–95. DOI: [10.1109/MCSE.2007.55](https://doi.org/10.1109/MCSE.2007.55).
- Hutchison, Taylor A. et al. (July 2019). “Near-infrared Spectroscopy of Galaxies During Reionization: Measuring C III] in a Galaxy at $z = 7.5$ ”. In: *ApJ* 879.2, 70, p. 70. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab22a2](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab22a2). arXiv: [1905.08812](https://arxiv.org/abs/1905.08812) [astro-ph.GA].
- Inoue, Akio K. et al. (Aug. 2014). “An updated analytic model for attenuation by the intergalactic medium”. In: *MNRAS* 442.2, pp. 1805–1820. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stu936](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stu936). arXiv: [1402.0677](https://arxiv.org/abs/1402.0677) [astro-ph.CO].
- Izotov, Y. I. et al. (May 2021). “Lyman continuum leakage from low-mass galaxies with $M_* \lesssim 10^8 M_\odot$ ”. In: *MNRAS* 503.2, pp. 1734–1752. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stab612](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stab612). arXiv: [2103.01514](https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.01514) [astro-ph.GA].
- Johns, Matt et al. (July 2014). “Design of the Giant Magellan Telescope”. In: *Ground-based and Airborne Telescopes V*. Ed. by Larry M. Stepp et al. Vol. 9145. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 91451F, 91451F. DOI: [10.1117/12.2057286](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2057286).
- Jonas, Graeme et al. (Dec. 2020). “Cementing and testing of the 4MOST WFC/ADC doublets”. In: *Advances in Optical and Mechanical Technologies for Telescopes and Instrumentation IV*. Ed. by Ramón Navarro et al. Vol. 11451. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 114513A, 114513A. DOI: [10.1117/12.2561953](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2561953).
- Jones, Gareth C. et al. (June 2023). “JADES: The emergence and evolution of Ly-alpha emission & constraints on the IGM neutral fraction”. In: *arXiv e-prints*,

- arXiv:2306.02471, arXiv:2306.02471. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2306.02471](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2306.02471). arXiv: [2306.02471](https://arxiv.org/abs/2306.02471) [astro-ph.GA].
- Jung, Intae et al. (Apr. 2023). “CEERS: Diversity of Lyman-Alpha Emitters during the Epoch of Reionization”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2304.05385, arXiv:2304.05385. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2304.05385](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2304.05385). arXiv: [2304.05385](https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.05385) [astro-ph.GA].
- Katz, Harley et al. (Jan. 2023). “First insights into the ISM at $z > 8$ with JWST: possible physical implications of a high [O III] $\lambda 4363$ /[O III] $\lambda 5007$ ”. In: *MNRAS* 518.1, pp. 592–603. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stac2657](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stac2657). arXiv: [2207.13693](https://arxiv.org/abs/2207.13693) [astro-ph.GA].
- Kimura, Masahiko et al. (Oct. 2010). “Fibre Multi-Object Spectrograph (FMOS) for the Subaru Telescope”. In: 62, pp. 1135–1147. DOI: [10.1093/pasj/62.5.1135](https://doi.org/10.1093/pasj/62.5.1135).
- Kuehn, Kyler et al. (July 2014). “TAIPAN: optical spectroscopy with StarBugs”. In: *Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy V*. Ed. by Suzanne K. Ramsay et al. Vol. 9147. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 914710, p. 914710. DOI: [10.1117/12.2055677](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2055677).
- Kuhlen, Michael et al. (June 2012). “Concordance models of reionization: implications for faint galaxies and escape fraction evolution”. In: *MNRAS* 423.1, pp. 862–876. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2012.20924.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2012.20924.x). arXiv: [1201.0757](https://arxiv.org/abs/1201.0757) [astro-ph.CO].
- Kulkarni, Shrinivas R. et al. (1988). “Neutral hydrogen and the diffuse interstellar medium.” In: *Galactic and Extragalactic Radio Astronomy*. Ed. by K. I. Kellermann et al., pp. 95–153.
- Le Fèvre, O. et al. (Mar. 2003). “Commissioning and performances of the VLT-VIMOS instrument”. In: *Instrument Design and Performance for Optical/Infrared Ground-based Telescopes*. Ed. by Masanori Iye et al. Vol. 4841. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, pp. 1670–1681. DOI: [10.1117/12.460959](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.460959).

- Le Fèvre, O. et al. (May 2019). “The VIMOS Ultra-Deep Survey: evidence for AGN feedback in galaxies with CIII]- λ 1908 Å emission 10.8 to 12.5 Gyr ago”. In: *A&A* 625, A51, A51. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201732197](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201732197). arXiv: [1710.10715](https://arxiv.org/abs/1710.10715) [astro-ph.GA].
- Llerena, M. et al. (July 2021). “The VANDELS survey: global properties of CIII] λ 1908Å emitting star-forming galaxies at $z\sim 3$ ”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2107.00660, arXiv:2107.00660. arXiv: [2107.00660](https://arxiv.org/abs/2107.00660) [astro-ph.GA].
- Luo, B. et al. (Jan. 2017). “The Chandra Deep Field-South Survey: 7 Ms Source Catalogs”. In: *ApJSS* 228.1, 2, p. 2. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4365/228/1/2](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4365/228/1/2). arXiv: [1611.03501](https://arxiv.org/abs/1611.03501) [astro-ph.GA].
- Mainieri, Vincenzo et al. (Mar. 2024). “The Wide-field Spectroscopic Telescope (WST) Science White Paper”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2403.05398, arXiv:2403.05398. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2403.05398](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2403.05398). arXiv: [2403.05398](https://arxiv.org/abs/2403.05398) [astro-ph.IM].
- Maiolino et al. (Aug. 2023). “JADES. The diverse population of infant Black Holes at $4 < z < 11$: merging, tiny, poor, but mighty”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2308.01230, arXiv:2308.01230. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2308.01230](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2308.01230). arXiv: [2308.01230](https://arxiv.org/abs/2308.01230) [astro-ph.GA].
- Maji, Moupiya et al. (July 2022). “Predicting Lyman-continuum emission of galaxies using their physical and Lyman-alpha emission properties”. In: *A&A* 663, A66, A66. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/202142740](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202142740). arXiv: [2204.02440](https://arxiv.org/abs/2204.02440) [astro-ph.GA].
- Marchi, F. et al. (Nov. 2019). “The VANDELS survey: the role of ISM and galaxy physical properties in the escape of Ly α emission in $z \sim 3.5$ star-forming galaxies”. In: *A&A* 631, A19, A19. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201935495](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201935495). arXiv: [1903.08593](https://arxiv.org/abs/1903.08593) [astro-ph.GA].
- Mason, Charlotte A. et al. (Apr. 2018). “Beacons into the Cosmic Dark Ages: Boosted Transmission of Ly α from UV Bright Galaxies at $z \gtrsim 7$ ”. In: *ApJL* 857.2, L11, p. L11. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/aabbab](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/aabbab). arXiv: [1801.01891](https://arxiv.org/abs/1801.01891) [astro-ph.CO].

- Matsuoka, Yoshiki et al. (June 2023). “Quasar Luminosity Function at $z = 7$ ”. In: *ApJL* 949.2, L42, p. L42. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/acd69f](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/acd69f). arXiv: [2305.11225](https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.11225) [astro-ph.GA].
- McConnachie, Alan et al. (May 2016). “The Detailed Science Case for the Maunakea Spectroscopic Explorer: the Composition and Dynamics of the Faint Universe”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1606.00043, arXiv:1606.00043. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.1606.00043](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1606.00043). arXiv: [1606.00043](https://arxiv.org/abs/1606.00043) [astro-ph.IM].
- McGreer, Ian D. et al. (Feb. 2015). “Model-independent evidence in favour of an end to reionization by $z \approx 6$ ”. In: *MNRAS* 447.1, pp. 499–505. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stu2449](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stu2449). arXiv: [1411.5375](https://arxiv.org/abs/1411.5375) [astro-ph.CO].
- McLure, R. J. et al. (Sept. 2018). “The VANDELS ESO public spectroscopic survey”. In: *MNRAS* 479.1, pp. 25–42. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/sty1213](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/sty1213). arXiv: [1803.07414](https://arxiv.org/abs/1803.07414) [astro-ph.GA].
- Merloni, A. et al. (Mar. 2019). “4MOST Consortium Survey 6: Active Galactic Nuclei”. In: *The Messenger* 175, pp. 42–45. DOI: [10.18727/0722-6691/5125](https://doi.org/10.18727/0722-6691/5125). arXiv: [1903.02472](https://arxiv.org/abs/1903.02472) [astro-ph.GA].
- Mesinger, Andrei et al. (Jan. 2015). “Can the intergalactic medium cause a rapid drop in Ly α emission at $z \lesssim 6$?” In: *MNRAS* 446.1, pp. 566–577. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stu2089](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stu2089). arXiv: [1406.6373](https://arxiv.org/abs/1406.6373) [astro-ph.CO].
- Moore, Anna M. et al. (Mar. 2003). “Spine development for the Echidna fiber positioner”. In: *Instrument Design and Performance for Optical/Infrared Ground-based Telescopes*. Ed. by Masanori Iye et al. Vol. 4841. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, pp. 1429–1439. DOI: [10.1117/12.462333](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.462333).
- Morris, Simon et al. (July 2018). “The ELT-MOS (MOSAIC): towards the construction phase”. In: *Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy VII*. Ed. by Christopher J. Evans et al. Vol. 10702. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 107021W, 107021W. DOI: [10.1117/12.2311430](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2311430). arXiv: [1807.00720](https://arxiv.org/abs/1807.00720) [astro-ph.IM].

- Naidu, Rohan P. et al. (Mar. 2022). “The synchrony of production and escape: half the bright Ly α emitters at $z \approx 2$ have Lyman continuum escape fractions ≈ 50 per cent”. In: *MNRAS* 510.3, pp. 4582–4607. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stab3601](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stab3601). arXiv: [2110.11961](https://arxiv.org/abs/2110.11961) [astro-ph.GA].
- Nakajima, K. et al. (June 2018a). “The mean ultraviolet spectrum of a representative sample of faint $z \sim 3$ Lyman alpha emitters”. In: *MNRAS* 477.2, pp. 2098–2111. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/sty750](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/sty750). arXiv: [1801.03085](https://arxiv.org/abs/1801.03085) [astro-ph.GA].
- Nakajima, K. et al. (May 2018b). “The VIMOS Ultra Deep Survey: Nature, ISM properties, and ionizing spectra of CIII] λ 1909 emitters at $z = 2-4$ ”. In: *A&A* 612, A94, A94. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201731935](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201731935). arXiv: [1709.03990](https://arxiv.org/abs/1709.03990) [astro-ph.GA].
- Onoue, Masafusa et al. (Sept. 2017). “Minor Contribution of Quasars to Ionizing Photon Budget at $z \sim 6$: Update on Quasar Luminosity Function at the Faint End with Subaru/Suprime-Cam”. In: *The Astrophysical Journal* 847.2, p. L15. ISSN: 2041-8213. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/aa8cc6](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/aa8cc6). URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/aa8cc6>.
- Osterbrock, Donald E. et al. (2006). *Astrophysics of gaseous nebulae and active galactic nuclei*.
- Pahl, Anthony J. et al. (May 2023). “The connection between the escape of ionizing radiation and galaxy properties at $z \sim 3$ in the Keck Lyman continuum spectroscopic survey”. In: *MNRAS* 521.3, pp. 3247–3259. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stad774](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stad774). arXiv: [2210.16697](https://arxiv.org/abs/2210.16697) [astro-ph.GA].
- Parry et al. (Jan. 1986). “An automated multiobject fibre optic coupler for the Anglo-Australian Telescope.” In: *Instrumentation in astronomy VI*. Ed. by David L. Crawford. Vol. 627. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, pp. 118–124. DOI: [10.1117/12.968080](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.968080).
- (Jan. 1988). “AUTO FIB Current Status”. In: *Fiber Optics in Astronomy*. Ed. by Samuel C. Barden. Vol. 3. Astronomical Society of the Pacific Conference Series, p. 93.

- Pentericci et al. (Dec. 2011). “Spectroscopic Confirmation of $z \sim 7$ Lyman Break Galaxies: Probing the Earliest Galaxies and the Epoch of Reionization”. In: *ApJ* 743.2, 132, p. 132. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/743/2/132](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/743/2/132). arXiv: [1107.1376](https://arxiv.org/abs/1107.1376) [astro-ph.CO].
- Pentericci et al. (Sept. 2018). “The VANDELs ESO public spectroscopic survey: Observations and first data release”. In: *A&A* 616, A174, A174. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201833047](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201833047). arXiv: [1803.07373](https://arxiv.org/abs/1803.07373) [astro-ph.GA].
- Planck Collaboration et al. (Sept. 2016). “Planck 2015 results. X. Diffuse component separation: Foreground maps”. In: *A&A* 594, A10, A10. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201525967](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201525967). arXiv: [1502.01588](https://arxiv.org/abs/1502.01588) [astro-ph.CO].
- Prieto-Lyon, Gonzalo et al. (Apr. 2023). “Early Results from GLASS-JWST XXIII: The transmission of Lyman-alpha from UV-faint $z \sim 3-6$ galaxies”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2304.02666, arXiv:2304.02666. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2304.02666](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2304.02666). arXiv: [2304.02666](https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.02666) [astro-ph.GA].
- Pritchard, Jonathan R. et al. (Aug. 2012). “21 cm cosmology in the 21st century”. In: *Reports on Progress in Physics* 75.8, 086901, p. 086901. DOI: [10.1088/0034-4885/75/8/086901](https://doi.org/10.1088/0034-4885/75/8/086901). arXiv: [1109.6012](https://arxiv.org/abs/1109.6012) [astro-ph.CO].
- Ravindranath, Swara et al. (June 2020). “The Semiforbidden C III] λ 1909 Emission in the Rest-ultraviolet Spectra of Green Pea Galaxies”. In: *ApJ* 896.2, 170, p. 170. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab91a5](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab91a5). arXiv: [2005.05399](https://arxiv.org/abs/2005.05399) [astro-ph.GA].
- Richard, J. et al. (Mar. 2019). “4MOST Consortium Survey 8: Cosmology Redshift Survey (CRS)”. In: *The Messenger* 175, pp. 50–53. DOI: [10.18727/0722-6691/5127](https://doi.org/10.18727/0722-6691/5127). arXiv: [1903.02474](https://arxiv.org/abs/1903.02474) [astro-ph.CO].
- Rigby, J. R. et al. (Nov. 2015). “C III] Emission in Star-forming Galaxies Near and Far”. In: *ApJL* 814.1, L6, p. L6. DOI: [10.1088/2041-8205/814/1/L6](https://doi.org/10.1088/2041-8205/814/1/L6). arXiv: [1510.02542](https://arxiv.org/abs/1510.02542) [astro-ph.GA].

- Robertson et al. (May 2013). “New Constraints on Cosmic Reionization from the 2012 Hubble Ultra Deep Field Campaign”. In: *ApJ* 768.1, 71, p. 71. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/768/1/71](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/768/1/71). arXiv: [1301.1228](https://arxiv.org/abs/1301.1228) [astro-ph.CO].
- Robertson, B.E. et al. (Apr. 2015). “Cosmic Reionization and Early Star-forming Galaxies: A Joint Analysis of New Constraints from Planck and the Hubble Space Telescope”. In: *ApJL* 802.2, L19, p. L19. DOI: [10.1088/2041-8205/802/2/L19](https://doi.org/10.1088/2041-8205/802/2/L19). arXiv: [1502.02024](https://arxiv.org/abs/1502.02024) [astro-ph.CO].
- Roy, Namrata et al. (July 2023). “Early Results from GLASS-JWST. XXII. Rest-frame UV-Optical Spectral Properties of Ly α Emitting Galaxies at $3 < z < 6$ ”. In: *ApJL* 952.1, L14, p. L14. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/acdbce](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/acdbce). arXiv: [2304.01437](https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.01437) [astro-ph.GA].
- Salvador-Solé, Eduard et al. (Jan. 2017). “Constraining the Epoch of Reionization from the Observed Properties of the High- z Universe”. In: *ApJ* 834.1, 49, p. 49. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/834/1/49](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/834/1/49). arXiv: [1611.02290](https://arxiv.org/abs/1611.02290) [astro-ph.CO].
- Sampson, R. A. (May 1913). “On correcting the field of a Newtonian telescope”. In: *MNRAS* 73, pp. 524–527. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/73.7.524](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/73.7.524).
- Sanders, Gary H. (June 2013). “The Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT): An International Observatory”. In: *Journal of Astrophysics and Astronomy* 34.2, pp. 81–86. DOI: [10.1007/s12036-013-9169-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12036-013-9169-5).
- Santos, Michael R. (Apr. 2004). “Probing reionization with Lyman α emission lines”. In: *MNRAS* 349.3, pp. 1137–1152. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2004.07594.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2004.07594.x). arXiv: [astro-ph/0308196](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0308196) [astro-ph].
- Saunders, Will et al. (July 2014). “Prime focus wide-field corrector designs with lossless atmospheric dispersion correction”. In: *Advances in Optical and Mechanical Technologies for Telescopes and Instrumentation*. Ed. by Ramón Navarro et al. Vol. 9151. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 91511M, p. 91511M. DOI: [10.1117/12.2055662](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2055662). arXiv: [1406.4168](https://arxiv.org/abs/1406.4168) [astro-ph.IM].

- Saviauk, Allar et al. (July 2014). “The fiber positioner for 4MOST: exploration of an alternative R- θ design”. In: *Advances in Optical and Mechanical Technologies for Telescopes and Instrumentation*. Ed. by Ramón Navarro et al. Vol. 9151. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 91514Y, 91514Y. DOI: [10.1117/12.2056289](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2056289).
- Saxena et al. (Apr. 2020). “The properties of He II λ 1640 emitters at $z \sim 2.5$ -5 from the VANDELS survey”. In: *A&A* 636, A47, A47. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201937170](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201937170). arXiv: [1911.09999](https://arxiv.org/abs/1911.09999) [astro-ph.GA].
- (Mar. 2022). “No strong dependence of Lyman continuum leakage on physical properties of star-forming galaxies at $\lesssim z \lesssim 3.5$ ”. In: *MNRAS* 511.1, pp. 120–138. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stab3728](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stab3728). arXiv: [2109.03662](https://arxiv.org/abs/2109.03662) [astro-ph.GA].
- (Feb. 2023). “JADES: Discovery of extremely high equivalent width Lyman-alpha emission from a faint galaxy within an ionized bubble at $z=7.3$ ”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2302.12805, arXiv:2302.12805. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2302.12805](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2302.12805). arXiv: [2302.12805](https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.12805) [astro-ph.GA].
- Saxena et al. (Apr. 2024). “JADES: The production and escape of ionizing photons from faint Lyman-alpha emitters in the epoch of reionization”. In: *A&A* 684, A84, A84. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/202347132](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202347132). arXiv: [2306.04536](https://arxiv.org/abs/2306.04536) [astro-ph.GA].
- Schaerer, D. et al. (Aug. 2018). “Intense C III] $\lambda\lambda$ 1907,1909 emission from a strong Lyman continuum emitting galaxy”. In: *A&A* 616, L14, p. L14. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201833823](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201833823). arXiv: [1808.03059](https://arxiv.org/abs/1808.03059) [astro-ph.GA].
- Schlegel, David J. et al. (Sept. 2022). “A Spectroscopic Road Map for Cosmic Frontier: DESI, DESI-II, Stage-5”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2209.03585, arXiv:2209.03585. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2209.03585](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2209.03585). arXiv: [2209.03585](https://arxiv.org/abs/2209.03585) [astro-ph.CO].
- Schubnell, Michael et al. (July 2018). “DESI fiber positioner testing and performance”. In: *Advances in Optical and Mechanical Technologies for Telescopes*

- and Instrumentation III*. Ed. by Ramón Navarro et al. Vol. 10706. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 107062A, 107062A. DOI: [10.1117/12.2311573](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2311573).
- Seifert, W. et al. (Aug. 2016). “4MOST: the high-resolution spectrograph”. In: *Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy VI*. Ed. by Christopher J. Evans et al. Vol. 9908. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 990890, p. 990890. DOI: [10.1117/12.2233252](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2233252).
- Shapley, Alice E. et al. (May 2003). “Rest-Frame Ultraviolet Spectra of z-3 Lyman Break Galaxies”. In: *ApJ* 588.1, pp. 65–89. DOI: [10.1086/373922](https://doi.org/10.1086/373922). arXiv: [astro-ph/0301230](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0301230) [astro-ph].
- Sheinis, Andrew et al. (Oct. 2023). “The Maunakea Spectroscopic Explorer: Thousands of fibers, infinite possibilities”. In: *Astronomische Nachrichten* 344, e20230108, e20230108. DOI: [10.1002/asna.20230108](https://doi.org/10.1002/asna.20230108). arXiv: [2307.07667](https://arxiv.org/abs/2307.07667) [astro-ph.IM].
- Simmonds, C. et al. (Jan. 2024). “Low-mass bursty galaxies in JADES efficiently produce ionizing photons and could represent the main drivers of reionization”. In: *MNRAS* 527.3, pp. 6139–6157. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stad3605](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stad3605). arXiv: [2310.01112](https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.01112) [astro-ph.GA].
- Skelton, Rosalind E. et al. (Oct. 2014). “3D-HST WFC3-selected Photometric Catalogs in the Five CANDELS/3D-HST Fields: Photometry, Photometric Redshifts, and Stellar Masses”. In: *ApJSS* 214.2, 24, p. 24. DOI: [10.1088/0067-0049/214/2/24](https://doi.org/10.1088/0067-0049/214/2/24). arXiv: [1403.3689](https://arxiv.org/abs/1403.3689) [astro-ph.GA].
- Smedley, Scott et al. (July 2018). “Performance of the first production-ready actuators for the 4MOST-AESOP fiber positioner”. In: *Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy VII*. Ed. by Christopher J. Evans et al. Vol. 10702. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 107027Z, 107027Z. DOI: [10.1117/12.2312863](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2312863).
- Spitzer, Lyman (1978). *Physical processes in the interstellar medium*. DOI: [10.1002/9783527617722](https://doi.org/10.1002/9783527617722).

- Stark et al. (Dec. 2014). “Ultraviolet emission lines in young low-mass galaxies at $z \simeq 2$: physical properties and implications for studies at $z \lesssim 7$ ”. In: *MNRAS* 445.3, pp. 3200–3220. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stu1618](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stu1618). arXiv: [1408.1420](https://arxiv.org/abs/1408.1420) [astro-ph.GA].
- (June 2015). “Spectroscopic detections of C III] $\lambda 1909$ Å at $z \simeq 6-7$: a new probe of early star-forming galaxies and cosmic reionization”. In: *MNRAS* 450.2, pp. 1846–1855. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stv688](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stv688). arXiv: [1408.3649](https://arxiv.org/abs/1408.3649) [astro-ph.GA].
- (Jan. 2017). “Ly α and C III] emission in $z = 7-9$ Galaxies: accelerated reionization around luminous star-forming systems?” In: *MNRAS* 464.1, pp. 469–479. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stw2233](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stw2233). arXiv: [1606.01304](https://arxiv.org/abs/1606.01304) [astro-ph.GA].
- Stratman, Caroline M. S. et al. (Oct. 2016). “The FourStar Galaxy Evolution Survey (ZFOURGE): Ultraviolet to Far-infrared Catalogs, Medium-bandwidth Photometric Redshifts with Improved Accuracy, Stellar Masses, and Confirmation of Quiescent Galaxies to $z \sim 3.5$ ”. In: *ApJ* 830.1, 51, p. 51. DOI: [10.3847/0004-637X/830/1/51](https://doi.org/10.3847/0004-637X/830/1/51). arXiv: [1608.07579](https://arxiv.org/abs/1608.07579) [astro-ph.GA].
- Sutherland, Will et al. (Mar. 2015). “The Visible and Infrared Survey Telescope for Astronomy (VISTA): Design, technical overview, and performance”. In: *A&A* 575, A25, A25. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201424973](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201424973). arXiv: [1409.4780](https://arxiv.org/abs/1409.4780) [astro-ph.IM].
- Swann, E. et al. (Mar. 2019). “4MOST Consortium Survey 10: The Time-Domain Extragalactic Survey (TiDES)”. In: *The Messenger* 175, pp. 58–61. DOI: [10.18727/0722-6691/5129](https://doi.org/10.18727/0722-6691/5129). arXiv: [1903.02476](https://arxiv.org/abs/1903.02476) [astro-ph.IM].
- Tacchella, Sandro et al. (Mar. 2022). “On the Stellar Populations of Galaxies at $z = 9-11$: The Growth of Metals and Stellar Mass at Early Times”. In: *ApJ* 927.2, 170, p. 170. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ac4cad](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ac4cad). arXiv: [2111.05351](https://arxiv.org/abs/2111.05351) [astro-ph.GA].

- Tang, Mengtao et al. (Jan. 2023). “JWST/NIRSpec Spectroscopy of $z = 7 - 9$ Star Forming Galaxies with CEERS: New Insight into Bright Ly α Emitters in Ionized Bubbles”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2301.07072, arXiv:2301.07072. DOI: [10 . 48550 / arXiv . 2301 . 07072](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2301.07072). arXiv: [2301 . 07072](https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.07072) [[astro-ph.GA](https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.07072)].
- Taylor, M. B. (Dec. 2005). “TOPCAT & STIL: Starlink Table/VOTable Processing Software”. In: *Astronomical Society of the Pacific Conference Series* 347. Ed. by P. Shopbell et al., p. 29.
- Tennyson, Jonathan (2011). *Astronomical Spectroscopy*. 2nd. WORLD SCIENTIFIC. DOI: [10.1142/7574](https://doi.org/10.1142/7574). eprint: <https://www.worldscientific.com/doi/pdf/10.1142/7574>. URL: <https://www.worldscientific.com/doi/abs/10.1142/7574>.
- Terebizh, V. Yu. (Aug. 2011). “New designs of survey telescopes”. In: *Astronomische Nachrichten* 332.7, pp. 714–742. DOI: [10.1002/asna.201111576](https://doi.org/10.1002/asna.201111576).
- The Pandas Development Team (Feb. 2020). “pandas-dev/pandas: Pandas”. Version latest. In: DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3509134](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3509134). URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3509134>.
- Topping, Michael W. et al. (Jan. 2024). “Metal-poor star formation at $z > 6$ with JWST: new insight into hard radiation fields and nitrogen enrichment on 20 pc scales”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2401.08764, arXiv:2401.08764. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2401.08764](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2401.08764). arXiv: [2401.08764](https://arxiv.org/abs/2401.08764) [[astro-ph.GA](https://arxiv.org/abs/2401.08764)].
- Trapp, A. C. et al. (Oct. 2023). “Lyman α emitters in ionized bubbles: constraining the environment and ionized fraction”. In: *MNRAS* 524.4, pp. 5891–5903. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stad2228](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stad2228). arXiv: [2210.06504](https://arxiv.org/abs/2210.06504) [[astro-ph.CO](https://arxiv.org/abs/2210.06504)].
- Turon, Catherine (2008). “Gaia in the European context”. In: *SF2A-2008*, p. 43.
- Vanzella, E. et al. (Oct. 2023). “An extremely metal-poor star complex in the reionization era: Approaching Population III stars with JWST”. In: *A&A* 678, A173, A173. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/202346981](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202346981). arXiv: [2305.14413](https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.14413) [[astro-ph.GA](https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.14413)].

- Verhamme et al. (Dec. 2006). “3D Ly α radiation transfer. I. Understanding Ly α line profile morphologies”. In: *A&A* 460.2, pp. 397–413. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361:20065554](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20065554).
- (June 2015). “Using Lyman- α to detect galaxies that leak Lyman continuum”. In: *A&A* 578, A7, A7. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201423978](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201423978). arXiv: [1404.2958](https://arxiv.org/abs/1404.2958) [[astro-ph.GA](#)].
- (Jan. 2017). “Lyman- α spectral properties of five newly discovered Lyman continuum emitters”. In: *A&A* 597, A13, A13. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201629264](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201629264). arXiv: [1609.03477](https://arxiv.org/abs/1609.03477) [[astro-ph.GA](#)].
- Watson, F. G. (Aug. 1983). “Multi-Object Spectroscopy with Optical Fibres”. In: *Journal of the British Astronomical Association* 93, pp. 193–199.
- WavesSurvey (2016). URL: <https://wavesurvey.org/project/facilityinstrument/aesop/>.
- Weisz, Daniel R. et al. (July 2017). “Local Group ultra-faint dwarf galaxies in the reionization era”. In: *MNRAS* 469.1, pp. L83–L88. DOI: [10.1093/mnras1/slx043](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras1/slx043). arXiv: [1702.06129](https://arxiv.org/abs/1702.06129) [[astro-ph.GA](#)].
- Willott, Chris J. et al. (July 2015). “Star Formation and the Interstellar Medium in $z \lesssim 6$ UV-luminous Lyman-break Galaxies”. In: *ApJ* 807.2, 180, p. 180. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/807/2/180](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/807/2/180). arXiv: [1504.05875](https://arxiv.org/abs/1504.05875) [[astro-ph.GA](#)].
- Winkler, Roland et al. (Dec. 2020). “The instrumental profile of the 4MOST facility”. In: *Modeling, Systems Engineering, and Project Management for Astronomy IX*. Ed. by George Z. Angeli et al. Vol. 11450. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 114502K, 114502K. DOI: [10.1117/12.2562998](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2562998).
- Witstok, Joris et al. (June 2023). “Inside the bubble: exploring the environments of reionisation-era Lyman- α emitting galaxies with JADES and FRESCO”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2306.04627, arXiv:2306.04627. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2306.04627](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2306.04627). arXiv: [2306.04627](https://arxiv.org/abs/2306.04627) [[astro-ph.GA](#)].

- Witten, Callum et al. (Jan. 2024). “Deciphering Lyman- α emission deep into the epoch of reionization”. In: *Nature Astronomy*. DOI: [10.1038/s41550-023-02179-3](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41550-023-02179-3). arXiv: [2303.16225](https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.16225) [astro-ph.GA].
- Wynne, C. G. (Nov. 1968). “Corrector Systems for Cassegrain Telescopes”. In: 7.11, 2326₁. DOI: [10.1364/AO.7.2326_1](https://doi.org/10.1364/AO.7.2326_1).
- Xing, Xiaozheng et al. (Aug. 1998). “Parallel controllable optical fiber positioning system for LAMOST”. In: *Advanced Technology Optical/IR Telescopes VI*. Ed. by Larry M. Stepp. Vol. 3352. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, pp. 839–849. DOI: [10.1117/12.319309](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.319309).
- Zahn, O. et al. (Sept. 2012). “Cosmic Microwave Background Constraints on the Duration and Timing of Reionization from the South Pole Telescope”. In: *ApJ* 756.1, 65, p. 65. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/756/1/65](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/756/1/65). arXiv: [1111.6386](https://arxiv.org/abs/1111.6386) [astro-ph.CO].
- Zeeuw, Pieter Timotheus de et al. (2007). *A science vision for european astronomy*. ASTRONET.
- Zhang et al. (Oct. 2022). “Conceptual Design of the Optical System of the 6.5m Wide Field MULTiplexed Survey Telescope with Excellent Image Quality”. In: *SpringerOpen*. DOI: [10.21203/rs.3.rs-2136738/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2136738/v1). URL: <https://photonix.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s43074-023-00094-4#citeas>.
- (Mar. 2024). “The Calibration of theta-phi Fiber Positioners Based on the Differential Evolution Algorithm”. In: *AJ* 167.3, 93, p. 93. DOI: [10.3847/1538-3881/ad1b4d](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ad1b4d).
- Zitrin, Adi et al. (Sept. 2015). “Lyman α Emission from a Luminous $z = 8.68$ Galaxy: Implications for Galaxies as Tracers of Cosmic Reionization”. In: *ApJL* 810.1, L12, p. L12. DOI: [10.1088/2041-8205/810/1/L12](https://doi.org/10.1088/2041-8205/810/1/L12). arXiv: [1507.02679](https://arxiv.org/abs/1507.02679) [astro-ph.GA].